

Adaptation of *Staphylococcus aureus* to Natural Environments and Aptamer- Based Sensing

*Adaptation de Staphylococcus aureus aux environnements naturels et
détection basée sur les aptamères*

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Titre : Adaptation de *Staphylococcus aureus* aux environnements naturels et détection basée sur les aptamères

Mots clés : *Staphylococcus aureus* ; Adaptation ; Aptamère ; Détection ; Sécurité alimentaire

Résumé : *Staphylococcus aureus* est une bactérie pathogène opportuniste qui constitue une menace majeure en sécurité alimentaire et en santé publique. De plus, cette bactérie possède un pouvoir d'adaptation lui permettant de persister et de survivre dans des environnements complexes, causant une grande variété de maladies chez l'Homme et chez l'animal. Face à ces défis, il est crucial de développer de nouvelles méthodes de détection rapide et fiable. L'émergence de souches multi-résistantes, combinée à leur capacité à se développer dans des matrices biologiques diverses exige des outils analytiques capables de dépister *S. aureus* directement dans ces environnements complexes. Les biosenseurs basés sur les aptamères sont un candidat prometteur pour atteindre cet objectif.

La première partie de cette thèse analyse l'adaptation de *Staphylococcus aureus* dans des environnements complexes riches en lipides, tels que le lait et le sérum. Ces environnements naturels remodelent la composition et la morphologie de l'enveloppe bactérienne et modifient la résistance au stress oxydatif ainsi que la résistance aux antibiotiques. Les résultats protéomiques comparatives révèlent des modifications importantes dans l'expression des protéines impliquées dans le métabolisme central du carbone, les voies biosynthétiques et les voies de fermentation dans les deux matrices par rapport BHI. Une régulation positive des facteurs de virulence et des protéines associées à la réponse au stress est également observée lorsque *S. aureus* est adapté au lait. Ces observations sont confirmées par l'étude de la létalité du pathogène dans un modèle d'infection en modèle insecte, mettant en évidence une forte corrélation entre la virulence de la souche bactérienne et sa capacité à s'adapter à différents environnements.

La seconde partie de cette thèse se concentre sur l'optimisation et l'analyse structurale

un aptamère nommé SA61, sélectionné spécifiquement pour se lier aux cellules de *S. aureus*. Cet aptamère est un oligomère d'ADN, possédant des propriétés de reconnaissance d'un épitope non identifié présent à la surface de *S. aureus*. Grâce à l'utilisation de techniques biophysiques telles que le dichroïsme circulaire, la spectroscopie UV, et la résonance magnétique nucléaire (RMN), une étude de la stabilité et de la structure de l'aptamère SA61 a été réalisée. Les résultats de ces travaux montrent que la séquence de l'aptamère SA61 forme un motif intercalé (motif-I) *in vitro*. Ces structures tétramériques d'ADN sont constituées de paires de bases C:C⁺ intercalées, se formant régulièrement avec des séquences riches en cytosine dans des conditions légèrement acides. Cette configuration particulière pourrait offrir une spécificité accrue à l'aptamère pour sa cible. Sur la base de ces données, la séquence initiale des nucléotides de SA61 a été modifiée pour optimiser son affinité de liaison pour *S. aureus*. Le motif-I se formant uniquement en conditions légèrement acides, des modifications chimiques de SA61 sont nécessaires pour stabiliser sa structure et améliorer son affinité pour se lier à *S. aureus* dans des conditions physiologiques. A ce jour, aucun motif-i spécifique à un biomarqueur pathogène n'a été clairement identifié ou étudié, ouvrant la voie à des investigations innovantes dans ce domaine.

Les résultats suggèrent que le développement d'un aptasenseur robuste, sélectif et sensible repose sur une compréhension des adaptations de *S. aureus* dans l'environnement naturel et l'optimisation structurale des aptamères. L'intégration de ces paramètres est cruciale pour concevoir des outils de détection efficaces et adaptés aux défis posés par cette bactérie pathogène.

Title : Adaptation of *Staphylococcus aureus* to Natural Environments and Aptamer-Based Sensing

Keywords : *Staphylococcus aureus* ; Adaptation ; Aptamer ; Detection ; Food Safety

Abstract : *Staphylococcus aureus* is an opportunistic pathogenic bacterium that poses a major threat to food safety and public health. Due to its remarkable adaptability, it can persist and survive in complex environments, causing a wide range of diseases in both humans and animals. The emergence of multidrug-resistant strains, combined with their ability to develop in diverse biological matrices, complicates traditional surveillance methods and highlights the need for rapid and reliable detection tools. Among these innovative approaches, aptamer-based biosensors represent a promising alternative.

The first part of this thesis investigates the adaptation of *S. aureus* in complex, lipid-rich environments such as milk and serum. These environments alter the composition and morphology of the bacterial membrane, influence oxidative stress resistance, and modulate antibiotic resistance. Comparative proteomic analysis reveals significant changes in the expression of proteins involved in central carbon metabolism, biosynthetic pathways, and fermentation processes. Furthermore, adaptation to milk induces an upregulation of virulence factors and stress-response proteins, as confirmed by pathogen lethality studies in an insect infection model. These findings highlight a strong correlation between bacterial virulence and its ability to adapt to complex environments.

The second part of this thesis focuses on the optimization and structural analysis of an aptamer named SA61, specifically selected for its ability to bind *S. aureus* cells. This DNA oligonucleotide targets an as-yet unidentified epitope present on the bacterial surface.

The second part of this thesis focuses on the optimization and structural analysis of an aptamer named SA61, specifically selected for its ability to bind *S. aureus* cells. This DNA oligonucleotide targets an as-yet unidentified epitope present on the bacterial surface. Using biophysical techniques such as circular dichroism, UV spectroscopy, and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), the structure and stability of SA61 were characterized. The results indicate that the aptamer adopts an intercalated motif (motif-I) *in vitro*, consisting of C:C+ base pairs, which are characteristic of cytosine-rich sequences under slightly acidic conditions. This unique architecture could enhance the aptamer's specificity for *S. aureus*. Based on these findings, nucleotide modifications were introduced to improve its binding affinity and stability. To date, no motif-I specific to a pathogenic biomarker has been clearly identified or studied, opening the door to further innovative research in this field.

The results obtained suggest that the development of a robust, selective, and sensitive aptasensor relies on a deep understanding of *S. aureus* adaptations to different environments, as well as on the optimization and thorough structural characterization of aptamers. This knowledge is crucial for designing targeted chemical modifications that are essential for the development of new detection tools. The integration of these parameters is fundamental to creating reliable diagnostic devices capable of addressing the challenges posed by this pathogenic bacterium.

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Abbreviations

A	Adenine	ELISA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
Å	Angström, 1 Å = 10 ⁻¹⁰ m	FA	Fatty acid
AMD	Age-related macular degeneration	FAO	the Food and Agriculture Organization of The United Nations
AMR	Antimicrobial resistance	FASII	Type II fatty acid pathway
AuNPs	Gold Nanoparticles	FRET	Förster resonance energy transfer
BCFAs.	Branched-chain fatty acids	G	Guanine
BHI	Brain Heart Infusion	G4	G-quadruplex
C	Cytosine	I-motif	Intercalated-motif
CD	Circular dichroism	K_d	Equilibrium dissociation constant
CFU	Colony forming unit	LAMP	Loop-mediated isothermal amplification
CL	Cardiolipin	LA-MRSA	Livestock-associated MRSA
CRET	Chemiluminescence resonance energy transfer	LFIA	Lateral flow immunoassay
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid	LSPR	Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance
DPV	Differential Pulse Voltammetry	LTA	Lipoteichoic acid
ECL	Electrochemiluminescence	MALDI-TOF-MS	Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrophotometry

EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy	MGEs	Mobile genetic elements
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay	SCVs	small colony variants
MRSA	Methicillin resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	SE	Staphylococcal enterotoxins
MSCRAMMs	Microbial Surface Components Recognizing Adhesive Matrix Molecules	SELEX	Systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment
NGS	Next generation sequencing	SERS	Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance	SFP	Staphylococcal Food Poisoning
NSET	Nanometal surface energy transfer	SpA	Staphylococcal Protein A
RNA	Ribo-deoxyribonucleic acid	SPIA	Single primer isothermal amplification
ROS	Reactive oxygen species	T	Thymine
PAGE	Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis	TSS	Toxic Shock syndrom
PBP2a	Penicillin-Binding Protein	VEGF-	Vascular endothelial growth factor
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction	WHO	World Heart Organisation
PG	Phosphatidyl-glycerol		
REASSURED	Real-time Connectivity, Ease of specimen collection, Affordable, Sensitive, Specific, User friendly, Rapid, Equipment free, and Delivered		
SAB	<i>S. aureus</i> bacteremia		

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Introduction générale

La résistance aux antibiotiques apparaît lorsque les bactéries s'adaptent et acquièrent des modifications génétiques qui les rendent insensibles aux agents antimicrobiens. L'usage excessif et inapproprié des antibiotiques dans le monde a accéléré l'émergence de l'antibiorésistance (AMR). En conséquence, les infections bactériennes deviennent de plus en plus difficiles à traiter. De plus, l'AMR représente un coût direct considérable pour les systèmes de santé, estimé à plus de 66 milliards de dollars par an (Mcdonnell et al., 2024). Si les tendances actuelles se maintiennent, ce coût pourrait atteindre 159 milliards de dollars par an d'ici 2050, avec des répercussions majeures sur la croissance économique dans les régions les plus touchées (Vollset et al., 2024).

Sur le plan humain, 4,71 millions de décès étaient associés à l'AMR bactérienne en 2022, dont 1,15 million directement attribuables à cette résistance. Les projections estiment que d'ici 2050, 1,91 million de décès seront directement causés par l'AMR, avec 8,22 millions de décès supplémentaires liés indirectement à cette problématique (Vollset et al., 2024 ; Naghavi et al., 2024). L'Organisation mondiale de la santé (OMS) a ainsi établi une liste de pathogènes résistants aux antibiotiques responsables d'infections nosocomiales, regroupés sous l'acronyme ESKAPEE (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter spp.*, *Escherichia coli*) (De Oliveira et al., 2020).

Parallèlement, de nombreux pathogènes d'origine alimentaire sont responsables de maladies contractées via des produits contaminés ou insuffisamment cuits. Chaque année, 600 millions de cas de maladies d'origine alimentaire et 420 000 décès leur sont attribués dans le monde (Ikuta et al., 2022). Selon l'OMS, ces maladies engendrent une perte de productivité et des coûts médicaux estimés à 110 milliards de dollars par an dans les pays à revenu faible et intermédiaire, et à 15,5 milliards de dollars aux États-Unis uniquement (WHO, 2015 ; Hoffmann, 2015). Ces données soulignent que la sécurité alimentaire constitue une priorité majeure pour le secteur agroalimentaire. Des pathogènes tels qu'*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* et

Staphylococcus aureus sont parmi les principaux acteurs de ces enjeux de santé publique. Les changements climatiques constituent un autre facteur aggravant. Ils favorisent l'émergence de nouveaux pathogènes capables de s'adapter à des environnements extrêmes.

Les conditions climatiques influent sur la température, l'humidité et les régimes météorologiques, ce qui affecte la survie et la réplication des microbes, tout en accélérant les transferts de gènes de résistance. Cela se traduit par une augmentation des infections d'origine alimentaire et hydrique ainsi qu'une efficacité réduite des traitements antibiotiques (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2024).

Face à ces enjeux, l'OMS a mis en place la stratégie « One Health », qui repose sur la reconnaissance des interactions étroites entre la santé humaine, animale et environnementale. Ce concept prend une importance croissante dans un contexte marqué par le changement climatique, l'augmentation de la population mondiale, la raréfaction des ressources naturelles et les pressions sanitaires accrues (Figure 1).

C'est dans ce cadre que s'inscrit mon projet doctoral au sein du consortium DIM1Health-2021. L'objectif de ce projet est de développer un outil de diagnostic rapide, simple d'utilisation et à faible coût, basé sur un dispositif électrochimique utilisant des aptamères (courtes séquences d'ADN) capables de reconnaître différents épitopes présents à la surface des cellules de *Staphylococcus aureus*. Une telle approche permettrait une détection quantitative de cette bactérie, aussi bien dans des matrices alimentaires complexes comme le lait que dans des fluides biologiques tels que le sérum.

Mon travail s'est ainsi focalisé sur deux axes complémentaires : d'une part, l'étude du comportement de *S. aureus* dans des environnements hôtes modèles (le lait cru et le sérum bovin adulte), afin de mieux comprendre son adaptation dans ces milieux complexes riches en lipides ; et d'autre part, l'optimisation structurale d'un

aptamère spécifique ciblant *S. aureus*, afin d'améliorer sa stabilité et son affinité de liaison pour le développement futur d'un aptasenseur performant.

Staphylococcus aureus est un pathogène à Gram positif en forme de cocci, hautement versatile et préoccupant pour la santé humaine et animale. Les souches résistantes à la méthicilline (MRSA) sont particulièrement répandues et représentent un défi majeur pour les hôpitaux (Otto, 2012). *S. aureus* est capable de provoquer une large gamme d'infections allant de simples lésions cutanées à des septicémies graves. Chez les animaux, il est également une cause majeure de mammite, une pathologie douloureuse qui a des conséquences économiques importantes, puisque le lait contaminé n'est pas propre à la consommation humaine (Martins et al., 2019).

Outre son rôle dans les infections, *S. aureus* peut produire des entérotoxines responsables d'intoxications alimentaires. Contrairement à d'autres bactéries telles que *Salmonella* ou *Campylobacter*, se sont principalement les toxines, plutôt que la bactérie elle-même, qui sont responsables de l'intoxication alimentaire. Ces toxines sont particulièrement problématiques car elles résistent à la chaleur et survivent donc à la pasteurisation (Argudín, Mendoza, et Rodicio, 2010).

Compte tenu de sa pathogénicité remarquable et de sa capacité d'adaptation, il devient urgent de développer de nouveaux outils de détection optimisés pour des analyses rapides, sensibles et peu coûteuses. Parmi ces alternatives, les aptamères apparaissent comme des éléments de reconnaissance particulièrement prometteurs. Ces molécules synthétiques offrent une grande spécificité et sélectivité, combinées à une stabilité chimique élevée. Elles constituent ainsi une alternative attractive aux anticorps, dont la production reste coûteuse.

Néanmoins, malgré l'intérêt croissant et de nombreuses publications sur le sujet, aucun aptasenseur commercial n'est encore disponible pour la détection de pathogènes. Cela s'explique notamment par la grande capacité d'adaptation de bactéries comme *S. aureus*, qui modifient l'expression et la structure de leurs protéines

selon l'environnement, compliquant la spécificité de détection. Par ailleurs, les matrices complexes telles que le lait ou le sérum peuvent induire des changements conformationnels dans les aptamères eux-mêmes, compromettant leurs performances.

De plus, la structure tridimensionnelle des aptamères reste souvent prédite par modélisation *in silico*, ce qui peut donner des résultats variables selon les logiciels utilisés. De récents progrès ont néanmoins permis d'accéder à des analyses structurales plus poussées, améliorant la compréhension et la performance des aptamères dans le cadre de biosenseurs (Troisi et al., 2023).

Depuis 2009, l'intérêt scientifique pour l'utilisation d'aptamères dans la détection de *S. aureus* est en forte croissance (Figure 2). La détection rapide et spécifique de ce pathogène constitue l'une des solutions les plus prometteuses pour développer de nouvelles stratégies de contrôle.

La première partie de ce manuscrit propose une revue de la littérature : elle introduit *S. aureus* et ses pathologies majeures (septicémie, mammite, intoxications alimentaires), passe en revue les méthodes de détection existantes, et se conclut par une synthèse sur les aptamères validés pour la détection de ce pathogène. Deux publications de revue signées en tant que premier auteur y sont intégrées. La première présente une méta-analyse de la prévalence de *S. aureus* dans les aliments, et la seconde discute des avancées récentes des aptasenseurs.

La deuxième partie est consacrée à l'étude de l'adaptation de *S. aureus* dans le lait et le sérum, deux environnements modèles pertinents respectivement pour la santé animale et la sécurité alimentaire. Les résultats obtenus montrent que *S. aureus* adapte son comportement en fonction du milieu, ce qui a un impact sur sa détection. Ces résultats ont donné lieu à une publication incluse dans ce manuscrit.

Enfin, la troisième partie explore l'optimisation structurale d'un aptamère spécifique de *S. aureus*. Grâce à diverses techniques biophysiques (dichroïsme circulaire, spectroscopie de fluorescence, analyses de température de fusion, RMN), j'ai

caractérisé la structure et la stabilité de l'aptamère SA61. Des modifications de séquence ont ensuite été réalisées afin d'améliorer son affinité de liaison, validée par anisotropie de fluorescence. Ces résultats ouvrent la voie à la conception d'aptasenseurs plus fiables et performants.

La dernière section de ce manuscrit discute les perspectives futures, les limites rencontrées et les applications possibles de ces travaux pour le développement de nouvelles stratégies de détection. Enfin, une annexe présente mes contributions annexes, incluant participations à des projets collaboratifs, conférences, enseignements et publications cosignées.

General introduction

General introduction

Antibiotic resistance occurs when bacteria adapt and acquire genetic modifications, rendering them insensitive to antimicrobial agents. The misuse and overuse of antibiotics worldwide have accelerated the emergence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). As a result, bacterial infections are becoming increasingly difficult to treat. Moreover, AMR imposes a significant direct healthcare cost, currently estimated at over 66 billion dollars per year (Mcdonnell et al. 2024). It was estimated that in case the current trends continue, this cost could reach 159 billion dollars per year by 2050, with serious implications for economic growth in regions most affected by AMR (Vollset et al. 2024).

Moreover, 4.71 million human deaths were associated with bacterial AMR including 1.15 million deaths attributable to bacterial AMR in 2022 alone. It is estimated that by 2050, the number of deaths attributable to AMR will rise 1.91 million with an additional 8.22 million deaths associated with antimicrobial resistance. (Vollset et al. 2024; Naghavi et al. 2024). The World Health Organization (WHO) has established a list of antibiotic resistant pathogens, primarily responsible for nosocomial infections, known as the ESKAPEE pathogens (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia coli*) (De Oliveira et al. 2020).

Additionally, many foodborne pathogens are responsible for a wide range of diseases caused by contaminated and undercooked products. According to the WHO, each year, unsafe food leads to 600 million cases of foodborne diseases and 420 000 deaths globally (Ikuta et al. 2022). Furthermore, the WHO estimates that foodborne diseases cost 110 billion dollars per year in lost productivity and medical expenses in low- and middle-income countries, and 15.5 billion dollars in United States alone (World Health Organization 2015b; Hoffmann 2015).

These data indicate that food safety is a priority in the agri-food sector. Foodborne pathogens, such as *Escherichia coli*, *pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* are major contributors to these public health issues.

Moreover, global climate change may lead to the emergence of new pathogens better adapted to extreme environments. Climatic conditions affect temperature, humidity and weather patterns which can influence pathogen replication and survival, while also accelerating the exchange of resistance genes between microbes. This can lead in an increase in food- and water- borne infections and reduced antibiotics efficacy (Mukhopadhyay et al. 2024)

Figure 1. “One health” concept. It is based on a simple principle: protecting human health requires safeguarding animal health and their interactions with the environment.

Altogether, it is evident that there is an urgent need to find new resources and solutions to combat the spreading of foodborne pathogens and their resistant genes. The “One Health” strategy was implemented by the WHO to address this issue,

recognizing the inseparable interactions between environmental, human and animal health (Figure 1). This concept has gained prominence in the context of climate change, population growth, rarefication of natural resources and increased health pressure on both human and animal populations.

It is within this context that I am participating in the DIM1Health-2021 project for my Ph.D. This project aims to develop a fast and user-friendly diagnostic based on an electrochemical setup using specific aptamers (short DNA sequences) that recognize different epitopes on *S. aureus* cells. The fast diagnostic method will enable the quantitative detection of this bacterium in food samples (such as milk) or in biological fluids (such as serum). Therefore, I focused in this project on two model host environments, adult bovine serum and raw cow milk, and the structural optimization of a specific aptamer binding *S. aureus* cells.

S. aureus is a Gram-positive, coccus-shaped bacterium and a highly versatile pathogen in both human and animal. It is a major health concern due to its accrued resistance to antibiotics, particularly, methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* strains (MRSA), which are largely widespread in hospitals (Otto 2012). The fight against this pathogen has been a major concern for health security for decades. Indeed, *S. aureus* can cause a wide range of illnesses, from minor skin infections to septicemia. It is also a leading cause of mastitis in farm animals, a disease that poses significant complications for animals, primarily due to the painful condition it induces. Additionally, milk from animals with mastitis cannot be used for human consumption, which has a substantial impact on the global economy (Martins et al. 2019).

Moreover, *S. aureus* can secrete enterotoxins that are frequently responsible for food poisoning. Unlike other bacteria, such as *Salmonella* or *Campylobacter*, food intoxication caused by *S. aureus* is primarily due to the toxins produced, rather than the bacterium itself. These toxins pose a significant risk for milk contamination because they are heat resistant and in consequence can survive to pasteurization (Argudín, Mendoza, and Rodicio 2010). Due to its remarkable pathogenicity and adaptability to

different environments and treatments, it has become urgent to develop new detection systems optimized for rapid, low cost and point-of-care bacterial detection. Among these, detection systems can be enhanced by using aptamers as promising recognition elements. These synthetic molecules provide a highly specific adaptable approach for identifying *S. aureus* and its toxins.

Aptamers are synthetic nucleic acid molecules that have been selected by the SELEX (Systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment) method, to bind specifically and with high affinity a target. DNA aptamers offer an attractive alternative to expensive antibodies for bacterial targeting, as they provide not only good sensitivity and selectivity but also a high chemical stability in solution. Over the past decades, there has been growing interest in using aptamers for the development of biosensors for detection purposes.

Despite numerous scientific publications, there is a notable absence of commercially available aptasensor for pathogen detection. This can be attributed to the ability of bacteria, particularly *S. aureus*, to adapt easily to different environments, altering protein expression and structure, which may hinder the specificity of detection. Moreover, detection can be further compromised in complex matrices that may induce structural modifications in the aptamer itself.

Aptamer structure is frequently unknown or relies on computational modeling, which may produce inconsistent results depending on the software used. Nevertheless, in recent years, there has been a strong push to resolve aptamer structures through more advanced techniques, improving the reliability and performance of aptamer-based biosensor (Troisi et al. 2023). The available studies often present certain gaps, and a understanding of these DNA molecules could facilitate the development of improved aptamers (Lakhin, Tarantul, and Gening 2013).

Since 2009, there has been a growing interest in the detection of *S. aureus* using aptamers (Figure 2). Indeed, the rapid identification of *S. aureus* with aptamers represents one of the promising solutions for developing new control strategies.

Figure 2. Number of publications from 2005 to 2025 on *S. aureus* detection using aptamers based on PubMed keyword searches (“Aptamer,” “Detection,” and *S. aureus*”). This illustrates the growing interest in aptamer-based detection technologies over time.

The first part of this manuscript will present a literature review, beginning with a general introduction to *S. aureus*, highlighting important diseases caused by this bacterium such as septicemia and mastitis together with the consequences of food contamination with *S. aureus* for the food industry. Next, I will present the existing *S. aureus* detection methods. The final part will focus on aptamers, providing a review of the current aptamers selected and validated for *S. aureus* detection. To complement this section, two review publications which I sign as the first author, are included. The first review (Manuscript 1) presents a meta-analysis of the prevalence of *S. aureus* isolates from various food sources, while the second (Manuscript 2) review discusses recent advances in aptamer-based biosensors for bacterial detection.

In the second chapter, I investigated the adaptation of *S. aureus* to serum and milk. Serum serves as an interesting infection model, particularly in the context of sepsis and milk is highly relevant to the food industry, where *S. aureus* contamination can lead to important economic losses. The observed differences confirm that *S. aureus* behaves differently depending on its adaptation to the surrounding environment. These changes may influence the specificity of detection. The results underscore the importance of considering environmental factors for developing robust detection systems based on aptamers. A publication detailing this research is included in this section (Manuscript 3).

The third chapter, I explored the structural optimization of a specific aptamer that was selected to bind *S. aureus* cells. By employing a range of biophysical techniques, including circular dichroism, fluorescent spectroscopy, melting temperature analysis and NMR spectroscopy, I characterized the stability and structure of this aptamer named SA61. Based on these structural findings, the initial nucleotide sequence was modified to enhance the binding affinity (K_d) of the aptamer for *S. aureus*. The modifications were validated using fluorescent anisotropy. One of the key challenges to develop an aptasensor is the need for more detailed studies of aptamer structure to identify potential areas of chemical modifications that could stabilize the structure and improve the analytical performance. A pre-publication detailing this research is included (Manuscript 4).

The final section presents the conclusions of this work and its future perspectives. It summarizes the key findings of the research, emphasizing their potential applications in the field of bacterial detection and diagnostics. Additionally, this section discusses the limitations and difficulties encountered during the study.

Following this, an appendix is included, showcasing other contributions made during this PhD, such as participation in collaborative projects, conferences, formations, teaching and published articles that I sign as co-author.

Part I

State of the art

Chapter 1

Staphylococcus aureus

1. *Staphylococcus aureus*

1.1 Discovery & general characteristics

Staphylococcus aureus, also called “Golden Staph” is an important pathogen that has a significant impact on the global health. It is one of the most well documented bacteria nowadays with more than 160,000 articles and scientific reviews. *S. aureus* was first identified and isolated in 1880 by the Scottish surgeon Sir Alexander Ogston from pus (Ogston 1881). The “bunch of grapes” circular in shape and arranged in clusters led to Ogston to name this bacterium “staphylococci”(Figure 3). In 1884, Friedrich Rosenbach isolated and cultured two strains of staphylococci from humans samples (Rosenbach, 1884). Due to his discovery, this physician named the pathogen *S. aureus* based, on the gold pigmented appearance of its colonies (Rasheed and Hussein 2021).

Figure 3: Alexander Ogston (1844-1929) on the left (Jon Hebditch – *Aberdeen & Aberdeenshire journal*) and *S. aureus* morphology and clustering under scanning electron microscopy on the right. Scanning electron microscopy performed at MIMA2 platform in MICALIS Institute.

S. aureus is a Gram positive coccus (0.5-1.5 μm in diameter) and belongs to the phylum *bacillota* – formerly *Firmicutes* (Gibbons and Murray 1978; Oren and Garrity 2021), with more 60 species. Staphylococci are facultative anaerobic organisms, non-sporing and non-motile and can be found ubiquitously in warm-blooded animals and in the environment, especially in food. This pathogen is not demanding for optimal growth, which occurs between 30°C to 37°C at pH 7.0-7.5, but it can adapt to more extreme environment (JE2 strain used in this study can be cultivated at 42-43°C). For

example, in humans, this pathogen is part of the commensal flora, mainly found in the nose, hands and on mucous membranes., but it can colonize the entire host, from the skin to the cellular compartments. It is estimated that 30% to 50% of the population are healthy carriers. This bacterium causes a wide range of infections, from simple ones like conjunctivitis or abscesses to renal and cardiac infections, and even sometimes septicemia (figure 4).

Figure 4. Infections in humans caused by *S. aureus*. This bacterium is present on nearly the entire skin surface causing a wide range of disease. Adapted from (Alghizzi and Shami 2023)

1.2 A major pathogen

1.2.1 A Major Global Infection Problem

Immunodeficient people, such as elderly or newborns, are more susceptible to *S. aureus*. infections. This pathogen is responsible of comminatory and nosocomial diseases. The incidence of *S. aureus* bacteremia (SAB) is currently estimated to be between 9.3 and 65 per 100,000 people per year (Hindy et al. 2022). These data mainly concern developed countries and are underestimated due to the limited data available low-income countries. In France, it is a common bacteria responsible for food

poisoning due to the enterotoxins it can release (Hennekinne 2018). The toxins can also be secreted *in situ* in the host, causing severe clinical symptoms such as Toxic Shock Syndrome (TSS) (Otto 2014b). Due to its significant adaptability to its environment, *S. aureus* has developed numerous resistance mechanisms, notably antibiotic resistance, which is a major challenge in the treatment of these bacterial infections in hospitals. These characteristics have led *S. aureus* to become part of a group of six virulent and resistant bacteria known by the acronym ESKAPE (M Campos, Antunes, and Ferreira 2020).

1.2.2 Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

In the 1940s and 1950s, the emergence of penicillin and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* strains (PRSA & MRSA respectively) in hospitals was a consequence of the introduction of antibiotics (Fleming 1929; Kirby 1944). Indeed, all β -lactam antibiotics are inactivated by the acquisition of the *mecA* gene through horizontal gene transfer. This gene encodes a novel Penicillin-Binding Protein (PBP2a) involved in peptidoglycan crosslinking. Mutations in *mecA* result in a low affinity of P2P for β -lactam antibiotics, leading to high resistance to these drugs (Turner et al. 2019).

Figure 5. Antibiotic resistance timeline for *S. aureus*. In 1943, The first Penicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (PRSA) strain was reported in 1943 (Rammelkamp and Maxon 1942). This was followed

by the emergence of Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strain in 1961 (Jevons 1961). An increase in community-onset MRSA infections was noted (H. Chambers 2001) and in 2022, Vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus* (VRSA) strain was identified (S. Chang et al. 2003).

Moreover, the resistant strains exhibit increased pathogenicity and can disseminate more easily into new vulnerable populations, causing a global health problem (H. F. Chambers and DeLeo 2009; Turner et al. 2019). With each new antibiotic administered, *S. aureus* rapidly developed resistance further confirming its high adaptability, due to its genetic flexibility (Figure 5): MRSA strains acquired vancomycin resistance through the transfer of the Tn1546 transposon, which encodes the vancomycin resistance gene *vanA* (Weigel et al. 2003).

Figure 6. Global number of deaths in 2019 among 33 bacterial pathogens. This graphic shows total number of deaths for each pathogen, with error bars representing the 95% confidence intervals. In red, *S. aureus* is the pathogens responsible for the most deaths among these 33. LRI=Lower respiratory infection. UTI= Urinary tract infection. iNTS=Invasive non-typhoidal *Salmonella*. CNS=Central Nervous System (Ikuta et al. 2022).

In 2024, The WHO continues to categorize MRSA as a high-priority pathogen, notably due to its significant estimated burden with a study in 2019 reporting 819,000-1,470,000 all-cause deaths (Figure 6) (Ikuta et al. 2022; WHO Bacterial Priority

Pathogens List 2024 Bacterial Pathogens of Public Health Importance, to Guide Research, Development, and Strategies to Prevent and Control Antimicrobial Resistance 2024).

In this work, we primarily used the USA300-MRSA strain (also known as JE2), which emerged during the 1990s (Carrel, Perencevich, and David 2015). This strain is predominant in the USA and among hospitalized children. This clone is spreading in hospitals and is responsible for nosocomial infections (Tenover and Goering 2009). Despite sporadic importation from the USA, there is no propagation in Europe, particularly in France (Glaser et al. 2016)

1.3 An arsenal of virulence factors

Figure 7. Host-specific virulence factors and their roles in evasion of the innate immunity. From (Buchan, Foster, and Renshaw 2019)

The diversity of infections diversity caused by *S. aureus* is due to its pathogenic potential, linked to biosynthesis of numerous virulence factors. These factors are involved in essential steps of host infection, from adhesion to invasion step, as well as escaping the host immune system (Figure 7), nutrient acquisition, intracellular survival and competition with other microorganisms. Moreover, this bacterium developed specific virulence factor depending of the host immunity (Figure 5) (Buchan, Foster, and

Renshaw 2019). *S. aureus* has more 100 weapons described with a repartition in two different categories: the cell surface factors and the secreted factors.

1.3.1 Cell surface factors

S. aureus expresses cell surface factors that play a role in its virulence. The Microbial Surface Components Recognizing Adhesive Matrix Molecules (MSCRAMMs) (Patti et al. 1994) These proteins are anchored to the cell wall, with the most well-known being Staphylococcal Protein A (SpA) (Bear et al. 2023; Buchan, Foster, and Renshaw 2019). Another important virulence cell surface factor, that we will mention more deeply later is the carotenoid pigment staphyloxanthin (Figure 8), which have a function in the resistance to host defense peptides and reactive oxygen species (ROS: H₂O₂, ClO⁻, OH) produced by neutrophils (Figure 7) (Buchan, Foster, and Renshaw 2019). Additionally, this pigment is responsible for the coloration of 90% of *S. aureus* strains and also increases its virulence (Song et al. 2009; Xue et al. 2019). Interestingly, staphyloxanthin is also involved in fitness of *S. aureus* envelop and can modify cell wall permeability and membrane fluidity (Mishra et al. 2011). This molecule requires the fatty acid biosynthesis (FASII) pathway for its synthesis. The final step involves the esterification of a molecule of glucose with the carboxyl group of the fatty acid (FA) anteiso C15:0, i.e., *ai*15. This FA is primarily biosynthesis naturally by the bacteria. It appears that the media, and also *S. aureus* acetate metabolism, have an impact on the staphyloxanthin production but the FA composition does not have a significant effect (Tiwari, Gatto, and Wilkinson 2018).

Staphyloxanthin

Figure 8. Staphyloxanthin molecule. This pigment is composed of two long carbon chains and is responsible for the golden color of 90% of *S. aureus* strains. It can act as virulence factor. Adapted from Xue et al., 2019.

1.3.2 Secreted factors

S. aureus has the faculty to secrete toxins or enterotoxins, which play a role in disarming host immunity. Indeed, they disrupt host cells and tissues and interact with host immune system to liberate nutriment to facilitate bacteria dissemination. They are usually classified in four categories: Cytotoxins, Superantigens, Enzymes and co-factors (More information (Dinges, Orwin, and Schlievert 2000; Tam and Torres 2019))

1.4 An array of resistance and adaptation mechanisms

S. aureus is a bacterium that adapt to diverse environmental conditions, including food. The pathogen is extremely halotolerant. Indeed, it have been shown that *S. aureus* can grow in the presence of NaCl concentrations as high as 3,5M. Its ability to survive in such conditions explains some food poisoning, as *S. aureus* can proliferate in salty environments such as cured meats (Scybert et al. 2003).

Figure 9. – Host-switching modelling of *S. aureus* between species. Human act as a major hub for *S. aureus* host jumps. Those who interact with domesticated livestock and companion animals constitute a significant point of exchange. The thickness of the arrows indicates the frequency of host-switching (Howden et al. 2023)

In animal and human hosts, *S. aureus* encounters major stress factors, including oxidative stress, lipid stress and pH variations. To counter these stress challenges, the pathogen has developed specific adaptation mechanisms. It possesses a large number of immune evasion strategies in contrast to other bacterial pathogens (Cheung, Bae, and Otto 2021). *S. aureus* also exhibits other lifestyles such as forming biofilms, which contribute to its pathogenesis. Biofilms are responsible for chronic infections and can be developed on both abiotic and biotic surfaces and interphases. Such a lifestyle allows the bacterium to protect themselves from the environment (Shen et al. 2021). Moreover, its genetic flexibility is well-suited to host specificity and adaptation. Indeed, recent advances in agricultural practices have increased transmission risks between humans and livestock (Figure 9)

Figure 10. Acquisition of MGEs by *S. aureus*. (1) Incorporation of plasmids or plasmid elements into genomic DNA. (2) Plasmids can be maintained as free circular DNA. (3) Suicide plasmid. (4) Transfer of transposon or an insertion sequence between plasmid and genomic DNA. (5) Transfer of a transposon or an insertion sequence between plasmids within the cell. (6) Transfer of a transposon or an insertion sequence from genomic DNA to another plasmid.

The *S. aureus* genome is circular and consists of about 2.8 Mb with around 2,600 genes. Its structure is highly conserved, with small variable regions. Genes that confer virulence and antibiotic resistance are often derived from extrachromosomal elements

Figure 11. Molecular mechanism of antibiotic resistance in *S. aureus* Antimicrobial resistance occurs due to various cellular adaptations, including the inactivation of β -lactam antibiotics by β -lactamase, target modification via the production of penicillin-binding protein PBP2A, bypass mechanisms (FASII), alterations in efflux pump activity,, decreased membrane permeability to block the passive transport of antibiotic molecules and biofilm formation. These adaptations often result from MGEs (Léguillier et al. 2024).

(Lindsay and Holden 2004). The genetic flexibility leads also to multi-resistance to antibiotics and has become the main reason why *S. aureus* infections are difficult to treat. Comparative genomics of *S. aureus* shows that around 25% of its DNA have mobile genetic elements (MGEs) such as transposons, plasmids; chromosomal

cassettes, bacteriophages or Staphylococcal pathogenicity islands (SaPIs) (Malachowa and DeLeo 2010) (Figure 10). This issue represents an important medical and economic challenge, driving the scientist community to find new therapeutic strategies (Salam et al. 2023). Despite these new strategies, *S. aureus* has developed numerous antimicrobial resistance mechanisms (Figure 11). Some bacterial variants of *S. aureus*, known as small colony variants (SCVs) arise from mutations in metabolic genes (around 1%). By definition, SCVs form small colonies on nutrient agar due to their slow growth and reduced metabolism (Proctor et al. 2006). These variants are not always virulent because they express fewer toxins, but they express more surface proteins allowing *S. aureus* to persist in host cells (Melter and Radojevič 2010; Proctor et al. 2006). They are often associated with chronic osteomyelitis and cystic fibrosis lung infections.

1.5 The fatty acid synthesis (FASII) pathway

Human and animal hosts are rich in FAs, which play an essential role in every living organism. FAs are necessary for the production of phospholipids, which are part of the membrane, such as the lipoteichoic acid, pigments and more. It's crucial for the bacterium to produce FAs for its growth and survival. The study of the FAs pathway is motivated by the search of new molecules capable to inhibiting *S. aureus* growth, with the hope to discovering new treatments alternative than classic antibiotics. FASII pathway is an interesting target in *S. aureus* because it is distinct from FASI, the fatty acid synthesis pathway mainly found in eucaryotes. This difference allows for the development of selective inhibitors targeting *S. aureus* without affecting the host.

1.5.1 The fatty acids: definition

FAs have structural functions as constituents of phospholipids. In a stressful environment, microorganisms can maintain their biological properties which may implicate changes in membrane protein composition for example, but it is mainly due to alterations in the lipid composition of their membrane (Hazel and Williams 1990). By modifying the FAs in membrane phospholipids, cells try to maintain fluidity through a mechanism named "homeoviscous adaptation" (Barbarek et al. 2024).

Figure 12. Three principal phospholipids of *S. aureus*. The phosphatidyl-glycerol (PG) is linked to transmembrane protein and serves as a precursor for lipoteichoic acid (LTA) synthesis (Parsons et al. 2013) – Cardiolipin (CL) has a distinct angle that induces significant deformation in the plasma membrane. This molecule has various function including stabilizing liposomes and membrane proteins (Tsai et al. 2011; Yeo et al. 2023). Lysyl-phosphatidyl-glycerol (L-PG) synthesized more under mildly acidic conditions, potentially playing a protective role (Rehal et al. 2017).

S. aureus is capable to synthesizing branched-chain fatty acids (BCFAs). As mentioned before saturated FAs *anteiso* 15 (*ai*15) is the principal FA synthesized by this bacterium. The FAs present in the phospholipids of the *bacilotta* are in general composed of 12 to 22 carbons. The main phospholipids found in the *S. aureus* membrane are the cardiolipin (CL), phosphatidyl-glycerol (PG) and the Lysyl-phosphatidyl-glycerol (L-PG) (Kuhn, Slavetinsky, and Peschel 2015) (Figure 12).

**Saturated fatty acid
16:0 - Palmitic acid**

**Unsaturated fatty acid
16:1 - Palmitoleic acid**

T

Figure 13. Examples of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids.

1.5.2 The plasma membrane and fatty acids: a vector of fluidity

The plasma membrane is amphiphilic, a characteristic derived from the phospholipids, which have a polar head group and hydrophobic FA tails. These phospholipids form bilayers in aqueous environments (De Carvalho and Caramujo 2018). This semi-permeable barrier delimits the cytoplasm from the exterior. The composition of FAs impacts the rigidity of the membrane. Saturated FA favor increased rigidity because of the lack of double bonds and form straight chains. In contrast, the presence of double bonds in unsaturated fatty acids, will form a kink responsible of the membrane fluidity (Figure 13). This composition affects also the expression of some membranes proteins (L.-H. Wang et al. 2018).

1.5.3 The FASII pathway

The FASII pathway consists of three primary steps: initiation, where a short FA is synthesized; elongation, where four enzymes (FabG ; FabZ ; FabI, and FabF) lengthen the FA by adding two carbons in each cycle; termination, where the final FA is directed towards phospholipid synthesis enzymes (Figure 14) (Y.-M. Zhang and Rock 2008).

Initiation: The first step involves the conversion of acetyl-Coa to malonyl-Coa by a complex of enzyme acetyl-Coa carboxylase (AccBCDA) (Polyak et al. 2012). Then, the malonyl transacylase FabD catalyzes the replacement of the CoA group on the malonyl by ACP. Finally, the β -ketoacyl-ACP synthase (FabH) condenses the intermediate acyl-enzyme with malonyl-ACP to form the first β -ketoacyl-ACP intermediate to start FA elongation.

Figure 14. The *S. aureus* FASII pathway. This pathway comprises three main steps: Initiation, Elongation, and Termination. *S. aureus* can bypass this FASII pathway by utilizing exogenous FAs. The *fak* genes are essential for the phosphorylation of these exogenous FAs, while *PlsX* and *plsC* are necessary to ensure the bypass. Adapted from (Morvan et al. 2016)

Elongation: Four enzymatic reactions occur during the elongation process, with each cycle extending the FA acyl chains by two carbons. The cycle is initiated by another elongation condensing enzyme, the β -ketoacyl-ACP synthase FabF. Next, the β -ketoacyl-ACP is reduced to a β -hydroxyacyl-ACP by the β -ketoacyl-ACP reductase FabG. This is followed by the dehydration of the β -hydroxyacyl-ACP to a trans-2-enoyl-ACP by the β -hydroxyacyl-ACP dehydratase FabZ. Finally the elongation process is completed with the reduction of the trans-2-enoyl-ACP by the enoyl-ACP reductase (Morvan et al. 2016; Y.-M. Zhang and Rock 2008).

Termination: This final step in FA synthesis is the formation of the membrane phospholipids. The membrane protein Glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase, PlsX, converts Acyl-ACP to acyl-phosphate. This acyl-phosphate is used by PlsY to attach the acyl group to the first position of the glycerol phosphate. The second acyl group is added to the second position of the glycerol phosphate by PlsC (Y.-M. Zhang and Rock 2008).

This cycle is regulated by the FapR repressor, which controls the expression of the majority of FASII pathway enzymes, including FabD, FabG, FabI, FabF, PlsX and PlsC.. When the malonyl-Coa and malonyl-ACP accumulate, they bind to FapR, lifting the repression and allowing the enzymes to be expressed and the cycle to proceed (Pathania et al. 2021).

S. aureus is also capable to incorporate exogenous FAs from its environment to its phospholipids (DeMars, Singh, and Bose 2020). Indeed, FAs from sources such as serum and food can be used by *S. aureus*. The group of enzymes responsible of this exogenous incorporation are the FA kinase (Fak) (Figure 11) (Parsons et al. 2014).

1.5.4 Novel therapeutic strategies: Targeting phospholipid synthesis

The FAs are essential for bacterial survival, making the FASII pathway a prime for developing alternatives to classic antibiotic treatments. Among the various anti-FASII

agents available, FabI is the preferred target. One of these drugs is AFN-1252, an inhibitor of the FASII pathway. Despite promising results, the pathogen has developed strategies to bypass the FASII pathway and adapt to FASII treatment, such as acquiring mutations in the anti-FASII target and FASII enzymes (Morvan et al. 2016). Additionally, this adaptation is highlighted by an incorporation of exogenous FAs, rendering the FASII pathway enzymes dispensable and the anti-FASII treatment ineffective and a better resistance to unsaturated FAs toxicity (Krute et al. 2019; Morvan et al. 2017). Indeed, as with common mechanisms antibiotics resistance, the target can undergo mutations (J. Yao, Maxwell, and Rock 2013; J. Yao and Rock 2016). In *S. aureus* adaptation to its environment can occur through the incorporation of exogenous FAs, despite inhibition of FASII pathway. Specifically, when FASII is blocked, *S. aureus* rapidly acquire mutations in the *fabD*, gene, leading to an accumulation of ACP and favoring the incorporation of exogenous FAs (Gloux et al. 2017; Morvan et al. 2016).

To study the incorporation of exogenous fatty acid in different media, I created a deletion *fabD* mutant in the lab. This mutant represents a tool to study the behavior of the bacteria in different rich lipid-media such as in serum or in milk. With this mutant, we can better understand the mechanisms of adaptation as shown in Manuscript 3.

Chapter 2

***S. aureus*: sepsis and mastitis**

2. *S. aureus* sepsis and mastitis

S. aureus is a bacterium capable of adapting to various host, surviving in complex environments, and causing a wide range of diseases. It is the most frequently isolated bacterium responsible for septic shock. Cases of *S. aureus* sepsis have also been observed in wildlife, such as black rhinoceroses, great apes and mallards (Haag, Fitzgerald, and Penadés 2019). Another significant issue affecting the dairy industry, with substantial economic and food security impacts worldwide, is mastitis caused by *S. aureus*. In this section, we will discuss about the sepsis and mastitis impact on patients and agro-food industry.

2.1. Septic shock

S. aureus causes human skin and soft tissue infections as well as bacteremia (Figure 4) (Lowy 1998). Patients may encounter complications, potentially leading to endocarditis and sepsis diseases. These severe diseases are hard to treat with antibiotics and are usually associated with high mortality. Unfortunately *S. aureus* is the leading cause of death due to bacterial bloodstream infections with an estimated 300 000 deaths in 2019 (Ikuta et al. 2022) and a mortality rate around 20% and did not change since the 1990s (Figure 6) (Corey 2009; Thomer, Schneewind, and Missiakas 2016). Female patients are at higher risk of death. (Westgeest et al. 2024). The burden of this infection has also led to the emergence of MRSA clones as a consequence of therapeutic failure (Corey 2009).

Sepsis is a life-threatening condition characterized by the inflammatory response in the host with the goal to eradicate the intrusive pathogen. The patient may develop a septic shock when the pro-inflammatory response is too excessive causing organ failure. This pathogenicity is due to the arsenal of virulence factors (Chapter 1.3) facilitate the tissue adhesion, immune evasion and host cell injury. These factors cause in the host an inflammation, impair immune cell function, alter the blood coagulation

and compromise the vascular integrity (Figure 15) (McAdow et al. 2011; Powers and Wardenburg 2014).

Figure 15. Overview of *S. aureus* virulence factors contributing to sepsis pathogenesis. (a) – Phenol-soluble modulins (PSM) (Otto 2014a), α -hemolysin (Hla) (Berube and Wardenburg 2013) -which is highly virulent in MRSA strains and leukotoxins Panton-Valentin leukocidin (PVL) (Boyle-Vavra and Daum 2007), LukAB/GH and LukED (Vandenesch, Lina, and Henry 2012) all contribute to the stimulation of the leukocyte inflammatory response. (b) *S. aureus* employs various strategies to modulate innate host immune response by secreting proteins that either dampen leukocyte recruitment or prevent opsonophagocytic uptake, such as the Chemotaxis Inhibitory Protein of Staphylococci (CHIPS) (Spaan et al. 2013) and (c) - Staphylococcal Complement Inhibitor (SCIN) (Buchan, Foster, and Renshaw 2019). (d) – To limit the function of innate immune cells, *S. aureus* uses Staphylococcal protein A (Spa) (Bear et al. 2023). (e) -*S. aureus* encodes virulence factors that modulate coagulation pathways: Coagulate (Coa) (Khan et al. 2013) and Von Willebrand factor binding protein (vWbp) (Herrmann et al. 1997) promote the non-catalytic activation of prothrombin leading to fibrin clot formation, promoting the agglutination of *S. aureus* in the blood (ClfA and ClfB) (O’Brien et al. 2002) and enhances its survival in the bloodstream. –(f) As an immunodefense mechanism against staphylococcal bloodstream infections: platelet traps surround the bacteria which adhere to kupffer cells (Oyama et al. 2016). – (g) – Limited diffusion of soluble virulence factor which initiates coagulation in flowing blood and adheres to the vascular wall with the Fibronectin-binding protein A (FnBPA) (Speziale and Pietrocola 2020) – (h) Hla expression causes direct injury to the endothelium. Adapted from (Powers and Wardenburg 2014)

Moreover, the prospects to treating and protecting hosts against *S. aureus* sepsis are currently at a standstill. Antibiotics resistance, coupled with bacterium’s diverse array of virulence factors, has hampered the acquisition of a specialized vaccine, such as the one used against the diphtheria toxin of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* (Rappuoli and Malito 2014). Despite similar efforts, the development of an *S. aureus*

vaccine has not been successful (Clegg et al. 2021). due to the diversity of virulence factors secreted and the numerous strategies the bacterium employs to spread, especially in the bloodstream infections. Although new paths are currently being explored, there is an urgent need to improve prevention by developing rapid detection techniques, enabling quicker patient care and better monitoring of its spreading (Thomer, Schneewind, and Missiakas 2016).

2.2. Mastitis

In animal health, *S. aureus* is a leading cause of mastitis, a significant inflammation of the mammary gland, primarily resulting from an intramammary infection (as illustrated in Figure 16) (Campos et al. 2022). Different types of mastitis are defined based on the severity of the symptoms, ranging from simple inflammation of the mammary glands, through observable milk abnormalities, to infectious gangrene (Cobirka, Tancin, and Slama 2020).

Figure 16. Mastitis in dairy cows. Various causes of bovine mastitis, caused by environmental and infectious pathogen. An asterisk (*) indicates the primary causes of mastitis in cows. Adapted from (X. Li et al., n.d.).

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of The United Nations (FAO) (2023), several billion tons of milk are produced annually (Ritchie, Rosado, and

Roser, n.d.). As a result, the dairy industry represents a significant financial boon to the global economy. Cow’s milk is particularly notable in the dairy sector with more than half billion tons produced per year. This production is primarily driven by Asia (33,7%) and Europe (30,5%), followed by North America (21%). The remaining 14,8% is shared by Central and South America, Oceania and Africa (US Department of Agriculture). Altogether, exports of this production amount to over \$68 billion by 2022 (Figure 17).

Milk production, 2022

Figure 17. Total production of whole fresh milk in 2022. (Ritchie, Rosado, and Roser, n.d.)

Currently, milk production, like agricultural production in general, faces many challenges, including quality, preservation, improved animal welfare and sustainability. Among these, mastitis stands out as one of the main challenges in the dairy sector. Mastitis has a major impact on the dairy industry and the economy (Gomes and Henriques 2016; Ibrahim 2017). Clinical mastitis is not only one of the most common diseases affecting dairy cow, but it is also the most costly (Jamali et al. 2018). The economic impact is substantial: This infectious disease can compromise the quality, quantity and properties of milk production. Additionally, veterinary care, animal treatments, and diagnostics represent significant expenses for the dairy industry.

Indeed, mastitis alone accounts for approximately 60-70% of all antimicrobials administered on dairy farms (Tommasoni et al. 2023).

Antibiotic-resistant strains of *S. aureus* mastitis are commonly associated with mastitis infections. Indeed, studies have confirmed the presence of resistance genes, with a high prevalence *blaZ*, *tetM* and *ermC* in milk isolates (J. Gao 2012; Jamali 2014). It has also been reported that the prevalence of *S. aureus* mastitis intramammary infections ranges from 5% to 70% across various countries (Zecconi 2013). As previously mentioned, *S. aureus* exhibits a high degree of adaptability, and the diversity of mastitis-associated isolates is considerable (Rainard et al. 2018). Indeed, *S. aureus* mastitis in cattle can have severe consequences for human health, not necessarily due to the bacterium itself, but because of its toxins. Staphylococcal enterotoxins (SEs) secreted in milk remain stable, even after pasteurization. SEs produced by *S. aureus* strains proliferating in food product are generally considered to be heat-resistant and may persist in foods even after heat treatment (Necidová et al. 2019). Currently, 33 SE genes have been identified (Cieza et al. 2024). These genes are located in MGEs, reinforcing the notion of pathogen's adaptability (Dicks et al. 2021).

As with many disease, early detection of mastitis is crucial for effective treatment and minimizing the impact of milk production and the use of antibiotics. At the onset of infection, there is an elevation in somatic cell count (SCC), which serves as the primary marker for detecting and diagnosing mastitis (Sharma, Singh, and Bhadwal 2011). To detect an intramammary infection, classic bacteriologic culture and Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) are commonly used (Adkins and Middleton 2018). However, bacteriologic cultures can take between 1 to 10 days and have a limited sensitivity. In contrast, PCR is fast, and sensitive, capable of detecting DNA from dead bacteria but it is more expensive and need specific primers. (Adkins and Middleton 2018; Hiitiö 2016). Further development of rapid and sensitive diagnostics, as well as cost-effective tools to determine contagiousness, pathogenicity, or antibiotic

resistance, has become a key objective. Biosensor could play a crucial role in achieving these goals, enabling early detection and facilitating timely treatment.

2.3. Food contamination with *S. aureus*

Foodborne illness and diseases pose significant threats to human health, with over 200 different diseases being transmitted through food (Mead et al. 1999). It is estimated that there are 600 million cases of foodborne diseases and 420,000 deaths worldwide each year (H. Lee and Yoon 2021). In comparison, foodborne illnesses caused by bacteria are more frequent than diseases caused by viruses and parasites cumulated (World Health Organization 2015b). These data are concerning, as food and water are essential for the survival of all living beings, making it vital to ensure the protection of all consumers. Moreover, food safety incidents have a significant economy impact, resulting in losses of several billion dollars worldwide each year (Hussain and Dawson 2013). *Salmonella spp.*, *Campylobacter spp.*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* are currently the leading bacterial causes of foodborne illness (Ammar et al. 2021; Bintsis and Department of International Trade, TEI of West Macedonia, Kastoria, Greece 2017; Popa and Popa 2021; Ravindhiran et al. 2023; EFSA 2023).

Figure 18. Staphylococcal food poisoning (SFP). *S. aureus* can contaminate food from various sources (Left). Inadequate food preservation can facilitate bacterial replication and the

production of enterotoxins (middle). Consumption of these enterotoxins can result in food intoxication, typically causing gastroenteritis (Ali and Alsayeqh 2022).

Despite lower mortality than these caused by *L. monocytogenes* or *E. coli*, Staphylococcal Food Poisoning (SFP) is the most prevalent foodborne intoxication worldwide (Hennekinne 2018). An infection is caused by the multiplication a microorganism within the host, while an intoxication results from the ingestion of toxins produced by this microorganism. SFP is caused by ingestion of a sufficient amount of one or several staphylococcal enterotoxin secreted in food during growth of the organism (Ali and Alsayeqh 2022; Alexandra Fetsch and Johler 2018) (Figure 18). Enterotoxin production depends on several factors, including pH value, water activity (a_w), temperature and NaCl concentration (Table 1) (Adam and Moss 2008). Since enterotoxins are heat-stable and resistant to proteolytic enzymes like pepsin, they can persist and be ingested even if *S. aureus* is eliminated during pasteurization (Bennett 2005; Necidová et al. 2019). Additionally, contamination can occur through raw milk and cheese from dairy animals affected by *S. aureus* mastitis (Johler et al. 2015). The first symptoms appear between 1 to 7 hours (on average 3 hours) after contamination, including nausea, vomiting, headache, diarrhea, severe abdominal pain and prostration. The symptoms usually resolve spontaneously within 24 to 48h (Argudín, Mendoza, and Rodicio 2010). Occasionally, SFP can be severe enough to require hospitalization, particularly among the group of YOPIs (Young, old, pregnant, immunosuppressed persons) (A. Fetsch et al. 2014; Murray 2005). The control of this disease incurs significant economic costs. Indeed, it represents a considerable burden through lost workdays, productivity, hospital expenses, restaurant and financial losses in food industries, particularly in milk production (B. Y. Lee et al. 2013).

Factors	<i>S. aureus</i> growth		Enterotoxin production	
	Optimum	Range	Optimum	Range
Temperature (°C)	35.0-37.0	7.0-48.0	35.0-40.0	10.0-45.0
pH	6.0-7.0	4.0-9.8	5.3-7.0*	4.8-9.0
NaCl (%)	0.5-4.0	0-20.0	0.5	0-20.0
a_w	0.98-0.99	0.83- 0.99	>0.99	0.86-0.99

Table 1. *S. aureus* growth and enterotoxin production conditions. (*) Staphylococcal enterotoxin A (SEA) production at optimum pH 5.3-6.8. Other Staphylococcal enterotoxin (SE) at pH 6.0-7.0. a_w = water activity (Adam and Moss 2008).

An extensive spread of MRSA with livestock origin has been observed along the food chain over the past twenty years (Alexandra Fetsch, Etter, and Johler 2021). Livestock-associated MRSA (LA-MRSA) has emerged in human indicating zoonotic transmission from animals to humans (Figure 9) (Crespo-Piazuelo and Lawlor 2021). Many studies conducted in Europe, North America and China have confirmed the contamination of food, mainly raw meat, with LA-MRSA, notably in poultry meat (Figure 19) (Bernier-Lachance et al. 2020; Léguillier et al. 2024; Silva et al. 2021; Shi Wu et al. 2019). Nevertheless, LA-MRSA strains are relatively rare in urban areas (Alexandra Fetsch, Etter, and Johler 2021). Contamination by direct contact with livestock's animals appears more important than through the consumption of contaminated food (Plaza-Rodriguez, Kaesbohrer, and Tenhagen 2019). However, LA-MRSA acquired new virulence and resistance determinants because of *S. aureus* high adaptability causing severe bloodstream infections in humans (Matuszewska et al. 2022). Indeed, MGEs appear frequently and give especially resistance to antibiotics and heavy metals resistance genes.

Figure 19. Overview of LA-MRSA strains detected in different animal hosts and geographical regions. Adapted from (Alexandra Fetsch, Etter, and Johler 2021)

2.4. Manuscript 1: A review and meta-analysis of *Staphylococcus* prevalence in foods

In this bibliographical section of this thesis, the topic of *S. aureus* as a food pathogen was described. The publication is named "Manuscript 1". The aim was to identify by meta-analysis the prevalence of *S. aureus* in food, highlight risk factors for food contamination, methods to detect foodborne *S. aureus* and resistance to antibiotics of food isolates. Based on the selected publications in this study covering the period from 2012 to 2022, ready-to-eat foods including meat and milk are the most contaminated by the pathogen. The meta-analysis show the highest antibiotics resistance of *S. aureus* isolated in rich-protein food. Finally, preventing *S. aureus* contamination requires better microbiological surveillance, rigorous hygiene measures and rational antibiotic use.

Manuscript 1

A review and meta-analysis of *Staphylococcus aureus* prevalence in foods

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ABSTRACT

We present the review and meta-analysis of the prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from various food sources. PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Science Direct were searched for articles from 2012 to 2022. *S. aureus* is a pathogenic bacterium present in natural skin flora, that can cause a variety of diseases with different degrees of severity. Although its natural habitat are humans and animals, *S. aureus* can be found in water, soil and contaminated surfaces. Consequently, multiple routes can be involved in food contamination by *S. aureus*. The bacterium was most prevalent in ready-to-eat food (35.1 %), meat (21.7 %) and dairy products (18.5 %). Among contaminated products, meat products represented 59.51 % and were distributed as such: 44 % for beef meat, 28 % for pork meat, 22 % for chicken meat, 6 % for turkey meat. Antibiotic resistance studies showed resistance to penicillins is the most common (61 %) while resistant to quinolones, amphenicols and rifamycins were found to be low (<10 %). Pooled prevalence of antimicrobial resistance in isolated strains revealed that 68 % of all isolates carried resistance to at least one antibiotic in clinical use. Future studies are needed to assess antimicrobial resistance, food-associated stress and biofilm formation of the foodborne pathogen *S. aureus*. Furthermore, improved diagnostic tools and implementation of surveillance programs could lead to reduction of the burden caused by *S. aureus*.

1. Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive bacterium, typically arranged in grape-form clusters that can colonize humans, animals, and the environment (Cheung, Bae, & Otto, 2021). It can be transmitted by contact with infected individual or contaminated surfaces, but also by contact with sick animals or contaminated food and water. In addition to infections, this pathogen can be responsible for intoxications which occurs after the consumption of foods containing toxins, like staphylococcal enterotoxins, which resist to thermal treatments used by the food industries to eliminate bacteria from food products.

S. aureus infections range from localized infections to more severe conditions like sepsis and pneumonia. Examples of easily manageable pathologies are folliculitis, blister bubble formation, and diarrhea, while

more severe disorders include osteomyelitis, mastitis, endocarditis, and toxic shock syndrome, which, if left untreated or mismanaged, can lead to death (Ford, Hurford, & Cassat, 2021).

S. aureus is one of the most problematic pathogens and one of the six ESKAPE pathogens (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter species*) that are increasingly associated with therapeutic failures. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a mechanism by which microorganisms undergo adaptive changes to become partially, or totally resistant to antimicrobial agents that were previously efficient (Darby et al., 2023; Guo, Song, Sun, Wang, & Wang, 2020; Urban-Chmiel et al., 2022). The easy adaptation of *S. aureus* to various environments and its high genetic flexibility contribute to its ability to survive against anti-staphylococcal drugs.

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In 1940s and 1950s, the emergence of penicillin- and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (PRSA and MRSA) strains detected in hospitals was a consequence of the antibiotic introduction (EFSA). For many years, treatment against MRSA relied on glycopeptides, particularly vancomycin, contributing to the emergence of vancomycin-resistant strains (VRSA). Nowadays, despite introduction of new antibiotics with different modes of action, new resistance systems have emerged, causing a serious public health and safety issue (Foster, 2017; Hughes & Andersson, 2017). Among glycopeptide antibiotics teicoplanin and vancomycin are still used as efficient for MRSA infections. Ceftobiprole and ceftaroline are new cephalosporins that seem to overcome the limits of cefazolin and other cephalosporins as they have a wide spectrum of antimicrobial activity. In addition, we can mention telavancin, oritavancin (lipoglycopeptides), dalbavacin (which is similar to teicoplanin) and oxazolidinones (linezolid and tedizolid) that are all effective against MRSA isolates (Esposito et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the extensive use of antibiotics for medicine and veterinary purposes and its consequent antibiotic selection pressure led to the selection of multidrug resistant *S. aureus* strains (MDR), able to resist to all clinically used antibiotics.

Besides *S. aureus* can form biofilms, enter in a transient phenotype of non-growing persister, and produce toxins after tissue colonization (Peyrusson et al., 2020). In some cases, host innate immunity alone is inefficient against staphylococcal infections, and a long-term treatment by antibiotics is necessary to clear out this rapidly multiplying bacterium. Consequently, *S. aureus* is one of the most noticeable causes of nosocomial and community acquired bacterial infections worldwide.

In this review we analyzed the prevalence of *S. aureus* in different foods, with particular focus on AMR stains and the resistance mechanisms. We based the study on existing publications from January 2012 to December 2022, using the meta-analytical approach. Besides, we critically present analytical methods used to detect *S. aureus* in different foods, mostly meat and milk, and the main preventive actions available to improve microbiological food safety and risk mitigation regarding *S. aureus*.

2. Methodology

Meta-analysis of *S. aureus* incidence in food products was applied on a collection of results from published primary studies with the objective to generate conclusions that the individual studies alone would not interpret and integrate clearly.

2.1. Search methodology

We examined data from different Medline search engines, including PubMed, Google Scholar, Web of Science, Scopus, and Science Direct, using preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guideline (<http://www.prisma-statement.org/>). To search the articles, MeSH terms and Boolean Logic tools with the connectors 'AND' and 'OR' were used, including (antimicrobial resistance OR antibiotic resistance OR AMR) AND (*Staphylococcus aureus* OR *S. aureus*) AND (food sources), OR (chicken Grilled fish and meat (barbecues)), OR sea food, OR dairy products, OR ready to eat food, OR pork, OR beef, OR turkey OR vegetables OR pastries OR pasta), AND (Multi drug resistance OR MDR) AND (Drug susceptibility tests of *Staphylococcus aureus*).

2.2. Selection criteria

In the process of assessing data from various articles, several criteria were meticulously applied: (i) availability of the full text and abstract of the article; (ii) examination of *Staphylococcus aureus* in different food sources; (iii) inclusion of studies specifying author names, publication year and total number of isolates of *S. aureus*; (iv) identification of sample sources (e.g., chicken, seafood, dairy products, ready-to-eat food, pork, beef, and turkey, vegetables, egg products, pastries, pasta,

rice, spices); and (v) AMR assessment method were applied, including different molecular techniques, disk diffusion (DD), minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), and (vi) sample size and susceptible/resistant organism, multidrug resistant.

Studies were excluded if they (a) were review articles, perspectives, case studies, thesis, editorial notes and book chapters, (b) did not mention antimicrobial susceptibility tests using the Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) guidelines studies, (c) had missing essential statistics, or (d) not written in English.

2.3. Data extraction and statistical analysis

To establish a baseline, complete versions of purportedly relevant articles were acquired. Author names, publication years, the total number of *S. aureus* isolates, and total samples from each article were independently gathered and documented in a spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel® 2023) (Table S1.) for preliminary testing before full extraction. Data extraction involved utilizing text, tables, and figures. The findings were scrutinized, and AMR pie charts were generated to present the data using GraphPad Prism®. Citations from the compiled papers were done by using Endnote software.

To adequately address potential biases stemming from heterogeneity, a random-effects model analysis was conducted. The results were presented using effect size estimates along with corresponding 95 % confidence intervals (95 % CIs). The entire analysis was performed using the “metafor” package in R (version 4.1.2; R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) within Rstudio (build 4.4.3). Proportions and pooled 95 % CIs were calculated within the framework of a random-effects model to evaluate the prevalence of *S. aureus* isolates in food samples. Heterogeneity was assessed using the I² statistic, and value of $p < 0.05$ was defined as the threshold for statistical significance.

3. Food contamination by *S. aureus*

S. aureus is found in various protein-rich foods, including raw meat and meat products, milk and dairy products, bakery products, and fresh vegetables (Grispoldi, Karama, Armani, Hadjicharalambous, & Cenci-Goga, 2021; Gunjan et al., 2023; Mukherjee, Vidic, Auger, Wen, Pandey, & Chang, 2023; Vidic, Manzano, Raj, Pandey, & Chang, 2023). Food contaminated with *S. aureus* poses a particularly high risk for consumers if strains produce enterotoxins. While *S. aureus* is inactivated by cooking or pasteurization processing, toxins are heat-stable and remain active reaching the human gastrointestinal tract. The enterotoxin production increases within an optimal temperature range of 20–37 °C and pH 4–7.4 with consequent release in foods (Al-Nabulsi et al., 2020). Furthermore, any food, which preparation requires warm temperatures, or low-salt solution after preparation and considerable handling, such as dairy products, are also commonly implicated in staphylococcal enterotoxins food poisoning.

The ability of *S. aureus* to adhere to abiotic surfaces and form biofilms is one of the main concerns in the food industry as it increases the riskiness of this species for the microbial cross-contamination of food products. The presence of other pathogenic microorganisms, which may co-exist with *S. aureus* in biofilm, potentiates disease transmission. Biofilms are mainly composed on an extracellular matrix of exopolysaccharides (EPS), which help bacteria resisting to their environment by limiting mobility and penetration of biocides deeper into the biofilm matrix (Kaplan et al., 2018; Tuon, Suss, Telles, Dantas, Borges, & Ribeiro, 2023). The resistance of *S. aureus* cells to cleaning and disinfection procedures within biofilms poses continuous risk for food deterioration and reduced food shelf life. This problem is of high concern for industries involved in meat production and processing (Wagner et al., 2020).

Fig. 1 illustrates possible diffusion routes of *S. aureus* in the food chain. The bacterium can grow in different food products, including foods with high salt or sugar content and low water activity (Beuchat

Fig. 1. Critical elements in *Staphylococcus aureus* diffusion within the food chain. The transmission of *S. aureus* starts during primary production, especially in livestock farming, then extends through food products and work environments to finally affect human health among final consumers.

et al., 2013; Castro, Santos, Meireles, Silva, & Teixeira, 2016). In these environments, inadequately cleaned surfaces promote dirt accumulation, which, in the presence of water, favorize bacterial biofilm development. Furthermore, climate change leads to changes in temperature and precipitation patterns, increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, ocean warming and acidification. All these changes modify environmental dispersal and persistence of *S. aureus*, with consequences for food safety (Hellberg & Chu, 2016; Kadariya, Smith, & Thapaliya, 2014).

Pathogenic and epidemiological characteristics of MRSA indicated that food can be contaminated with community associated-MRSA, livestock associated-MRSA and even hospital associated-MRSA (Sergelidis & Angelidis, 2017). Agricultural intensification and simplification and livestock density are key drivers of MRSA reservoir in livestock animals which role in human invasive infections is difficult to assess (Fetsch, Etter, & Johler, 2021). Human invasive *S. aureus* infections are declining in regions with advanced surveillance systems such as in the EU member states with the centralized European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network (EARS-Net) hosted by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and in the USA with Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services relying on National Healthcare Safety Network Reports, the Emerging Infections Program (Authority, 2021; Fetsch et al., 2021). However, it is not a general trend at the global level. For example, the significant increase of infections caused by methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* in Asia-Pacific region is evidenced since the 1980s (W. W. Lim et al., 2019).

3.1. Food screening for *S. aureus* presence

To assess the safety of food products, the European Commission has defined the food safety and hygiene criteria (Regulation (EC) No. 2073/2005) which comprehends a well-defined guideline to identify and quantify foodborne pathogens, as *S. aureus*, and the toxin that they can produce in food (Cossetini, Vidic, Maifreni, Marino, Pinamonti, &

Manzano, 2022; De Medici et al., 2015). The conventional approach used to detect *S. aureus* in food is based on bacterial culturing and includes sample preparation, enrichment, plating, isolation, and confirmation of the colonies as illustrated in Fig. 2. Even though the culture-based methods are still reported as the gold standard, due to the sensitivity and efficiency, they do not fit the need of the food industry because of the long time required to obtain the results.

Recently, Gizaw et al. (2023) reports the collection of 1001 samples of raw milk, and tank milk, buckets, farm tanks, milkers' hands, and nasal swabs to evaluate the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gizaw et al., 2023). A non-selective pre-enrichment, plating for identification, Gram-stain test, and biochemical tests (coagulase, catalase, indole production, methyl red test, Voges-Proskauer reaction, urease production, citrate utilization, and sugar fermentation) were needed to identify the presence of *S. aureus*. The overall analysis take several days. Similar timing was reported for detection of *Staphylococcus* species from alkaline fermented foods (Ouoba et al., 2019). In this study, along with the identification steps (including the homogenization, the plating on nutrient agar, and the plating on Baird Parker), detection of AMR and toxin genes were added, demanding for 5 days to provide results. These studies illustrate the complexity and time- and efforts- associated challenges of the traditional methods to provide conclusive outcomes.

Given these limitations, the attention has shifted towards the development of molecular methods capable of providing results rapidly (Vidic et al., 2019). Besides, the emergency of bacteria carrying AMR has led to extensive development of tests to detect resistance to antibacterial drugs because many of these resistance mechanisms are driven by specific genes. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) stands out as the most widely used molecular method for detecting the presence of *S. aureus* species by amplifying usually the *nuc* or 16 S rRNA gene. By selecting primers specifically designed for genes associated with AMR, PCR enables to assess the presence of antibiotic resistance in the bacterial pathogens detected in food samples. PCR is a gold-standard technique to detect the gene carrying resistance to methicillin (*mecA* is the most diffused methicillin-resistance gene) and consequently

Fig. 2. Detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* in foods by classical microbiological techniques: steps including food sampling, homogenization, pre-enrichment, and plating, followed by colony isolation are required to evidence suspicious *S. aureus* strains. Furthermore, biochemical and morphological tests are needed for the final confirmation.

MRSA. We found that most of the studies using PCR method examined the presence of either *mecA*, *mecC*, *ermA*, *ermB*, *ermC*, *blaZ*, *tetK*, *tetM*, *tetS*, *tetL*, *vanA*, *vanB*, *vatA*, *vatB*, or *vatC* resistance genes. To increase the sensitivity and selectivity of detection, PCR is usually performed on isolated colonies for confirmation. For instance, PCR was applied to amplify the *nuc* gene and resistance genes for methicillin, *mecA* and *mecC*, in isolates from raw cow's milk collected from bulk cooling tanks on dairy farms (Oliveira, Pinho, Almeida, Azevedo, & Almeida, 2022). Moreover, a multiplex PCR can be employed on positive samples to simultaneously detect different genes of antibiotic resistance and toxins. Parco et al. (2021) investigated the antimicrobial resistance of *S. aureus* strains isolated from milk of sheep and goats using specific primers for *mecA*, *tetK*, *tetM*, *ermA*, and *ermC*. After isolation, dilution, homogenization, identification, and DNA extraction, PCR results were obtained within approximately 3 days (Parco et al., 2021) indicating molecular methods are an attractive alternative to traditional methods. Real-time PCR is used for quantitative gene detection. For instance, real-time PCR was applied in routine microbiome surveillance of genes associated with resistance to different antibiotics in the human gut (glycopeptides, beta-lactams, and macrolides), including *ermB*, *mefA*, *vanB*, and *mecA*, belonging to resistant species such as *Staphylococcus* (Burcham et al., 2019). When used to detect genes associated with resistance, real-time PCR and multiplex PCR show sensitivity between 95.7 % and 100 % (Sanchini, 2022).

Table 1
Prevalence and sample size for the detection methods of *S. aureus*.

Method	Total sample number	Case number	% Prevalence	% Weight
Culture	12,912	2328	18.03	65.31
Culture/biochemical	1414	466	32.96	7.15
Culture/PCR	4627	1365	29.50	23.40
Culture/ biochemical/PCR	818	340	41.56	4.14
Total	19,771	4504	22.78	100

Although the PCR-based methods are well-developed, they are still less standard than culture-based method, as shown in Table 1. We found that less than 30 % of the studies used PCR. It is worth noting that molecular methods are highly sensitive, specific, and able to provide quantitative results, but also have limitations since they are costly, complex and require isolated genetic materials, manipulation with special care and sophisticated equipment. Moreover, PCR may miss novel or less common genes, which highlights the need for complementary methods like next-generation sequencing for comprehensive surveillance.

In recent years there was a shift towards specific detection tools like biosensors (McNaught & Wilkinson, 1997) that offer the advantage of further reducing the time of analysis and allowing for *in-situ* working. These specialized tools are composed of two main components: a biological element designed to specifically interact with the target of interest, and a transducer that converts the biorecognition event into a measurable signal. Biosensors may be categorized according to the transducer element employed in the construction (electrochemical, piezoelectrical, and optical) or to the bioreceptor (DNA probes, aptamers, antibodies, enzymes, etc.). Once the target is detected, biosensors generate a signal directly proportional to the concentration of the analyte of interest. Due to their sensitivity, specificity, ease of use, and short time of analysis, biosensors find applications across various fields, including the detection of microorganisms, toxins and antimicrobial resistance genes (Balbinot, Srivastav, Vidic, Abdulhalim, & Manzano, 2021; Ionescu et al., 2020; Kotsiri, Vidic, & Vantarakis, 2022; Novakovic et al., 2024; Poggesi, Zhou, Bariani, Mittapalli, Manzano, & Ionescu, 2021; Rizzotto et al., 2023).

Marin et al. (2017) developed a colorimetric biosensor that enabled a naked-eye detection of *S. aureus* in milk and infant formula (Marin, Rizzotto, Léguillier, Péchoux, Borezee-Durant, & Vidic, 2022). This tool combines gold nanoparticles functionalized with specific aptamers that bind *S. aureus* cells, and phenomenon of localized surface plasmon resonance. Under optimized conditions, *S. aureus* was visually detected within only 30 min. However, the sensitivity was low since the detection

limit was 7.5×10^4 CFU/mL in milk and 8.4×10^4 CFU/mL in infant formula, respectively. This study highlights the benefits that can be obtained by adopting biosensors for food microbiological safety assessment regarding a considerable reduction of the overall time required for the analysis, and possibility to detect pathogen directly in food sample and *on-site*. However, further optimizations are needed to reach the end-users compliance and regulatory guidelines on food microbiological quality.

Biosensors have been also developed to replace common antibiotic susceptibility tests. For instance, resistances to ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, daptomycin, erythromycin, vancomycin, and methicillin can be accessed by measuring the impedance generated by *S. aureus* cells cultured on plastic microchips (Safavieh et al., 2017). Alternatively, biosensors can be employed on bacterial DNA to detect antibiotic resistant genes. Although DNA extraction from bacterial cells is needed prior to analysis, the gene detection by biosensors is achieved quickly, taking less than 2 hours for the hybridization between the DNA probe and the target gene. The *nuc* and *mecA* genes were simultaneously detected within 1 hour using target-specific ssDNA probes immobilized on the N-doped porous carbon materials with limits of detection of 1.6 fM and 3.6 fM, respectively (Dai et al., 2021). Similar strategies with analogous timing were applied in other studies to detect simultaneously *nuc* and *mecA* genes, such as the streptavidin-graphite-epoxy bio-composited geno-biosensor (Zacco, Pividori, & Alegret, 2006), or argonaute-centered portable and visual biosensor (Kou et al., 2024).

Although in dynamic development, biosensors are still rarely used for food items screening. The large majority of publications on *S. aureus* detection in food used culturing and PCR-based methods (Table 1).

3.2. Origin of food products contaminated with *S. aureus*

The meta-analysis conducted on research reports dealing with 19771 different food samples revealed that *S. aureus* is most frequently reported in ready-to-eat, meat and dairy products (Fig. 3). The publications were classified into two categories, one dealing with ‘raw and cooked meat’ comprising all references that precise or not the animal origin of meat (Fig. 3A and 3C) and the other with animal origin ‘chicken’, ‘beef’, ‘pork’, and ‘turkey’ (Figs. 3B and D). The study employed a random effects model to examine food consumption proportions, encompassing sea food, dairy products, chicken, pork, turkey, beef, ready-to-eat foods, vegetables, egg products pastries, starchy foods and spices. Prediction intervals were calculated for each category, showing varying proportions with corresponding confidence intervals. The analysis revealed high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 100\%$) and low variability between studies ($\tau^2 = 0.0699$, $p = 0$). The overall proportion and 95% confidence interval under the random effect model was calculated as 0.37 (0.20; 0.53). The sample size of food types ranged from 60 to 10606, and the prevalence of *S. aureus* ranged from less than 1–35.1% with the highest prevalence for ready-to-eat food (35.1%, 95% CI: 33.3; 36.9) followed by raw and cooked meat (21.7%, 95% CI: 20.6; 22.8) and dairy products (18.5%, 95% CI: 17.6; 19.4). The lowest prevalence of *S. aureus* was found in pastries (0.57%, 95% CI: 0.54; 0.60), starchy foods (0.6%, 95% CI: 0.57; 0.63) and spices 2.3 (95% CI: 2.19; 2.42). Among meat samples analyzed, the highest prevalence of *S. aureus* was found in turkey (42.8%), followed by pork (36%), beef (34.5%) and chicken (31%), as shown in Fig. 3B.

Among all samples positive to *S. aureus*, the raw and cooked meat was the most represented food category (59.51%) followed by dairy

Fig. 3. Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates in all kinds of foods. (A) The prevalence of *S. aureus* in all kinds of foods. The highest prevalence was found in ready-to-eat foods. (B) The prevalence of *S. aureus* in meat products of different origin seem to be similar. (C) The food sources of *S. aureus* isolates are very diverse, but raw and cooked meat seem to be at high risk of contamination compared to other food products. (D) Meat products contaminated by *S. aureus* were separated depending on their animal origin and beef is the main source of contamination.

products (30.10 %), ready-to-eat food (8.87 %), sea food (0.82 %), vegetables (0.56 %), and finally egg products, pastries, starchy food and spices with less than 0.1 % of positive samples (Fig. 3C). Interestingly, among meat positive samples, beef was the most represented meat (44 %) followed by pork (28 %), chicken (22 %) and turkey (6 %), as shown in Fig. 3D. It is to note that the majority of studies focused on meat and dairy products because these categories are known as high risk.

S. aureus is a well-known raw and cooked meat contaminant. The bacterium is responsible for mastitis in bovines, and makes milk from infected cows not useful for human consumption. Indeed, *S. aureus* is a primary cause of mastitis in small ruminants, causing significant losses in dairy industries. Mastitis is a challenge in dairy cattle farming due to the high diffusion of *S. aureus* and the easy dissemination through contaminated animals, which can lead to contamination of meat products. Cross-contamination from inadequately cleaned surfaces or improper actions of workers during slaughter or preparation processes can produce bioaerosols responsible for *S. aureus* spread.

Milk, a common food in many diets and ingredient in numerous food products can be a route for the transmission of antibiotic-resistant bacteria to humans. *S. aureus* can contaminate raw milk in different ways including soil and grass in contact with cow but also during transport from the farm to the dairy plants or via contaminated milking processing equipment if hygienic conditions are not fully respected (Doyle, Hartmann, & Wong, 2012). Previous studies indicated the presence of *S. aureus* in pasteurized or heated milk, which may result from insufficient heat treatment or post-treatment contamination by food handlers. It can also be contaminated along the retail chain or during storage, consequence of an insufficient temperature control (More O'Ferrall-Berndt, 2007; Ou et al., 2018). In addition, dairy industry production lines often contain residues of proteins and minerals such as calcium and phosphate, which promote the formation of biofilms by *S. aureus* (Shen, Wang, Zhu, Zhang, Shang, & Xue, 2021). These various contamination routes may partly explain the 18.5 % prevalence of milk and dairy products with *S. aureus* in this study. The presence and transmission of pathogenic MRSA in milk samples indicates a significant risk to human health, that need to be assessed and controlled.

Although *S. aureus* is generally susceptible to disinfectants, some strains are resistant in poultry processing plants, dehydrated products, and food rich in fat and salt (Bertolatti, O'Brien, & Grubb, 2003). In addition to cleaning, disinfection and thermal treatments, *S. aureus* can also survive unconventional treatments used in the food industries. Referring to non-thermal technologies, acidification is acknowledged as a method to control the proliferation of undesirable microorganisms, including pathogens, while also enhancing the shelf life, texture, and flavor of food products.

The overall prevalence of *S. aureus* was investigated in 26 studies originated from China, USA, Italy, Portugal, Thailand, Malaysia, Portugal and Egypt. Since the food production practices vary across these countries, we compared the differences in the pooled prevalence of *S. aureus* among different countries. The lowest prevalence was found in Italy (8.3 %), followed by Malaysia (15 %), China (27.8 %) and Thailand (30.6 %), while the highest prevalence was reported in Egypt (32.2 %), Portugal (53 %) and USA (46.0 %). Regarding the sample size, the number of tested samples was highly variable with the largest size for Italy (11794 samples), and the smallest for Portugal (100 samples).

Some studies suggested that AMR strains are more tolerant to food-associated stresses and can adapt to nonthermal treatments used by the food industries (Liao et al., 2020). For instance, Ma et al., found that *S. aureus* strains resistant to antibiotics exhibited high resistance to strong acid exposure (HCl, pH 1.5, 40 min) compared to antibiotic-susceptible counterparts (Ma et al., 2019). Another study showed that antibiotic-resistant strains were more resistant to gamma radiation and high energy electron beam (Skowron et al., 2018), methods used to eliminate microorganisms and food preservation. Several molecular mechanisms involving *S. aureus* sigma factors, SOS

response, mutations, and two-component system were reported for the cross protection between antibiotics and food-associated stresses (Liao et al., 2020). These findings indicate that the food chain can be a vector for dissemination of AMR strains. However, further investigations are necessary to fully understand the relationship between AMR and bacterial resistance to food-associated stress.

4. Antimicrobial resistance of *S. aureus*: burden, mechanisms and prevalence in food products

Antibiotic resistance is mainly attributed to the selection pressure caused by the misuse and overuse of antibiotics. Although antibiotics are one of the most important advances in medicine, their overprescribing has led to resistant bacteria (Bell, Schellevis, Stobberingh, Goossens, & Pringle, 2014). The escalating demand for animal proteins and the intensification of food animal production resulted in greater antibiotic utilization since their initial deployment as growth promoters (Dibner & Richards, 2005). Besides, antibiotics are commonly used to treat livestock in order to prevent animal diseases, which favors the development of AMR in foodborne bacteria (Gao et al., 2020). However, antibiotics cannot be completely absorbed by animal intestines and enter into the environment through the urine and feces. Because of their low biodegradability, antibiotics are further released and spread into soils, sediments and sewage through the application of fertilizers and the use of recycled water. A study conducted on cereals cultivated using wastewater indicated the presence of 19 different antibiotics in wheat, barley oats and rice (Albero, Tadeo, Miguel, & Pérez, 2019).

The increased prevalence of antibiotic-resistant foodborne bacteria is linked not only to their exposure to corresponding antibiotics but also to environmental chemical pollutants such as heavy metals, per- and polyfluoroalkyl compounds (PAFS), disinfectants, and pesticides. Moreover, this excessive release of pollutants in the environment can induce selective pressure of two or more chemical compounds on bacteria by co-selection mechanisms including co-resistance, cross-resistance, co-regulation and biofilm resistance (Huo et al., 2023; Murray, Hayes, Snape, Kasprzyk-Hordern, Gaze, & Murray, 2024; Sentic et al., 2023). For instance, the coexisting of heavy metals and antibiotics in manures and manure-amended agricultural soils were shown to exert a strong selection pressure and acted as complementary factors for abundance of antibiotic resistance genes (Ji et al., 2012). These co-selection mechanisms makes bacteria resistant to multiple antibiotics, heavy metals and chemical substances (Imran, Das, & Naik, 2019; Murray et al., 2024). It was shown that soil from mining sites rich in zinc and iron contained numerous isolates with multiple co-resistance to antibiotics and heavy metals such as mercury, zinc and nickel (Sinegani & Younessi, 2017). In addition, the co-transmission mechanism of resistance genes among microbial populations through the vertical and horizontal gene transmission allow bacteria to indirectly obtain resistance. The horizontal gene transmission can be enhanced by chemical pollutants in the environment in various mechanisms: conjugation transfer, membrane vesicles transport, bacterial transformation and bacteriophage transduction (Huo et al., 2023; Lu, Wang, Jin, Yuan, Bond, & Guo, 2020).

Altogether, the presence of antibiotic residues and pollutants in the environments surrounding food production sites promotes the emergence of AMR, contributes to food contamination with resistant strains and poses a serious risk to humans and animals (Hazards et al., 2021). Especially, *S. aureus* adaptability to diverse environments and regulation of gene expression contribute to its ability to survive against anti-staphylococcal drugs (O'Gara, 2017). Indeed, *S. aureus* possesses a high genetic flexibility, and can easily develop novel defense mechanisms. The co-selection pressure may play a significant role in the emergence and persistence of multi-drug resistant *S. aureus* strains in industrial plants and farms. A CC398 LA-MRSA strain that potentially acquired resistance to tetracycline and zinc in feed by the co-selection mechanism was shown to be highly prevalent in pig farms in Korea (Back, Eom, Lee, Lee, Park, & Yang, 2020). Depending on the

antimicrobial used, the pathogen can use one or more specific resistance mechanisms as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Based on data from the scientific literature, a meta-analysis of *S. aureus* isolates detected in food products and their AMR profiles was conducted in order to estimate the prevalence of resistant strains. In the present study, we grouped the reported antibiotics into eight categories based on the classification of the World Health Organization (WHO). We found that over the 3900 *S. aureus* isolated from 19771 food samples, 68 % were resistant to at least one antibiotic in clinical use. The highest overall prevalence of resistant *S. aureus* was against penicillins (61 %), followed by tetracyclines (49 %), and macrolides (37 %), aminoglycosides (26 %), cephalosporins (21 %), fluoroquinolones (16 %), glycopeptides and lincosamides (10.5 %), as shown in Fig. 5A. Besides, as shown in Fig. 5B, among all these resistant isolates detected in foods, 26 % were resistant to penicillins, 22.6 % to tetracyclines, 10 % to aminoglycosides and 8 % to cephalosporins. Less than 10 % of isolates were found resistant to quinolones, amphenicols and rifamycins. Table 2 presents mode of action of antibiotics and the most prevalent bacterial resistance mechanism acquired by *S. aureus* strains isolated from food, based on Fig. 5. This high prevalence of AMR strains indicates that through the food, humans can be exposed to resistant *S. aureus*, that is difficult to treat.

The resistance to penicillin is the first resistance to emerged rapidly after the introduction of penicillin G in the 1940s (Kirby, 1944). The antibiotic targets the transglycosylase-transpeptidase PBP2 in the cell envelope and blocks peptidoglycan synthesis. *S. aureus* inhibits the

action of this antibiotic by expressing a β -lactamase BlaZ which hydrolyses the amide bond of the four-membered β -lactam ring of the penicillin. The *blaZ* gene is regulated by an inducible system activated by β -lactams involving a repressor DNA-binding protein (BlaI) and a transmembrane protein (BlaR1), which serves as both a receptor and a signal transducer (Hao, Dai, Wang, Huang, & Yuan, 2012). The *bla* genes may be located on transposons or in the chromosomal DNA. Other β -lactam antibiotics, such as methicillin and oxacillin, are inactivated via the *mecA* gene encoding a novel Penicillin-Binding Protein, PBP2. This mechanism has caused the emergence of MRSA strains. The enzyme has low affinity for β -lactams and in consequence is not sensitive to these drugs (D. Lim & Strynadka, 2002; Turner et al., 2019). Nevertheless, MRSA strains growing in the presence of β -lactam generally have a less cross-linked peptidoglycan, giving them much more pro-inflammatory properties (D. Lim & Strynadka, 2002; Müller, Wolf, Iliev, Berg, Underhill, & Liu, 2015).

Several mechanisms can provide tetracycline resistance to *S. aureus*. Tetracycline is a bacteriostatic compound that binds to 30 S ribosomal subunits and blocks the protein production. *S. aureus* may develop ribosomal protection due to the *tetM* gene (Nguyen, Starosta, Arenz, Sohmen, Dönhöfer, & Wilson, 2014). Alternatively, mutation in efflux pump system coded by the *tetK* gene may limit the uptake of the drug (Wilson, 2016). Additionally, the overexpression of specific efflux pumps encoded by *tetK* and *tetL* genes increases strongly the resistance to the tetracyclines by facilitating their expulsion from the bacterium (Hooper & Jacoby, 2015). Similarities have been observed in resistance

Fig. 4. Molecular mechanisms of *Staphylococcus aureus* adaptation to antibiotics. The bacterium can degrade or modify the antibiotic molecule, alter the binding site of the antibiotic, bypass the antibiotic activity by producing or incorporating the target molecule of the antibiotic, decrease the influx, decrease the permeability of the envelop to block the passive transport of the antibiotic molecule into the cell, activate efflux to export the antibiotic from the cell or mutate the gene encoding the antibiotic's target.

Fig. 5. Overview of antimicrobial resistance of *S. aureus* isolated in food products. (A) Prevalence of *S. aureus* resistant isolates to specific class of antibiotics from food products. (B) Antimicrobial resistance of *S. aureus* food isolates in this study. The data were obtained via a meta-analysis approach compiling publications from 2012 to 2022. More than 50 % of isolated were resistant to penicillins and tetracyclines.

to fluoroquinolones with the mutations in the topoisomerase IV genes *gyrA* and *gyrB* (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska, Kowalewski, Krolak-Ulinska, & Marusza, 2022).

As mentioned above, horizontal gene transfer plays an important role of bacterial evolution and AMR spreading. *S. aureus* relies on mobile genetic elements (MGEs) such as plasmids, transposons, chromosomal cassettes, bacteriophages or Staphylococcal pathogenicity islands (SaPIs). These elements act as crucial facilitators for genetic exchange between bacteria through horizontal gene transfer, one of the main mechanisms of adaptation and evolution (Malachowa & DeLeo, 2010). Interestingly, this pathogen is capable of rapidly acquiring MGEs following a host-switching event, to get the capacity for survival and adaptation to a new environment. For instance, a strong antibacterial

selective pressure targeting the innate immune response via bacterial effectors in acute mastitis can confer resistance to antibiotics and heavy metal (Campos et al., 2022).

Phages have an important impact on Staphylococcal diversity and evolution. For example, the ciprofloxacin can induce the SOS response, which can stimulate the gene transfer by phages and lead to the acquirement new resistance genes (Úbeda, Maiques, Knecht, Lasa, Novick, & Penadés, 2005), or the transfer of Staphylococcal cassette chromosome carrying the *mecA* gene (SSC*mec*) (Ray, Boundy, & Archer, 2016). Moreover, phages can participate in other MGEs. The helper phage 80 α can mediate excision, replication, encapsidation and transduction to transfer SaPIs to other staphylococci (Mir-Sanchis et al., 2012).

Table 2

Main antibiotics to which *S. aureus* isolates from food products have developed resistance and mechanisms implicated.

Antibiotic class	Antibiotics	Mechanism of action	Resistance mechanism
Penicillins	Cloxacillin, ampicillin, penicillin G, amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, methicillin, oxacillin	Inhibit PBP transpeptidases catalyzing the final step in cell wall synthesis (peptidoglycan cross-linking)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of β-lactamases • Mutations accumulation in PBP leading to reduced binding affinities
Cephalosporins	Cefoperazone, cefoxitin, cefazolin, ceftaroline-fosamil, ceftriaxone, cefalexin, cefuroxime, cefotaxime, cefalotin		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced permeability • Efflux
Carbapenems β -Lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor	Imipenem Ampicillin/ sulbactam, amoxicillin/ clavulanic-acid	Combination of a β -Lactam (blocking cell wall synthesis) and a β -lactamase inhibitor (inhibiting the β -lactamase responsible for β -Lactam inactivation by hydrolysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutation in β-lactamase
Aminoglycosides	Gentamycin, amikacin, erythromycin, kanamycin, streptomycin	Inhibit protein synthesis by binding to the 16 S rRNA of the 30 S ribosome, causing misreading or truncated proteins	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enzymes modifying aminoglycosides • Decreased influx • Increased efflux • 16 S ribosomal methylases
Tetracyclines	Tetracycline, doxycycline	Inhibit protein synthesis by binding the 16 S rRNA of the 30 S ribosomal unit, blocking the binding of tRNA at the A-site of the ribosome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ribosome protection • Mutations in ribosome • Enzymatic inactivation of drug • Efflux
Glycopeptides	Vancomycin	Inhibits the cell wall biosynthesis by binding the D-alanyl-D-alanine portion of the lipid II (peptidoglycan precursor)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enzymatic modification and hydrolyse of peptidoglycan precursors • Mutations leading to low permeability
Macrolides	Azithromycin, erythromycin, tilimicosin	Inhibit bacterial protein synthesis by targeting the 23 S rRNA of the 50 S ribosomal subunit, causing truncated peptide chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modification of the 23 S rRNA by methyltransferases • Protection of the ribosome via ABC-F proteins

Table 2 (continued)

Antibiotic class	Antibiotics	Mechanism of action	Resistance mechanism
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, enrofloxacin	Inhibit DNA replication by blocking DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutations in DNA gyrase or topoisomerase IV
Quinolones	Nalidixic acid		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proteins protecting DNA • Efflux of antibiotic
Lincosamides	Clindamycin, lincomycin	Inhibit bacterial protein synthesis by targeting the 23 S rRNA of the 50 S ribosomal subunit, causing truncated proteins	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modification of the 23 S rRNA by methyltransferases • Inactivation of antibiotic • Efflux
Amphenicols	Chloramphenicol, floropenicol	Inhibit bacterial protein synthesis by binding the 50 S ribosomal subunit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutations in the 50 S ribosomal subunit • Enzymatic inactivation • Efflux
Rifamycins	Rifampicin	Inhibit transcription by binding to RNA polymerase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutations in <i>rpoB</i>, encoding RpoB, target of the antibiotic • Enzymatic ribosylation or inactivation of drug

Together, different *S. aureus* food isolates carried various antibiotic resistance suggesting that all mechanisms of resistance described for clinical strains can be also found in food. Consequently, food seems to be one of the most important vehicles for spreading resistant *S. aureus* strains.

5. Conclusions and future outlook

The aim of this review was to search available literature in order to identify the prevalence of *S. aureus* in food, highlight risk factors for food contamination, methods to detect foodborne *S. aureus*, and its resistance to antibiotics.

The WHO has classified *S. aureus* as a high-tier priority II pathogen. Foods are favorable environment for *S. aureus* survival and proliferation. Based on the selected publications in this study, ready-to-eat foods, meat, and milk are the most contaminated. In addition, the meta-analysis revealed the high antibiotic rates of *S. aureus* isolates. These findings of high prevalence of *S. aureus* including resistant strains in various foods impose a potential hazard to consumers, and also food handlers. Moreover, it is possible that *S. aureus* in meat and milk was identified because they were most often sampled. While there are many studies that assessed *S. aureus* presence in protein-rich foods, there is a need for additional analysis of other food categories together with food production facilities and environmental monitoring. Indeed, the spreading of *S. aureus* should be considered using a One health approach, as recommended by the WHO (Garcia, Osburn, & Jay-Russell, 2020; Mukherjee et al., 2023).

Improved diagnostic methods could significantly contribute to improve food safety. We found that most studies used culture alone while others combine culturing with PCR or biochemical testing. *mecA* is the most diffused methicillin-resistance gene in *S. aureus* and PCR is a gold-standard technique to detect the gene and consecutively MRSA. PCR-based methods have high sensitivity and selectivity, and their specificity can reach 100 % accordance when compared to culturing methods. However, PCR methods are expensive, labor intense and

require complex sample preparation, DNA extraction and amplicon analysis that significantly increase the overall time of analysis. Molecular methods are still lacking quality reagents, standardized equipment and analysis methods, which affect results between studies. Consequently, the food industry has a strong interest for advanced technologies for *S. aureus* detection to provide quality products and minimize the health risks. Biosensors can represent an alternative to culture-based and molecular methods as they provide needed sensitivity, specificity, and rapidity in pathogen detection. In addition to being affordable and user-friendly, biosensors can work in real-time, require no instrumentation and are suitable for point-of-care testing. The major challenge associated with the development of a biosensor for *S. aureus* detection in the food industry is the complexity of food matrices that may affect the accuracy and detection probability.

Prevention of food contamination by *S. aureus* requires rapid methods of microbiological surveillance and routine analysis for the bacterial cells, their toxins and AMR genes presence in food products. The surveillance of *S. aureus* should be performed in humans, animals, food and farm environments. Besides, it is necessary to develop programs to promote rational use of antimicrobial agents, infection prevention and control to reduce the incidence of resistance *S. aureus* strains. The surveillance along with the caution in the use of antibiotics in both human and animal health are related to the implementation of global and national One Health antimicrobial resistance programs. Moreover, to control MRSA strains spreading, prevention strategies and monitoring programs need to be implemented from farm to distribution posts. Besides, prevention of contamination from livestock to human via foods requires good farming practice and biosecurity and rigorous hygiene control measures together with the rational use of antibiotics. Prevention of food contamination by *S. aureus* requires strict hygiene standards for food industry staff in contact with raw food such as meat and milk. Finally, consumers need to be aware of potential risks. Cooking food thoroughly and maintaining good sanitation conditions in kitchen would help to prevent contamination and cross-contamination.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.microb.2024.100131](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microb.2024.100131).

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Chapter 3

Diagnostic of *S. aureus*

3. Diagnostic of *S. aureus*

3.1. Introduction

Due to the significant burden caused by bacteria resistance to antibiotics worldwide, the WHO adopted the “Global action plan on antimicrobial resistance (AMR)” in 2015 (World Health Organization 2015a). This plan has five objectives: to reduce infections, strengthen surveillance and research, promote the rational use of medicines in humans and animals, improve the understanding of AMR and enhance education and open science for professionals and policymakers, as well as increase investment in the development of new medicines and diagnostics. The last objective is particularly relevant to us. Indeed, there are many detection methods for pathogens and *S. aureus* (Figure 20). While these methods offer several advantages, they all share the same challenges: Their rapidity, accuracy and the possibility to be used as point of care detection method.

Figure 20. Detection methods of foodborne pathogenic bacteria (Sha Liu et al. 2022)

3.2. *S. aureus* detection methods

The conventional approach used to detect *S. aureus* in food is based on cultivation and plate counting (Roda et al. 2012). This method is time-consuming, requiring steps of bacterial enrichment, isolation, identification through biochemical screening and serological tests. It can take about three to seven days to obtain confirmed results, which is the time scale enabling *S. aureus* infections to spread significantly. Nevertheless, the results are accurate, reliable, affordable and simple. Given the limitations, molecular methods are also employed, particularly for detecting antibiotic resistant strains driven by specific genes. PCR is the most widely used method for detecting the presence of *S. aureus* species (Mullis 1990; Parco et al. 2021; Umesha and Manukumar 2018). By selecting primers for genes associated with AMR, it is possible to determine the antibiotic resistance of the bacterial pathogen (Alarcon, Vicedo, and Aznar 2006). In recent years, several rapid and automated detection methods have been developed, including a direct enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit (Nouri, Ahari, and Shahbazzadeh 2018), next generation sequencing (NGS) (Weterings et al. 2017), lateral flow immunoassay (LFIA) (Amini et al. 2020) and the matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrophotometry (MALDI-TOF-MS) (Manukumar and Umesha 2017). However, these techniques share common disadvantages: they are expensive, complex to operate and require specialized equipment and trained professionals.

3.3. SEs detection methods

As mentioned, *S. aureus* can secrete SEs, posing a threat to food safety and food security. Since toxins may persist in food even the bacterial cells were eliminated detection method have been developed to identify SEs, such as PCR-based techniques (Duquenne et al. 2010; Neill et al. 1990), loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) (Nkouawa et al. 2009) and single primer isothermal amplification (SPIA) (Q. Yang et al. 2018). PCR can be applied to a variety of foods issues related to bacterial cell lysis, DNA degradation or PCR inhibition can lead to false-negative results.

Moreover, routine detection is costly, requires professional technicians, and does not guarantee accurate results, which is unacceptable in both prevention and diagnostics. Chromatographic methods can be used for detecting SEs, as these basic proteins can be enzymatically degraded into peptides, separated by liquid chromatography and analyzed by mass spectrometry (Callahan et al. 2006; Lefebvre et al. 2022; Muratovic et al. 2015). In addition, numerous immunoassays identification methods have been developed, based on specific recognition of antigens and antibodies. These methods offer advantages such as high specificity and sensitivity, there are rapid to operate and can be used to detect SEs in complex samples without pre-treatment (Shijia Wu et al. 2016). Colorimetric immunoassays are among the most common optical detection techniques, measuring the absorbance of a colored substance, and have led to the development of several ELISA kits (Poli, Rivera, and Neal 2002; Sapsford et al. 2009).

3.4. Are we “REASSURED” with new detection methods?

Efficient diagnostics are essential to ensure safe food for consumers and to limit production losses, making the development of new analytical tools a priority. To address this, the WHO recommended essential criteria for developing new detection tools under the acronym REASSURED (Real-time Connectivity, Ease of specimen collection, Affordable, Sensitive, Specific, User friendly, Rapid, Equipment free, and Delivered) (Land et al. 2018). In the era of advanced technology, it has become standard for diagnostic results to be accessible via mobile devices (Ding et al. 2019). Simplicity and low cost of rapid point-of-care tests facilitate large-scale-population testing. Reducing costs while maintaining the same sensitivity and specificity is crucial to minimizing the economic impact on the agri-food sector. By making diagnostic tests user-friendly, easy to use, and portable for patients, farmers and the public costs can be reduced and the need for specialized staff and equipment can be eliminated. However, developing a diagnostic method that meets all these criteria simultaneously is challenging and often requires significant compromise.

In recent decades, innovative approaches beyond traditional detection methods have been developed, including microfluidic tests, colorimetric tests and biosensors. Among biosensors, aptamer-based biosensors (or aptasensors) have emerged as one of the most promising new tools, particularly for pathogen detection.

3.5. Aptamer-based biosensors

3.5.1 Biosensor definition

Biosensors were first introduced by Leyland C. Clark in 1962. Their biosensor is capable to measure glucose concentration by detecting dioxygen consumption during substrate oxidation by glucose oxidase (Clark and Lyons 1962). A biosensor is defined as an analytical device capable of quantitatively or semi-quantitatively detecting substances present in a biological sample (Monošík, Středanský, and Šturdík 2012). It is composed of several key components (**Figure 21**):

Figure 21. Principle of a biosensor. Created with BioRender.

- **A bioreceptor:** This element consists of a biological recognition component such as antibodies, enzymes, peptides, polymers or nucleic acid. The bioreceptor is

immobilized on the surface of the device and recognizes specific analyte like nucleic acid, proteins, peptides metabolites, ions (X. Wang, Zhou, and Wang 2024; Malhotra et al. 2017).

- **A transducer:** The transducer converts the interaction between the bioreceptor and the analyte into a measurable signal, which can be optical, electrochemical, thermometric, ion-sensitive, magnetic, acoustic or piezoelectric (X. Wang, Zhou, and Wang 2024; Malhotra et al. 2017).

- **An electronic element:** This component translates the signal from the transducer into a digital output, which correlates with the concentration of the target analyte in the sample (X. Wang, Zhou, and Wang 2024; Malhotra et al. 2017).

3.5.2 Nucleic acids

Nucleic acids (DNA and RNA) are macromolecular biomolecules naturally present in both eukaryotes and prokaryotes. They play a crucial biological role in storing and transmitting genetic information. DNA is the support of genetic information and constitutes the genome. It consists of a sequence of purine nitrogenous bases adenine (dA) and guanine (dG), and pyrimidine nitrogenous bases cytosine (dC) and thymine (dT). In RNA, the thymine is substituted by uracil. (U) When nitrogenous bases are linked to a deoxyribose (DNA) or a ribose (RNA), they form nucleosides. Nucleotides are formed by the covalent bonding of a nucleoside with a phosphate group. They are linked covalently by phosphodiester link, which constitutes the primary structure of nucleic acids (Saenger 1984) (Figure 22). This sequence encodes genetic information, which is organized into genes and expressed through RNA. The nucleic bases of one DNA strand interact with the complementary strand with hydrogen bonds. This complementarity follows specific base pairing rules with adenine pairing with thymine via two hydrogen bonds, and guanine pairing with cytosine via three hydrogen bonds. This complementarity base pairing forms the structure of the double helix DNA and is described as canonical B-form by Watson and Crick (figure 22).

B-form DNA

Watson-Crick base pairing

Stem-loop

Four-way-junctions

Bulge

Internal loop

G-quadruplex

I-motif

Figure 22 – Illustration of DNA structures, and base pairing. Created with BioRender

3.5.3 Non-canonique structures

DNA is primarily organized in the form of a double helix, with the B-form being the most adopted conformation in the nucleus. However, in certain specific sequences and environmental conditions (pH, salt type, ionic force), other structures known as non-canonical structures can emerge. The most well-known non-canonical DNA double helix conformations are the A-form and Z-form (Saenger 1984). Unlike other non-canonical structures, the A-form is not sequence-dependent but forms under conditions of low hydration. In contrast, the Z-form typically is sequence-dependent with a high repetition of purine-pyrimidine bases and favors in regions of DNA with high negative supercoiling or under conditions of high salt concentration and could have important biological functions (Sahayasheela et al., n.d.).

Variant of the double helix can also form either within a single strand or involve more than two, such stem-loops structure or three- or four-way junctions. These structures can occur during replication, transcription, or notably after DNA damage. They are generally sequence dependent. In 1957, G. Felsenfeld and A. Rich first observed the formation of triple-helix nucleic acids (Felsenfeld and Rich 1957). This structure is formed when a third DNA strand inserts itself into the major groove of a B-form DNA.

In 1962, M. Gellert proposed a novel non-canonical structure known as the G-quadruplex, which consists of a stack of guanine quartets (G-quartets) (Gellert, Lipsett, and Davies 1962). These structures do not follow the traditional Watson & Crick base-pairing rules. Indeed, the stability of the G-quadruplex is due to Hoogsteen hydrogen bonds between four guanines bases. Each G-quartets are stabilized by monovalent cations such as potassium or sodium (Figure 22). This non-canonical structure is among the most studied today, with numerous biological functions discovered, sparking significant interest in its roles. Telomeric chromosomal and promoter regions in the Human genome contain sequences that can form G-quadruplex structures. It was shown that these structures contribute to chromosomal stability and play important

roles in replication, transcription, and translation, (Tian et al. 2018; Teng et al. 2021). They have also been found to regulate telomerase, the enzyme responsible for synthesizing telomeric DNA.

In 1993, Gehring et al. discovered a new DNA structure known as the intercalated motif (I-motif) (Gehring, Leroy, and Gueron 1993). This tetrameric structure is composed of two parallel, antiparallel duplexes that are intercalated and stabilized by hemiprotonated C•C⁺ base pairs (Figure 22). This unique DNA structure is one of the central focuses of my PhD project. A detailed introduction to the I-motif is provided in Part 3 of this manuscript.

3.5.4 Definition and history of aptamers

In the 1990s, two research groups, led respectively by Andrew D. Ellington and Jack W. Szostak and by Larry Gold and Craig Tuerk, discovered short, single-stranded oligonucleotides, capable of folding into various 3D structures, known as aptamers (Andrew D. Ellington and Jack W. Szostak 1990; Tuerk and Gold 1990) The term "aptamer" is derived from the latin "*aptus*" meaning "to adapt" and the Greek suffix *meros*, meaning "part" or "region" Aptamers are typically composed of single-stranded nucleic acids with sizes ranging from 6 to 40 kDa, and lengths of 20 to 60 nucleotides. They can be made from various types of nucleic acids, including synthetic RNA or ssDNA sequences. In the early years of aptamer research, RNA aptamers were the primary focus, as it was initially thought that only RNA molecules possessed the structural motifs and secondary configurations necessary for effective target recognition. However, this perspective changed when it was demonstrated that ssDNA could adopt spatial non-canonic DNA conformations as mentioned earlier, such as loops, hairpins, G-quadruplexes, and i-motifs, capable of interacting with specific targets. This 3D structure is fundamental to the function of aptamers. They are characterized by an high affinity and specificity for a broad range of targets including proteins, small molecules, toxins, peptides, ions, virus, microorganisms, human cell or tissues. (Ji et al. 2023; Shahdordizadeh et al. 2017; DeGrasse 2012; Hu et al. 2024; W.

Guo et al. 2021; Smith et al. 2007) Moreover, DNA aptamers are easy to synthesize and have low production cost. While DNA aptamers are robust and cost-effective, RNA aptamers offer the advantage of forming more diverse and complex 3D structures, but are more vulnerable to nuclease degradation (Park 2018; Röthlisberger and Hollenstein 2018).

In consequence, over the past decade, the research on aptamers has increasingly focused on DNA, largely due to their enhanced stability and resistance to nuclease degradation, making them more suitable for various applications. Building on these advances, the synthesis of DNA aptamers has become a critical aspect of their development for various applications.

3.5.5 DNA Synthesis

DNA is commonly synthesized in the laboratory by chemical solid-phase synthesis in the form of single-stranded molecules (Amarnath and Broom 1977; Glazier et al. 2020). Enzymatic methods are also employed for oligonucleotides synthesis using molecular biology amplification techniques such as PCR and rolling circle amplification (RCA) (Hollenstein 2015; M. Hao, Qiao, and Qi 2020). These two approaches have different advantages and disadvantages: Chemical synthesis is limited in terms of sequence size and quantity obtained, whereas the enzymatic approach does not have such limitations. However, the use of polymerases imposes restrictions on sequence modifications.

Additionally, these traditional methods are outstripped by demand and technical limitations due to the growing complexity of oligonucleotides chemical nature. (Pichon and Hollenstein 2024). New synthesis strategies are being explored, such as controlled enzymatic synthesis, an oligonucleotide production method *de novo*, that combines synthesis elements of solid-phase synthesis and of enzymatic (Pichon and Hollenstein 2024).

Chemical modifications and functionalization of oligonucleotides, such as the incorporation of thiol groups or fluorescence molecules during synthesis are also possible. These modifications are particularly valuable for applications in nanotechnology, therapeutic, or diagnostic applications (Chan et al. 2022; Sun et al. 2017). New detection methods based on nucleic acid hybridization are enjoying phenomenal growth in recent decades, leading to the development of new strategies oligonucleotide synthesis.

3.5.6 Comparison of aptamers and antibodies

Both DNA and RNA aptamers share similar functionalities but offer distinct advantages over antibodies. Aptamer selection and production are conducted entirely *in vitro*, allowing for rapid, large-scale synthesis with homogeneous batch consistency. In contrast, monoclonal antibody production is labor-intensive, costly, and performed mostly *in vivo*, while polyclonal antibody production suffers from high batch-to-batch variability.

Aptamers also provide flexibility in target selection, as they can be developed against any molecule, unlike antibodies, which require targets that differ from endogenous proteins to elicit an immune response in animals. DNA aptamers are particularly valued for their stability, demonstrating resistance to temperature fluctuations and maintaining structural integrity through cycles of denaturation and renaturation, making them reusable. In contrast, antibodies are prone to irreversible denaturation, sensitive to storage conditions and susceptible to degradation.

Aptamers can be easily modified to enhance their binding properties or adapt them for diagnostic applications. For example, aptamers can be biotinylated, fluorescently labeled, or conjugated with enzymes without compromising systematically their binding affinity. In contrast, chemical modifications of antibodies are more complex and costly. Both aptamers and antibodies are employed in diagnostics and therapeutics for target recognition, but they differ fundamentally in their production, stability and adaptability (Table 2).

Aptamers	Antibodies
Selected and screened in vitro	Selected and screened in vivo
Can target toxins, drugs, and small molecules	Limited to targets that induce an immune response
Produced via automated synthesis (e.g., PCR)	More complex production involving animal hosts and bioreactors
Highly reproducible and pure products	Batch variations in non-monoclonal antibodies
Easily labeled without loss of function	Labeling may cause loss of function
Stable with regeneration capability and long-term storage	Limited shelf life and temperature sensitivity

Table 2 – Comparison Aptamer vs Antibodies

3.5.7 Applications and challenges of aptamers in diagnostics and therapeutics

Aptamers are employed in diverse applications, including food safety, biosensing, biomedical diagnostic, therapeutic, and bioimaging. A RNA aptamer drug, pegaptanib (marketed as *Macugen*), which targets vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)-165 was approved by the US FDA in 2004 for the treatment of age-related macular degeneration (AMD). Pegaptanib works by specifically binding to VEGF-165, a key factor in abnormal blood vessel formation in the retina, thereby inhibiting its activity and slowing the progression of AMD (Ng et al. 2006). More recently, a second RNA aptamer, the Avacincaptad pegol was approved by FDA in 2023 (Marketed as *Izervay*) for the treatment of geographic atrophy, a late-stage form of AMD (Patel et al. 2023). Several aptamers are in various stages of development or clinical trial for different therapeutic applications including aptamers for cancer, atherosclerosis, autoimmune myocarditis, inflammation and diabetes. As of today, there are more than 1,400 aptamers listed in the University of Texas Aptamer Database along with their sequences, structures and targets (Askari et al. 2024).

In food safety, especially for pathogen detection, aptasensors are becoming increasingly popular. Companies such as NeoVentures Biotechnologies (<https://neoaptamers.com/fr>) and Aptus Biotech's (<https://aptusbiotech.com>) offer services for the design and development of aptamers tailored for specific applications. However, the market for pathogen detection using aptasensors remains in its early stages of growth. One key challenge is ensuring the stability, reproducibility and

consistent performance of aptasensors across different sample matrices. These technical limitations have contributed to limited use of aptasensors in routine diagnostics.

3.6. Selection and characterization of the aptamers

3.6.1 Aptamers selection techniques

Figure 23. Cell-SELEX method for aptamer selection. First, a complex is formed between the target and a random DNA library. Then, unbound DNA is separated from the complex and the target-bound DNA is collected. The selected DNA sequences are amplified through PCR to generate multiple copies. This enriched DNA library is sequenced and reused for additional cycles until a highly specific and high-affinity DNA aptamer library is obtained for the target.

Aptamers are selected from vast library of nucleic acid sequences, comprising between 10^{13} and 10^{16} different molecules, using an *in vitro* selection technique known as SELEX (Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Exponential Enrichment). This process involves cycles of selection and amplification where a large pool of nucleic acid molecules is exposed to specific target molecules under controlled conditions, such as

defined temperature and salt concentrations (Sampson 2003). Molecules that first bind to the target are separated from those that remain unbound. Next, the bound molecules are amplified by PCR to generate an enriched population. This cycle is then repeated until, finally, a small pool of highly specific molecules is obtained (Figure 23).

Over time, SELEX has undergone numerous modifications and optimizations, making it more efficient, adaptable, and cost-effective for aptamer identification (Komarova and Kuznetsov 2019; Kohlberger and Gadermaier 2022; C. Zhu et al. 2024). The success of SELEX depends on the initial library, which typically consists of a random nucleotide region flanked by two constant primer regions to enable amplification during the selection process. These primers, generally non-essential for folding or target recognition, facilitate enrichment (Cowperthwaite and Ellington 2008). However, in rare cases, primer regions may contribute to the aptamer's structure, especially when the random region is short (Legiewicz et al. 2005). Longer random regions allow for more complex secondary and tertiary structures, whereas shorter regions enhance coverage and offer production advantages. The optimal random region length is 20-50 nucleotides, with primers typically around 20 nucleotides long.

Since the advent of this technology, numerous studies on aptamers have been conducted across a large range of targets. Notably, selection targeting pathogenic bacteria has been performed on whole cells, proteins, toxins, lipopolysaccharides, and even spores. Depending on the desired target, the SELEX is adapted accordingly. For the selection of *S. aureus* aptamers, the cell-SELEX method (Figure 24) is commonly used, allowing the identification of aptamers that bind specifically to the whole bacteria cell. However, in certain cases, specific molecular targets, such as surface proteins or toxins, are researched.

3.6.2 Affinity of the aptamers

After completing the SELEX procedure, it is necessary to select the most affinity-optimized aptamers. The binding process between an aptamer and its target is

reversible and the binding affinity is determined by the equilibrium dissociation constant (K_d) (X. Lu et al. 2024) (Figure 23). A stronger binding affinity corresponds to a lower K_d . In general, aptamers reported in the literature exhibit a strong affinity for their target, with K_d ranging from picomolar (pM) to nanomolar (nM) (Table n°3). The specificity of an aptamer is also important, as it reflects the ability of an aptamer to distinguish its target from non-specific ones, notably due to its unique 3D conformation. The interactions between aptamers and their targets include hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions, van der Waals forces, hydrogen bonding and shape complementarity (S. Cai et al. 2018)

Figure 24. Equilibrium binding of the aptamer to its biomarker target. Created with BioRender.com

A strong affinity and specificity for a target is the basis of analytical applications. In the context of detecting whole bacterial cells, such as *S. aureus* in this work, strong affinity is crucial for developing effective biocaptors. Additionally, specific interactions with the target are essential, as bacterial surfaces contain numerous biomarkers that can lead to non-specific interactions.

3.7. *S. aureus* & aptamers

The rapid and specific detection of *S. aureus* is a major challenge due to its impact on human and animal health, as well as food safety. In recent years, numerous aptamers have been selected to specially target this bacterium using different SELEX techniques. These aptamers recognize various targets on the bacterial cell wall such as surface proteins, toxins, teichoic acids or toxins produced by the bacterium. The table

below lists the aptamers published to date, detailing their targets, sequences, and affinities expressed by the K_d (Table 3). The selection of these aptamers has led to the development of highly sensitive detection tools capable of identifying low bacterial concentrations, which is crucial for preventing contamination in clinical and food environments. Some of these aptamers are presented in the table below (Chen et al. 2022) (Table 4).

Aptamer name	Aptamer sequence (5-3')	Target	Kd (nM)	References
SA20	GCGCCCTCTCACGTGGCATCAGAGTGCCGGAAGTTCTGCGTTAT	<i>S. aureus</i>	70.86 ± 39.22	(Cao et al. 2009)
SA23	GGGCTGGCCAGATCAGACCCCGGATGATCATCCTTGTGAGAACCA		61.50 ± 22.43	
SA31	TCCCACGATCTCATTAGTCTGTGGATAAGCGTGGGACGTCTATGA		82.86 ± 33.20	
SA34	CACAGTCACTCAGACGGCCGCTATTGTTGCCAGATTGCCTTTGGC		72.42 ± 35.23	
SA43	TCGGCACGTTCTCAGTAGCGCTCGCTGGTCATCCCACAGCTACGTC		210.70 ± 135.91	
SA17	CCCCCAGTCCGTCCTCCCAGCCTCACACC	<i>S. aureus</i>	35.0	(Y.-C. Chang et al. 2013)
SA61	CTCCCAACCGCTCCACCCTGCCTCCGCCTC		129.0	
A14	CACACCGCAGCAGTGGGAACGTTTCAGCCATGCAAGCATCACGCCCGT	<i>S. aureus</i>	3.49 ± 1.43	(Moon et al. 2015)
RAB1	CGGGTGGGCTCCAATATGAATCGCTTGCCCTGACGCTATCT	<i>S. aureus</i>	56 ± 87	(Ramlal et al. 2018)
RAB3	CGTAGTCTAGTGTCGATTAGTTTCCTTGAGACCTTGTGCT		37 ± 112	
RAB5	CGTAGTCTAGTGTCGATTAGTTTCCTTGCTATTGCAGACCTTGTGCT		58 ± 14	
RAB10	TCGAGAGGGATCTCGGGCGTGCGATGATTTTGCCTTCAT		46 ± 24	
RAB20	GCGTTACGTTAGTGGCCGCCTATGAGGACAGGCGGTTGTA		128 ± 45	
RAB28	TGGACGTCGTGGCGGAGGTTTATAAAACGGCGCCACTGT		49 ± 39	
RAB35	GGGGGGTTGTGCCATTTAAGATGACCGGTTGCCGCGATTT		34 ± 5	

SA25	GGGGAAGGTCGTCCGACGAACCCGGTCAGATAGGGTGGGG	<i>S. aureus</i>	44.92 ± 1.36	(Nguyen, Kim, and Gu 2022)
SA28	GCGGCCACGGAGGGGGTGCCGGGCGTGGAATAAGATGTGG		77 ± 1.22	
SA35	CACAGGTGTGGGGAGGTCCCATGGAGGTGGTTCAATG		58.77 ± 0.73	
SA37	AAAGACGGGGGGGGGGACCGGCGTATGAGTGAAGATGGGG		16.5 ± 3.41	
SA40	CGACGTGAAGCAATCATGGGTGGGGTACGTCGGGTCATGG		126.95 ± 0.51	
SA81	AACGAGGCGCAGGGGGAGGGGGTGGTACAGATAAGATGGGG		14.47 ± 8.18	
ApSA1	GGTCCCCTTTCTCTCCCC	<i>S. aureus</i>	62.7 ± 5.6	(De Melo et al. 2023)
ApSA2	GAGAACCCCCCTTCTCCCCA		45.7 ± 8.2	
ApSA3	GGGACAGGAGTGCGTGCTCCCC		43.3 ± 3.0	
ApSA4	GGGACAGGGAGAAAGCGGCACCCC		16 ± 55	
ApSA5	GGACTACCTTCTTTTTCTCCCCCC		165.8 ± 27.6	
ApSA6	GGGGACAGGGAGAAGGGGGGGGCCCC		90.2 ± 10.5	
SH-apt2	GCAATGGTACGGTACTTCTCGGCACGTTCTCAGTAGCGCTCGCTGGTCATCCCAC AGCTACGTCAAAGTGACGCTACTTTGCTAA	<i>S. aureus</i>	210.7	(Zhao et al. 2023)
cApt	GTACCGTACCATTGCTAGCGTCTCCCGTCCTT	<i>S. aureus</i>	not reported	(Q. Kang et al. 2023)
H1	GCAATGGTACGGTACCCCTATGCGCATGTACCATTGCAGTTGTCAGAGAGCGA		not reported	
H2	GGTACATGCGCATAGGGGTACCGTACCATAACCCCTATGCGCA		not reported	

DTMRSA 1	ATGCGGTTGGTTGCGGTTGGGCATGATGTATTTCTGTG	<i>S. aureus</i>	1.6 ± 5	(Turek 2013)
DTMRSA 2	CGACACGTTAGGTTGGTTAGGTTGGTTAGTTTCTTG		2.0 ± 6	
DTMRSA 3	GTAGATGGTTTGGTTGGTGTGGTTTCCACTGATGTTGGG		1.3 ± 5	
DTMRSA 4	TTATGGGGTGTGGTGGGGGGTTAATGCGTTGGTTATCCG		9.5 ± 2	
S15K3	GGTGCGGTACCCGGGGATGCGG	<i>S. aureus</i>	36,7	(Kusumawati et al. 2022)
R12.06	GATTACTATAATTTCTATCGTCCGACCGCCGTCA	Alpha Toxin	93.7 ± 7.0	(Vivekananda, Salgado, and Millenbaugh 2014)
AT-27	ACCCCTGCAGGATCCTTTGCTGGTACC-(N42)-AGTATCGCTAATCAGTCTAGAGGGCCCCAGAAT	Alpha Toxin	Not reported	
AT-33			Not reported	
AT-36			Not reported	
AT-49			Not reported	
APT^{SEB1}	CACTGGTCGTTGTTGTCTGTTGTCTGTTATGTTGTTTCGT	Enterotoxin B	Not reported	(DeGrasse 2012)
APT^{SEB2}	CCGTAGTGTGTTCTTATTCGTGTCTGTGTGTTCTGTGCG		Not reported	
Spiegelmer (B12b10 65)	GACGTCTTCGAATCCCCATACTGTGGCATTGGCTCAGGACGGTCTGGAGGATGGG GCTTGACGTC	Enterotoxin B	420	(Purschke 2003)

A15	TACTTATGCATTTCTCCCACGATCTTATTTGAGAGTGAC	Enterotoxin A	48.57 ± 6.52	(Y. Huang et al. 2014)
A1	AGGCGATTACGCTTCTTGTACTTCAATAACGACTCAACTC		92.17 ± 16.75	
S3	CCCGCCTCTGAGCATTATTAATGTTATACCTTACGGCTGG	Enterotoxin A	36.93 ± 7.29	(K. Wang et al. 2016)
S12	GCCACTGTGGACTTGTATTTCGTCTTTGCCGTCTAATTCG		79.35 ± 12.09	
C10	TATACTTCTAAAATTTGTTTGTATCTACGATGTTCTTCGT	Enterotoxin C1	65.14 ± 11.64	(Y. Huang et al. 2015)
T1-280/RNA	ACTGTCrGrCrGrCrArCrGrCrGrUrGrUrGrUrArGrUrArCrArCrArCrGrArUrCrGrCrGrCrGrCrArCrArArUrArU	IsdA	2.2 ± 0.5	(Wijesinghe et al. 2023)
T2-139040/RNA	CTGTCrArArUrUrUrGrArArUrArUrArUrArGrUrGrCrGrCrGrCrGrUrArGrUrGrUrGrUrArArArArArUrU		1.0 ± 0.3	
T3-117558/RNA	ACTGTCrArArUrUrUrGrArGrUrGrUrGrUrGrArUrCrArUrArUrArUrCrGrUrArGrCrGrCrGrCrUrArCrArArCrC		0.7 ± 0.4	
Antibac1	GCAGTTGCGGGACAGGGAGTGCGCTGCTCCCC	Peptidoglycan	415 ± 47	(Bakhshandeh et al. 2023)
Antibac2	GGGGACTAGAGGACTTGTGCGGCC		1261 ± 0.280	
G1	UCCGAACAGCGGAAGGUGGUUCGAAGUUGGGGCUUUGGA	Teichoic acid	Not reported	(S. R. Han and Lee 2014)
#2	GGGAGUUUUGAUACGGCUUCAUGCAGUAAUGUUUUUUAU		Not reported	
#18	UCCGAACAGCGGAAGGUGGUUCGAAGUUGGGGCUUUGGA		Not reported	

PA#2/8	AGCAACATGAGGGGGATAGAGGGGGTGGGTTCTCTCGCCT	spA	1060 ± 200	(Stoltenburg, Schubert, and Strehlitz 2015)
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Table 3 – List of aptamer selected on *S. aureus*

3.8. *S. aureus* & aptasensors

Over the past decade, aptasensors technology have seen significant expansion, notably in the area of food pathogen detection. Their ability to bind specifically to a wide range of targets, including whole cells, proteins and small molecules, has made them an attractive alternative to traditional detection methods. New innovative aptasensors have been developed for the detection of *S. aureus* including colorimetric, fluorescence, electrochemical and surface plasmon resonance (SPR)-based methods, which offer high sensitivity and flexibility for different applications. They are more easily integrated into portable devices for on-site testing, addressing the growing demand. The table below (Table 4) presents an important diversity of aptasensor develop for the detection of *S. aureus*. This table, adapted from the review by Chen *et al.* (2022), has been updated with the most recent aptasensors developed up to 2024.

Despite numerous advantages, several challenges remain. One major limitation is the stability of aptamers in complex food matrices, where interactions with other components can reduce their performance. They require optimization to maintain reproducibility and robustness, notably from laboratory settings to commercial applications. Nowadays, there is no aptasensors commercialized for the detection of *S. aureus*. Despite these challenges, chemical modifications to enhance stability in complex media and affinity are driving their increasing application in food safety

Detection methods	Strategy/Assay	Linear Range (CFU/mL)	LOD (CFU/mL)	Analysis time	References
Colorimetric	Gold nanoparticle-based colorimetric aptasensor using tyramide signal amplification (TSA) technology	$10^3 - 10^6$	9	1-2 h	(Yuan, Wu, et al. 2014)
Colorimetric	Visual detection based on aptamer recognition coupled to tyramine signal amplification	$10 - 10^7$	8	1-2 h	(Yuan, Yu, et al. 2014)
Colorimetric	Colorimetric based on Cu-MOF-catalysed chromogenic reaction with aptamer recognition and magnetic separation	$50 - 10^4$	20	1 h	(S. Wang et al. 2017)
Colorimetric	A chemiluminescence biosensor based on nicking enzyme amplification reaction and rolling circle amplification	$5 - 10^4$	5	2 h	(Xu et al. 2018)
Colorimetric	Colorimetric biosensor based on specific aptamer and catalysis of dsDNA-SYBR GreenI (SG I) complex	$10^2 - 10^7$	81	5-6 h	(T. Yu et al. 2020)
Colorimetric	On-site colorimetric based on aptamer-immobilized gold nanoparticles (aiGNPs)	$1.5 \times 10^7 - 5.3 \times 10^7$	1.5×10^7	1 h	(Lim, Ryu, and Hwang 2021)
Colorimetric	A colorimetry and fluorescence dual-signal strategy based on upconversion Nanoprobes	$56 - 56 \times 10^7$	20	/	(Ouyang et al. 2021)
Colorimetric	Multicolorimetric assay based on oxidase mimicking dioxide-coated ferriferrous oxide nanocomposites and oxTMB etching of gold nanocrs (AuNRs)	$10 - 10^6$	1,2 - 1,4	40 min	(Huiwen Zhang et al. 2021)

Colorimetric	Naked-eyes detection of <i>S. aureus</i> in powdered milk and infant formula using gold nanoparticles	$10^2 - 10^8$	7.5×10^4 and in milk 8.4×10^4	30 min	(Marin et al. 2022)
Fluorescence	A sensitive luminescent bioassay based on dual-color upconversion nanoparticles (UCNPs) and aptamer functionalized magnetic nanoparticles	$10 - 10^5$	8	40 min	(Duan et al. 2012)
Fluorescence	Aptasensor simultaneous detection of various pathogenic bacteria based on multicolor upconversion nanoparticles (UCNPs)	$50 - 10^6$	25	40 min	(Shijia Wu et al. 2014)
Fluorescence	Sensitive assay based on aptamer functionalized silica nuclease resistant oligonucleotides-capped nanokeepers	$800 - 10^4$	682	17 min	(Borsa et al. 2016)
Fluorescence	A dual-excitation sensing method based on aptamer functionalized quantum dots and upconverting nanoparticle	$50 - 10^6$	16	30 min	(Kurt et al. 2016)
Fluorescence	A dual recognition strategy using aptamer-coated magnetic beads and antibiotics-capped gold nanoclusters	$32 - 10^8$	16	3-4 h	(D. Cheng et al. 2016)
Fluorescence	A transcription aptasensor by using a light-up RNA aptamer	$10^2 - 10^6$	77	/	(Sheng et al. 2019)
Fluorescence	Fluorescent detection based on a finely designed functional chimera sequence, a molecular beacon (MB) and strand displacement target recycling.	$80 - 8 \times 10^6$	39	2 - 3 h	(R. Cai et al. 2019)
Fluorescence	A highly selective platform based on aptamer-gated nano-materials	$10 - 10^3$	2 in buffer and 5 in blood	1 h	(Pla et al. 2020)

Fluorescence	A fluorescent aptasensor based on strand displacement amplification (SDA) technology and unique self-assembled DNA hexagonal structure	$7-7 \times 10^7$	1.7	5 h	(R. Cai et al. 2020)
Fluorescence	A fluorescence biosensor based on a peptide mediated immunomagnetic separation technique and an immunofluorescence quantum dot technique	$10-10^7$	5.407 in buffer, 19.9 in tap water and 10.7 in milk simulation	4 h	(D. Wang et al. 2020)
Fluorescence	A colorimetry and fluorescence dual-signal strategy based on Upconversion Nanoprobes	$56-5.6 \times 10^6$	22	/	(Ouyang et al. 2021)
Fluorescence	A novel aptasensor based on aptamer-functionalized DNA-silver nanocluster nanofilm	$10^7 -10^{11}$	/	>12 h	(M. Yang et al. 2021)
Fluorescence	A new fluorescence biosensor using aptamer- and vancomycin -copper nanoclusters as dual recognition strategy	$10^2 -10^8$	80	45 min	(Bagheri Pebdeni, Mousavizadegan, and Hosseini 2021)
Fluorescence	A novel UCNP-based aptasensor for rapid and ultrasensitive detection of <i>S. aureus</i> by low speed centrifugation	$6.36 \times 10^2 -6.36 \times 10^7$	146	0,58 h	
Fluorescence	Fluorescent aptasensor for sensitive detection by coupling DNA walking and hybridization chain reaction (HCR)	$10^2 -10^8$	10	>3 h	(J. Zhang et al. 2024)
FRET	A multiplexed FRET-based aptamer biosensor using multicolor dyes as donors and carbon nanoparticles (CNPs) as a sole acceptor	$10^2 -10^6$	50	>3 h	(Duan et al. 2016)

FRET	A dual-recognition FRET sensor based on fluorescent vancomycin–gold nanoclusters and aptamer–gold nanoparticles	$20 \sim 10^8$	10	30 min	(M. Yu et al. 2017)
FRET	A FRET aptasensor based on self-assembled Fe ₃ O ₄ and multicolor fluorescent carbon dots (CDs)	$50 \sim 10^7$	8	30 min	(Cui et al. 2019)
FRET	A biosensing platform based on the binding protection effect of aptamer-cell complex	$10^2 - 10^7$	64	1 – 2 h	(Y. Lu et al. 2020)
FRET	A fluorescent turn-on aptasensor based on the FRET between green carbon quantum dot and gold nanoparticle	$10 - 10^8$	10	2 h	(Pebdeni, Hosseini, and Ganjali 2020)
FRET	A simple one-step FRET sensor based on the aptamer modified quantum dots (Aptamer-QDs) and antibiotic molecule of Teicoplanin functionalized-gold nanoparticles (Teico-AuNPs)	/	1/cellta	2 h	(Fu et al. 2020)
FRET	An efficient FRET sensor based on stimuli-responsive nanoprobe PDANSs-FAM-Apt	$0-3.5 \times 10^8$	1	6 h	(Ye et al. 2020)
FRET	A simple one-step FRET sensor based on aptamer modified quantum dots (aptamer-QDs) w and antibiotic of teicoplanin functionalized-gold nanoparticles (Teico-AuNPs)	$10^{-5} \times 10^8$	2 in buffer and 100 in milk	1 h	(Tao et al. 2021)
FRET	A FRET aptasensor based on Aptamer-functionalized gold nanoparticles (AuNPs-aptamers) and cDNA modified upconversion nanoparticles (UCNPs-cDNA)	$47-4.7 \times 10^7$	10.7	17 min	(Ouyang et al. 2021)

NSET	A one-step fluorometric strategy based on nanometal surface energy transfer (NSET) between carbon dots (CDs) and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs)	10^{-10^6}	10	1 h	(S. Yao et al. 2021)
Fluorescence imaging	A fluorescence microscopy imaging based on positive dielectro-phoresis (pDEP) driven on-line enrichment and aptamer-fluorescent silica nanoparticle (FNP)	50^{-10^6}	93 in deionized water and 270 in spiked water	1 -2 h	(Shangguan et al. 2015)
Fluorescence imaging	A quantitative fluorescence imaging platform on a smartphone based on aptamer-functionalized fluorescent magnetic nanoparticles	50 – 2000	10	10 min	(Shrivastava, Lee, and Lee 2018)
SERS	A SERS biosensor based on sandwich structure by using gold nanoparticles and MGNPs immobilized with aptamers	$10^2 -10^7$	35	2 – 3 h	(Hui Zhang et al. 2015)
SERS	A label-free SERS detection based on aptamer dependent <i>in situ</i> formations of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs)	10^{-10^7}	1.5	25 min	(W. Gao et al. 2017)
SERS	Dual-recognition SERS biosensor based on vancomycin- -Au@MBA as SERS tags and aptamerFe ₃ O ₄ @Au as specific magnetic concentration and dual-SERS substrat	10^{-10^7}	3	45 min	(Pang et al. 2019)
SERS	Fluorescence and SERS dual-mode biosensor based on gold nanoparticle-modified polystyrene microspheres (Au/PS)	$16-1.6 \times 10^5$	3	1 -2 h	(Lei et al. 2020)
SERS	A SERS aptasensor based on AuNPs functionalized polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) film	$43-4.3 \times 10^7$	13	>2 h	(A. Zhu, Ali, et al. 2021)

SERS	A SERS aptasensor based on artificial peroxidase enzyme regulated multiple signal amplified system	10^{-10} - 10^{-6}	1.95	>3 h	(Shuangshuang Liu et al. 2021)
SERS	A simple and novel biosensor based on target induced release of signal molecules from aptamer gated aminated mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) coupled with surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) technology	$47-4.7 \times 10^8$	17	13 min	(A. Zhu, Jiao, et al. 2021)
SERS	A SERS biosensor based on the sandwich recognition of aptamer-functionalized magnetic beads and polyphenolic SERS nanotags	10^2 - 10^8	100	1 -2 h	(Y. Huang et al. 2015)
SERS	Colorimetric-SERS dual-mode aptasensor for <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> based on MnO ₂ @AuNPs oxidase-like activity	10^1 - 10^7	0.926 (colorimetric) & 1.561 (SERS)	1h	(Jiahe Dai et al. 2024)
LSPR	A LSPR sensors based on aptamer at nanostructured plasmonic elements	/	10^3	2 min	(Khateb et al. 2020)
ECL	An electrochemiluminescence aptasensor based on the quenching effect of MoS ₂ -PtNPs-vancomycin to S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻ /O ₂ system	1.5×10^2 - 1.5×10^8	28	2 – 3 h	(D. Han et al. 2019)
CRET	An enhanced chemiluminescence resonance energy transfer aptasensor based on rolling circle amplification and WS ₂ nanosheet	$50 \sim 1.5 \times 10^5$	15	1 h	(L. Hao et al. 2017)
Potentiometric	A potentiometric biosensor based on chemically modified graphene (transducer layer of the aptasensor) and aptamers (sensing layer	/	1	1-2 min	Hernandez (2014)

DPV	An electrochemical immunosensor based on dual-aptamer-based sandwich by using streptavidin coated magnetic beads (MB) and silver nanoparticles immobilized with aptamers	10^{-10^6}	1	30 min	(Abbaspour et al. 2015)
DPV	A versatile signal-on electrochemical biosensor based on triple-helix molecular switch	$30-3 \times 10^8$	8	>3 h	(R. Cai, Zhang, Chen, Tian, et al. 2021)
DPV	A dual signal amplification electrochemical biosensor based on a DNA walker and DNA nanoflower	$60-6 \times 10^7$	9	140 min	(R. Cai, Zhang, Chen, Li, et al. 2021)
DPV	A pair-based sandwich-type electrochemical biosensor for sensitive detection of <i>S. aureus</i>	$1.9 \times 10^2-$ 2.5×10^4	39 in buffer and 414 spiked tap water	/	(Nguyen, Kim, and Gu 2022)
DPV & EIS	Vancomycin-based electrochemical biosensor to detection Gram-positive bacteria	/	2 and 100 in milk	45 min	(Novakovic et al. 2024)
EIS	Impedimetric biosensor based on aptamer as biological recognition element	10^{-10^9}	10	10 min	Reich (2017)
EIS	An electrochemical aptasensor based on gold nanoparticles/carbon nanoparticles/cellulose nanofibers nano-composite (AuNPs/CNPs/CNFs) at the surface of glassy carbon electrode	$12-1.2 \times$ 10^8	1	30 min	Ranjbar and shahrokhian (2018)
EIS	Electrochemical sensitive aptasensor based on a zeolite imidazolate framework-8 and gold nanoparticles	$1.5 - 1.5 \times$ 10^7	3.4	/	(Morsalpour et al. 2024)
Capacitance	A capacitance sensors array functionalized with aptamers	/	10	1 h	(Jo et al. 2018)

Conductimetric	An electrochemical aptasensor coupled with the combination of SPCE/AuNPs, for detecting the IsdA surface protein	10^{-10^6}	0.2	1 min	(Soleimani et al. 2024)
Volumetric	A bacteria-detection V-Chip based on the extraordinary catalytic activity of platinum nanozyme and the aptamer-modified magnetic beads	1^{-10^8}	1	1.5 h	(T. Huang et al. 2019)
TSM	A thickness shear mode (TSM) acoustic aptasensor with an antifouling probe linker for <i>S. aureus</i> detection	100^{-10^6}	33	Few min	(Spagnolo et al. 2023)

Table 4 – List of biosensors developed for *S. aureus* detection. This table is adapted from Chen et al (2022) and completed with recent new biosensors research.

Chapter 4

Manuscript 2

4. Second manuscript: Recent advances in aptamer based biosensors for bacterial detection

Aptamer-based biosensors have emerged as a promising alternative for the detection of pathogenic bacteria. The following review will present a comprehensive overview of advancements in this field, highlighting the limitations of conventional methods such as bacterial culture and PCR, which are often time-consuming, resource-intensive and unsuitable for real-time applications. We emphasize the advantages of aptamers and details the SELEX process for their selections. Recent innovations in structural and chemical modifications aimed to enhancing their stability and performance are also mentioned.

We reviewed various types of aptasensors, including electrochemical, optical and colorimetric biosensors with examples of their application in detecting bacterial cells, toxins and proteins for pathogens. Despite important advancements, the absence of commercially available aptasensor remain significant hurdles. In this review, we underscores the potential of aptamer-based technologies for the rapid, portable and cost effective detection of pathogens, offering a promising future in diagnostic innovation.

Manuscript 2

Recent advances in aptamer based biosensors for bacterial detection

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Review

Recent Advances in Aptamer-Based Biosensors for Bacterial Detection

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Abstract: The rapid and sensitive detection of pathogenic bacteria is becoming increasingly important for the timely prevention of contamination and the treatment of infections. Biosensors based on nucleic acid aptamers, integrated with optical, electrochemical, and mass-sensitive analytical techniques, have garnered intense interest because of their versatility, cost-efficiency, and ability to exhibit high affinity and specificity in binding bacterial biomarkers, toxins, and whole cells. This review highlights the development of aptamers, their structural characterization, and the chemical modifications enabling optimized recognition properties and enhanced stability in complex biological matrices. Furthermore, recent examples of aptasensors for the detection of bacterial cells, biomarkers, and toxins are discussed. Finally, we explore the barriers to and discuss perspectives on the application of aptamer-based bacterial detection.

Keywords: detection; biosensors; aptamers; bacterial pathogens; food security

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1. Introduction

Pathogenic microorganisms have posed a serious challenge to human health and well-being throughout history. They encompass a wide range of bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites that can be transmitted through food, water, soil, and air or through contact with infected individuals or animals. A survey for pathogens is one of the most important elements in tracing infectious diseases, determining the distribution of agents according to sites, and preventing their spread. Among bacterial pathogens, of particular concern are those resistant to the antibacterial drugs commonly used to treat infections, such as pathogenic strains designated by the acronym ESKAPE (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* species). These bacteria cause the majority of nosocomial and community-acquired infections worldwide [1,2]. In addition, more than 200 identified bacterial pathogens are associated with foodborne illnesses, which can occur through either foodborne infection (when ingested bacteria colonize and multiply in the human host) or foodborne intoxication (resulting from the consumption of food containing bacterial toxins). The most widespread foodborne and waterborne bacteria are *Escherichia coli* O157:H7, *Salmonella* spp., *Clostridium perfringens*, *Cronobacter sakazakii*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *S. aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Shigella* spp., *Clostridium botulinum*, *Vibrio* spp., and *Yersinia enterocoli* [3,4]. Some foodborne bacteria, such as *L. monocytogenes*, pose a significant risk due to their high mortality rates, while others, such as *Salmonella* and *C. jejuni*, present a high frequency of occurrence. Moreover, some pathogenic bacteria are spore-forming (e.g., *Clostridium botulinum*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Clostridioides difficile*) [5–7]. In their sporulated forms, bacteria are highly heat-resistant and survive most disinfection procedures used in the food industry or hospitals. Some bacterial toxins, such as staphylococcal enterotoxin B (SEB) and cereulide, are resistant to heat and may persist in food products for long periods. Additionally,

bacteria can form biofilms, which provide them with further protection against disinfection measures, making eradication more challenging.

Bacterial detection holds practical importance in the pharmaceutical industry, environmental control, and food safety. Foodborne infections and intoxication resulting from contaminated beverages or food are considered serious problems and have become more prevalent recently. In 2015, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that there had been 600 million cases of foodborne illnesses, representing 11.6% of the world's population and resulting in no fewer than 420,000 deaths. In 2019, it was estimated that 7.7 million deaths had been caused by pathogenic bacteria [8]. In the interest of public health and consumer protection, it is evident that there is a need to concentrate efforts to develop new methods for production control, including new detection techniques.

To reduce the risks and control disease progression, a diverse range of methods have been developed for pathogen detection, including culture methods and molecular methods, such as those based on nucleic acid amplification (e.g., polymerase chain reaction (PCR)) [9–11] and the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) [12]. Although they are the most frequently used methods for pathogen detection, they show many disadvantages that prevent efficient health security and sanitary control. Methods based on cultivation are time-consuming as they require several steps for bacterial enrichment, isolation, and identification. In addition, they can be performed only by qualified personnel and within a laboratory setting. Molecular methods are less time-consuming, but they also require a pre-enrichment step to increase the number of targeted bacterial cells and to prevent the detection of dead bacteria. In an effort to address these shortcomings, in recent years, the rapid development of biosensors for bacterial detection has been pursued. Biosensors are analytical devices that integrate a bioreceptor, which assures the recognition of the target, with a transducer, which converts the recognition event into a measurable signal, enabling the detection of chemical or biological analytes [13].

Among bioreceptors, aptamers, which are small, artificial, single-stranded DNA or RNA molecules (usually 20–100 nucleotides long), capable of binding to targets with high specificity and sensitivity, have emerged as specific sensing elements. Aptamers usually have no biological function but exhibit a strong affinity for specific targets through structural recognition, similar to the natural interactions observed between antigens and antibodies. Aptamers possess several advantages over expensive antibodies and stand out as strong candidates to replace them. They can selectively recognize the desired target with a strong affinity and specificity, and they can be easily customized to accommodate changes [14–16]. Due to such properties, aptamers have attracted significant attention in recent years for their potential to revolutionize various fields, including diagnostics and therapeutics, as illustrated in Figure 1.

This review focuses on the latest advancements in the use of aptamers for bacterial detection, and recent studies are discussed. In particular, we consider the strategies for the selection of aptamers and their kinetics, thermodynamics, and structural characterization. Furthermore, we discuss the principal methodologies and techniques used to enhance the overall efficiency and functionality of aptamers for improved target detection. Recently, two reviews have described aptamer identification, the transducer technologies used in aptasensors and nanomaterials for aptasensors [17–23]. Differing from these reports, the current review aims to demonstrate the present circumstances and the prospects of various aptasensors for the detection of pathogenic bacteria. In addition, this review analyzes barriers to the use of aptasensors and may assist researchers in developing user-friendly, low-cost, labor-saving, and point-of-care diagnostic devices.

Figure 1. Major aptamer characteristics and applications. Figure created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com/). (accessed on 2 April 2024).

2. Aptamer Selection Strategies for Bacterial Pathogen Detection

Aptamers, first developed in the early 1990s by two independent teams, Ellington and Szostak [24] and Tuerk and Gold [25], are distinct nucleic acid sequences with selective and specific binding to a target. These sequences are selected from a large pool of nucleic acids with an extensive sequence capacity, ranging between 10^{13} and 10^{16} , utilizing an in vitro selection technique known as the systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment (SELEX) [26,27]. SELEX is a series of selection and amplification steps in which a large pool of nucleic acid molecules binds to the desired target molecules under specific conditions, including a specific temperature and salt concentration. The molecules that bind to the target are isolated from those that remain unbound, and then they are amplified to generate a newly enriched population. This cycle is repeated until a small population of highly specific molecules is obtained.

The SELEX technique has undergone numerous modifications and improvements, making it more efficient, reliable, and affordable for the identification of aptamers, as detailed in [28–31]. The success of SELEX experiments relies heavily on the initial population. The initial pool of nucleic acids used in SELEX contains a random nucleotide region flanked by two constant regions, the primers, that enable amplification in the SELEX process to enrich the sequences that bind to the target molecule. The primers are usually nonessential nucleotides and are not involved in the folding process or used to recognize the target [32]. However, in some outlier cases, the primer region can participate in the aptamer structure's formation, particularly for a short random sequence [33–36]. The influence of the

random region length on aptamers has been studied, but overall, there is no significant correlation between the length and the aptamer's affinity and stability [37,38]. However, a longer random region enhances the complexity of the secondary and tertiary structures, while a shorter one provides better coverage and gives production advantages [39]. The optimal random region length was estimated to be 20–50 nt, while the primers' length was 20 nt [32]. More complex initial nucleic acid libraries are increasingly being used. For instance, secondary structures have been included in the initial random sequences to increase the likelihood of complex functional folds. A library containing modified bases, including sugar, backbone, and base modifications, has been shown to successfully generate aptamers, although several modified enzymes need to be utilized for the SELEX process [40–42].

Bacterial pathogen detection can be achieved indirectly by developing aptamers against secretory molecules such as toxins. Some bacterial toxins can survive pasteurization and resist high temperatures (<100 °C), indicating the bacteria's past or current presence. Thus, the indirect detection of bacteria is important for food, medical, and environmental safety. Toxins pose significant risks to food safety and the environment, with even low concentrations potentially harming human health. The detection of these toxins relies on labor-intensive processes and expensive laboratory equipment. However, the selection of aptamers to target small-molecule toxins faces challenges such as the inefficient separation of bound and unbound DNA, limited binding motifs on target surfaces, a lack of chemical groups for target immobilization, and difficulties in distinguishing between molecules with similar structures. Among the few aptamers for toxins documented in the current literature are enterotoxins, cholera toxins, and botulinum toxins, produced by *S. aureus*, *Vibrio cholerae*, and *C. botulinum*, respectively [43–52].

Another and more direct approach employs aptamers selected to act against a specific molecule of bacteria. Bacterial cell surfaces present a multitude of molecules, particularly proteins, including surface epitopes such as membrane and cell wall proteins or peptidoglycans, which can be chosen as a target for aptamer selection. However, this strategy requires prior knowledge of the surface molecule and its production in a pure soluble form, which may not accurately represent its cellular context. Furthermore, the epitope might not be accessible in its native environment. Achieving selectivity against a specific strain of bacteria requires the surface molecule to be exclusive to this strain, which presents a considerable challenge. Consequently, this strategy has been primarily successful in detecting a type of bacterium rather than a particular strain of bacteria. For instance, RNA aptamers have been reported that target teichoic acid in *S. aureus* [53], a component of the cell wall of most Gram-positive bacteria, as well as peptidoglycan-specific aptamers for the detection of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* [54] and, more recently, aptamers targeting *isdA*, a crucial surface protein for *S. aureus*' survival and colonization. Over time, this protein has gradually become a key marker for the detection of this bacterium [55,56].

Aptamers can be selected to detect a specific bacterium directly by using whole cells or spores as targets. This approach is termed cell-based aptamer selection or cell-SELEX [57,58]. It was first introduced in 1998 by Morris et al., who used human red blood cells to generate aptamers capable of selectively binding to unidentified molecular biomarkers present on the surfaces of live cells [59]. Many aptamers that selectively bind Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, such as *E. coli* [60,61], *C. jejuni* [62,63], *Streptococcus pyogenes* [64], *S. aureus* [65–68], *B. cereus* [69], *Salmonella typhimurium* [70], or *Listeria* spp. [71], can be found in the literature.

Cell-SELEX was shown to be effective in generating specific aptamers against a particular bacterium or even a particular clone. Similarly, the cell-SELEX procedure can be used with bacterial spores to develop specific aptamers. In their sporulated forms, bacteria exhibit higher resistance to various stress factors, such as UV radiation and heat, than the corresponding growing cells [72,73]. The conventional microbiological methods used to detect bacterial spores have lengthier procedures than those used for vegetative cell detection. This is because the spores are first subjected to germination; then, their vegetative cells are characterized. Therefore, conventional detection methods such as PCR or immunological

assays are not adapted to ensure full safety. In contrast, aptamers that bind to the surfaces of bacterial spores offer the potential for rapid and direct detection. In particular, aptamers have been developed and used in different aptasensors for the detection of spores from *Bacillus* species, which are ubiquitously present in air, water, and soil [74–76].

The procedure of cell-SELEX does not require purification or prior knowledge of a specific targeted surface epitope. Moreover, the proteins on the cell surface represent a more physiological and natural folding condition than purified proteins. However, cell-SELEX might be difficult to perform because the bacterial cell surface is negatively charged, leading to DNA repulsion from the cell surface [77]. Additionally, the process can introduce selection biases. For instance, the presence of dead cells in a suspension can result in non-specific binding, strongly influencing the selection. Another challenge lies in identifying the specific target(s) of the selected aptamers. The majority of the literature using cell-SELEX fails to demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of the targets.

Alternative *in silico* strategies have been developed in the last few decades. These methods are based on the computational screening of a large library of aptamer sequences to fit modeled target structures. These techniques require 3D structure predictions, through docking methodologies using software such as HADDOCK, AutoDock, or Xdock, enabling the study of aptamer folding and the selection of structural patterns responsible for the aptamer/target interaction based on the predicted affinity and Gibbs free energy (ΔG) [78–80]. The *in silico* method has been successfully conducted to select aptamers for bacterial surface proteins [81–83]. Another example is a recently employed computational screening method used to select antimicrobial aptamers against the pathogen *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [84]. The *in silico* strategy is a powerful and complementary tool to SELEX for the development of new aptamers against pathogenic bacteria. As a computational-based approach, it offers time savings and cost-effectiveness compared to SELEX. Nevertheless, *in silico* methods still require knowledge of aptamers' tridimensional (3D) structures and *in vitro* testing to confirm the binding interaction between the selected aptamers and the targets.

3. Aptamer Characterization: Affinity, Stability, and Structure

Aptamers are typically short, single-stranded nucleic acids, either DNA or RNA molecules, that can fold into various 3D structures. Nucleic acids are chemically and structurally stable. Both share similar functionalities and have their advantages: RNA aptamers offer more diverse and complex 3D structures that can enhance the binding specificity, and DNA is known for its stability and lower production costs [15]. They can recognize and bind their targets with high specificity and strong affinity in the nano- and picomolar ranges. The structural conformation of an aptamer depends not only on its base composition but also on its environment, including the pH, salt type, and ionic force. These parameters have a significant influence on the formation and stability of specific conformations of aptamers; they are particularly important for intercalated motif (I-motif) or G-quadruplex structures [85–88].

It has been shown that aptamers can adopt various tertiary structures, which can be categorized into three types: structures containing duplexes, loops, bulges (e.g., hairpins, pseudoknots, triplexes, and three-way junctions), G-quadruplexes, and I-motifs (Figure 2). The loop, bulge length, and base composition (Figure 2A), play a crucial role in the structure and function of aptamers, influencing their binding affinity and specificity [89–91].

Structures containing a duplex stem with different loops and bulges are very diverse (the loop length number and composition can vary), ranging from simple hairpins to pseudoknots (Figure 2A), all resulting in a spectrum of distinct conformations that participate in the target's selection. G-quadruplexes are four-stranded non-canonical nucleic acid structures that can form under physiological conditions [95]. G-quadruplex structures are stacked G-tetrads formed by four hydrogen-bonded guanines stabilized by cations (Figure 2B). They display remarkable structural diversity, capable of adopting various conformations depending on the sequence composition, loop size, salt type, and concentration [96,97]. In terms of stability, they exhibit high thermal and nuclease

resistance. Their structural features include a large hydrophobic planar surface (G-tetrad, Figure 2B) and high electrostatic density, providing a stable scaffold for aptamer selection through iterative rounds of amplification and selection. These unique properties contribute to their widespread use in selecting aptamers for various applications, including bacterial detection [98].

Figure 2. Schematic aptamer structures of three-way junctions and hairpins (A), G-quadruplexes and G-tetrads (B) and I-motifs and C•C⁺ base pairs (C). Below each schematic, a ribbon view of a representative structure in each category is displayed, [92] PDB code 6GzK, (A) [93] PDB code 148D, (B) [94] PDB code 1A83 and (C) PDB. The backbone is colored orange, and the bases are pink.

The intercalated motif (I-motif) is a structure involving a hemiprotonated C•C⁺ base pair formed under slight acidic pH conditions (Figure 2C). Although several aptamers have C-rich sequences [67], only one aptamer has been shown to form an I-motif [99]. None have been developed in the context of bacterial detection. This may be explained by the lack of structural studies on aptamers or the extensive use of secondary structure prediction, which does not predict I-motif formation. Aptamers that form an I-motif for bacterial detection represent a potential area for future research. Prediction software has been overwhelmingly used to predict the secondary structures of aptamers. However, these predictions consider simple rules of base pairing and free energy and fail to predict other secondary structures, such as G-quadruplexes or I-motifs [100–102].

Different methods have been used to evaluate the K_d , relying on either label-based or label-free techniques [103]. Label-based approaches, using fluorescent or radioactive labels, lower the detection limit in the experiments, resulting in the more accurate determination of the K_d . Label-free methods, such as surface-based detection methods, are also often used. One of the most commonly used methods is surface plasmon resonance (SPR), an optical method used to detect molecular binding interactions between one mobile and one fixed molecule. SPR is used to evaluate different kinetic parameters, such as the association and dissociation rate constant and the dissociation/association constant [104].

These traditional methods have been adapted to evaluate the binding affinity of an aptamer when the target is known, such as proteins or toxins that can be isolated or produced in a purified form. However, in the cell-based SELEX method, the target(s) for the aptamer is unknown. This, in turn, complicates the measurement of the kinetic parameters because the number of targets and their concentrations are unknown. This

uncertainty makes it challenging to measure the binding affinity accurately and necessitates complex protocols in terms of the detection sensitivity and apparatus, such as microfluidics. Several studies have estimated the K_d using fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) and fluorescence spectrophotometry [55,105–107]. Both methods require fluorescently labeled aptamers and cannot be performed in a multiplexed format.

Comprehensive descriptions of aptamers, including details on their thermal stability, topology, and structure, are essential for their effective utilization in various applications and in ensuring their effectiveness in real-life scenarios. The stability of nucleic acid structures can be evaluated through thermal denaturation experiments using either UV-CD absorption techniques or fluorescence techniques such as FRET [108–110]. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) is used to derive the thermodynamic parameters and stoichiometry of the aptamer/target interactions. Several factors can influence the melting temperature of an aptamer, affecting its stability, such as the base composition, length, structure, ionic strength, and pH [111–115]. Moreover, the potential conformational changes in aptamers upon binding with their targets are rarely explored and deserve further investigation [116]. Resolving an aptamer's high-resolution topology could lead to a better understanding of its target specificity and pave the way for the further optimization of its stability and specificity.

Various computational tools have been developed to complement the experimental characterization of aptamers. They can be applied in the preliminary stage of selection to complement SELEX, by designing high-affinity aptamers for the target, and in the final stage to optimize the aptamer's implementation. The main limitation of *in silico* approaches lies in the limited experimental data on the structures of aptamer/target complexes [117]. Prediction methods have been used to obtain successful topological indicators, but experimental data are required to gain insights into the structure adopted by an aptamer.

Different experimental methods can be used to gain insights into the folding of aptamers. Shape experiments, which chemically probe unpaired or paired base pairs, are used to determine the secondary structures of nucleic acids [118,119]. These experiments are convenient for long sequences. Spectroscopic methods such as UV, circular dichroism, or fluorescence can be used to obtain information on the folding topology of a nucleic acid [120]. For example, CD is widely used for G-quadruplex or I-motif structures to gain insights into the G-quadruplex topology [121]. These relatively easy methods can be used to examine the dependence of the secondary structure, such as the ion type and concentration, pH, and buffer composition. This is particularly true for I-motifs [122,123] and G-quadruplexes [124,125]. This information is crucial in establishing a protocol that ensures correct folding and the monitoring of their stability over time.

Three main experimental techniques have been used to resolve the structures of aptamers in free form or in complex with their targets: nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), X-ray crystallography, and cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-EM). All three methods can give rise to high-resolution structures (see [126] for a comprehensive analysis of aptamer structures). NMR uniquely investigates nucleic acids' conformational states and folding through simple 1D experiments. It monitors structures such as I-motifs, G-quadruplexes, or hairpins, specifically through the imino-proton chemical shift [127]. These methods provide detailed information and are becoming crucial in understanding the aptamer-binding mode. One notable example is an RNA aptamer's three-dimensional resolution, which was used to recognize the bacterial protein Hfq of *Bacillus subtilis* [128]. Recently, there has been growing interest in resolving these aptamers' complex structures [126,129,130].

Aptamers' chemical modification and optimization are being increasingly explored, serving as a crucial strategy to enhance their binding affinity, thermal stability, and protection against nucleases. These properties directly influence the overall suitability of aptamers for biosensing applications. One significant disadvantage of aptamers as oligonucleotides is their high sensitivity to nuclease degradation, which affects the detection in biological samples, especially in serum [131]. Temperature fluctuations can also impact aptamers' binding capacity and susceptibility to enzymatic degradation by nucleases. To overcome

these limitations, various chemical strategies have been devised to thermally stabilize, protect against degradation, and enhance the binding affinity of the active conformation of an aptamer.

Chemical modifications to the base, phosphate group, or sugar unit have been used to enhance aptamers' suitability [132–134]. For instance, the incorporation of non-natural phosphorothioate into the aptamer's backbone structure and the modification of the 5'-ends or sugar structures of strands were shown to slow down the hydrolysis of nucleases present in biological fluids while retaining their activity [135–138]. Another approach to avoiding the problems related to aptamer degradation is the incorporation of non-natural base pairs (such as 5-methyl-isocytidine) or the utilization of L-DNA to make strands highly resistant to nuclease attacks [139]. The majority of such chemical modifications aim to improve the stability of nucleic acid structures that are highly vulnerable to nuclease digestion, particularly in single-stranded segments and internal nicks.

Aptamers can acquire relative nuclease resistance when covalently linked to a protective group such as a protein. For instance, a DNA-type thrombin-binding aptamer was shown to resist a variety of serum nucleases when it was tightly bound to its target protein [140]. Moreover, different protective coatings of DNA strands increase their nuclease resistance. Lacroix et al. increased the stability of a DNA strand by coating it with human serum albumin and DNA dendrites [141]. In another study, an oligolysine–polyethylene glycol (PEG) coating was shown to protect DNA structures from low-salt denaturation and nuclease degradation [142]. The stability can also be improved via the ligation of strand termini or the introduction of terminal functional groups, such as hexanediol or hexaethylene glycol; through the crosslinking of nucleic strands via click chemistry; or through the formation of a thymidine dimer using ultraviolet irradiation [143,144]. These chemical modifications eliminate internal nicks once they are constructed. In a different approach, El-Khoury and Damha used chemical end-ligation to stabilize an intramolecular I-motif at both an acidic and neutral pH using deoxy-2-fluoroarabincytidine [145]. This method allows for the use of I-motifs on a large scale for in vitro applications such as detection.

Finally, the effect of nucleases on the aptamer structure can also be minimized by applying conditions to denature nucleases or by using nuclease inhibitors. For instance, detection in serum can be performed after serum heat pretreatment at 75 °C for 10 min, thus rendering most nucleases inactive [146].

4. Aptasensors for Bacterial Detection

Given the increasing prevalence of foodborne and infectious diseases, many aptamers have been selected and optimized to target bacteria, as illustrated in Figure 3. Biosensors that integrate aptamers as recognition elements are usually called aptasensors. The detection potential of aptamers plays a pivotal role in these biosensors' analytical performance. Fortunately, aptasensors can satisfy the REASSURED criteria (Affordable, Sensitive, Specific, User-Friendly, Rapid, Equipment-Free, Delivered, Real-Time, and Ease of Specimen Collection and Environmental Friendliness) established by the WHO for high-quality diagnostic devices that can be used across all levels of the healthcare system [147].

Aptamers possess a high binding affinity, comparable to that of monoclonal antibodies, and have several advantages over expensive antibodies when used in biosensors [148]. The primary advantages include their structural complexity and the possibility of fine-tuning through post-SELEX modifications, enabling the enhancement of their binding affinity and biochemical stability in complex matrices [149,150]. Moreover, in contrast to antibodies, aptamers provide ease of production due to their small sizes and have low immunogenicity [151–153]. Finally, these small nucleic acid molecules have lower synthesis costs compared to antibodies and can be easily customized to accommodate changes [154].

Aptasensors composed of aptamers that can be modified with an optical or redox reporter at one terminus and attached to the sensor via the other end transform the recognition of targets into a measurable signal that can be electrochemical, optical, or mass-sensitive. Moreover, some aptasensors combine different techniques; for example, a dual-mode

sensing platform for the detection of *Clostridium perfringens* was obtained that combined electrochemical signals and fluorescence [155].

Figure 3. Aptamer development and their application in bacteriology in the literature in the period of 1990–2023. Values were obtained by searching “aptamer” and “aptamer & bacteria” keywords in Scopus. Trends obtained by fitting a tendency curve and projecting it for the next 4 years.

4.1. Electrochemical Aptasensors for Bacterial Detection

Electrochemical aptasensors have immobilized aptamers on the working electrode, allowing for the conversion of the recognition event into a measurable electrical signal. Since the first reported electrochemical aptasensor for thrombin detection in 2004, devices have been developed that couple the use of aptamers with different electrochemical methods, such as amperometry (where a measurable current intensity is generated), potentiometry (where a potential is measured while keeping the current constant), voltammetry (where a current change is measured under controlled potential variations), and impedance (where a relationship between the alternative current and the applied sinusoidal potential in the frequency domain is measured) [156,157]. Electrochemical aptasensors enable bacterial detection in very small volumes of several μL , with high sensitivity.

Usually, thiolated DNA aptamers are employed because they can be covalently self-assembled onto a gold electrode. To provide robust and reproducible results, thiolated aptamers should be reduced to break the disulfide bonds between the aptamer molecules immediately before immobilization on a clean gold surface [158]. Alternatively, the electrode surface can be modified using nanomaterials to increase the active electrode surface, which in turn enables one to enhance the signal [20]. Compared to other analytical methods, such as chromatography or mass spectroscopy, electrochemical methods do not require sophisticated equipment or complex sample preparation steps and are affordable. Finally, electrochemical biosensors can be easily fabricated “in-house” and miniaturized into a hand-held format. Table 1 summarizes the recently reported aptamer-based electrochemical biosensors for the detection of bacterial cells or their toxins.

Infectious bacterial agents differ in numerous aspects, including their virulence factors, contagion, and transmission. All these factors and molecules, playing a role in the bacterial lifecycle, can be targeted by aptamers to enable specific and efficient bacterial detection and identification using aptasensors. There are significant practical advantages to the development of aptasensors for the detection of whole bacterial cells. The diversity of biomarkers and their abundance on a cell surface provide the potential for higher sensitivity than when targeting a single protein expressed at a low level. In addition, the targeting of whole cells facilitates the overall detection procedure, as the sample preparation stage prior to analysis is highly simplified [159]. In most traditional and molecular methods for bacterial detection, sample preparation is the most expensive and the most time-consuming step. Finally, the selection of specific aptamers is also facilitated because there is no

need for the lengthy process of purifying a specific target biomarker [160]. However, bacterial surfaces can vary in structure and composition depending on the environmental conditions. This bacterial adaptation to external conditions may modify their surface molecule compositions, which influences the reliability of diagnostic tests. This problem can be overcome by the utilization of a mixture of aptamers that target different surface epitopes of the target bacterium [161,162].

A recently developed bacterial electrochemical aptasensor was designed for the selective and ultrasensitive detection of *S. aureus* at the single-cell level using a sandwich assay [163]. The aptasensor relied on dual recognition through a bacteria-imprinted polymer film (BIF) and an aptamer (Figure 4). The BIF, which served as a capture probe, was fabricated on a glass carbon electrode, whereas the aptamer, which served as a detection probe, was functionalized with 6-ferrocenyl-hexanediol on gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). The aptamer was produced with a thiol on its 5'-end to allow its covalent binding to the AuNPs. After anchoring *S. aureus* on the BIF-modified electrode, the AuNP-aptamers were introduced to bind the captured bacteria, leading to an amplified current signal. The achieved ultrasensitive detection enabled the sensing of a single *S. aureus* cell in a buffer. The limit of detection (LoD) of the aptasensor was 10 CFU/mL when used in complex, lipid-rich media such as milk. This high sensitivity suggests the sensor's applicability in food safety and prevention.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration presenting (A) preparation of the BIF-modified glassy carbon electrode, (B) preparation of aptamer carrying signal nanoprobe, and (C) dual BIF-aptamer based electrochemical sandwich detection of *S. aureus* cells. Reprinted with permission from [163]. Copyright (2023). American Chemical Society.

In another recent example, Ding et al. [164] developed a novel ratiometric dual-signal electrochemical aptasensor for pathogenic bacteria at the single-cell level. This sensor was based on the aptamer-recognition-induced rolling circle amplification/G-quadruplex strategy [165–167]. G-quadruplexes can interact with various signaling molecules, including the electrochemical signal redox indicator methylene blue (MB). In this study, signal amplification was achieved through the utilization of two probes—one being an aptamer modified with ferrocene for the target bacteria and the other being the primer sequence for rolling circle amplification (RCA), anchored to the gold electrode with a sulfhydryl probe (Figure 5). These two probes formed a complex that was disrupted by the presence of the

target bacterium, *S. aureus*. Consequently, when contaminated samples were tested, only the RCA probe remained on the gold surface. To stimulate the RCA reaction, a C-base-rich circular template was introduced to the reaction mixture, generating a multitude of G-base-rich nucleic acid sequences that formed the RCA products into a G-quadruplex. Upon the addition of MB, the substantial cascade amplification of the electrochemical signals occurred due to the strong affinity of the G-quadruplex [168].

Figure 5. Schematic illustration presenting ratiometric dual-signal electrochemical biosensor for ultrasensitive detection of pathogenic bacteria based on aptamer recognition-induced rolling circle amplification (RCA)/G-quadruplex strategy. Adapted with permission from [164]. Copyright (2023) Wiley.

An electrochemical aptasensor was also designed for the detection of staphylococcal enterotoxin B (SEB), a potent bacterial toxin responsible for severe food poisoning [169,170]. The sensor utilized a commercial carbon screen-printed electrode modified with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) and gold nano-urchins (AuNUs). The electrode was further functionalized with a single-stranded DNA probe, followed by the attachment of a specific aptamer. Upon encountering SEB molecules, the aptamer detached from the electrode surface. Following this, the electrochemical signal of the redox probe, hematoxylin, decreased significantly (Figure 6). The aptasensor's analytical performance was validated with food samples, serving as simulated real samples. This tool surpassed a commercial ELISA kit in terms of SEB detection. Employing this method, the potential application of the aptasensor to food sample screening was demonstrated.

Aptamers can be combined with other sensing elements to improve the specificity and sensitivity of bacterial detection. For instance, the selective dual-aptamer-antibiotic-based sandwich detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* was recently developed [171]. In the system, vancomycin, which binds to the cell walls of Gram-positive bacteria, was immobilized onto a carbon electrode. This electrode concentrated the bacterial cells in less than 10 min in a highly efficient manner, as shown using impedance measurements. The captured bacterial cells were then identified using a strain-specific aptamer and differential pulse voltammetry (Figure 7). When applied directly in milk or bovine serum, the aptasensor identified *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* with an LOD of 100 CFU/mL in less than 45 min.

Alternatively, the robustness of bacterial detection can be improved by using a mixture of different aptamers targeting the same bacterium (Figure 8A). Kim et al. showed the signal enhancement and improvement in sensitivity obtained through the combinatorial use of aptamers immobilized on gold electrodes. The detection limit for *E. coli* achieved using the aptamers individually was approximately 18 times that obtained when the three

aptamers were used in combination, as demonstrated using cyclic voltammetry [162]. This high efficiency in *E. coli* detection was confirmed by the fluorescent signal observed with the mixture of the three aptamers, which was higher than that obtained for any single aptamer (Figure 8B). This enhancement likely resulted from the presence of numerous binding epitopes on the surface of a single bacterial cell.

Figure 6. Schematic illustration of fabrication process of SEB aptasensor using reduced graphene oxide and gold nano-urchins. Adapted with permission from [169]. Copyright (2019) Elsevier.

Figure 7. Schematic illustration of vancomycin/aptamer sandwich electrochemical detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*. A screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) was modified by drop-casting with bovine serum albumin (BSA). Vancomycin was attached to the surface, and ethanolamine was used as a blocking agent. When bacterial suspension was added to the surface, only Gram-positive bacterial cells were attached. In the last step, the captured bacterial cells were identified by specific aptamers. Adapted with permission from [171]. Copyright (2024) American Chemical Society.

Figure 8. (A) Schematic illustration of detection signal enhancement by a mixture of three aptamers for *E. coli* detection. (B) Intensities of fluorescence obtained by staining bacterial cell with single, double, and triple aptamers. Adapted with permission from [162] Copyright (2014) Elsevier.

4.2. Optical Aptasensors for Bacterial Detection

Optical aptasensors are among the most studied devices due their relatively easy utilization and high sensitivity, robustness, reliability, and potential to be integrated on a single chip. Optical transducer technologies include plasmon surface plasmon resonance (SPR), optical fibers, localized SPR (LSPR), surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS), and fluorescence-based and colorimetric sensors. These optical techniques allow bacterial detection with non-labeled aptamers. Some representative, recently developed aptamer-based optical biosensors are shown in Table 2.

Plasmonic sensors, such as SPR, LSPR, and SERS, employ gold or silver metallic thin films and nanostructures due to their higher optical absorption bands in the visible–near-infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum, called the plasmonic band. SPR couples the resonance of the evanescent field of transverse magnetic polarized light with an oscillating free electron wave bound at the metallic–dielectric interface. A conventional prism with a Kretschmann configuration can be used to achieve SPR-based biosensors for quantitative target detection. Although very sensitive, SPR sensors based on noble metal substrates suffer from low penetration depths (100–300 nm) into the dielectric medium above the surface, preventing the detection of bacterial cells of several μm . However, recently, portable SPR biosensors were developed for the monitoring of bacterial biofilms by coupling an insulator–metal–insulator structure with a higher penetration depth in the Kretschmann configuration [172].

When metallic nanostructures are used, the resonant field is associated with surface plasmons, which is referred to as LSPR. In these biosensors, the resonance wavelength

depends on the shape and size of the plasmonic nanoparticles and the surrounding medium. Based on this, LSPR aptasensors have been realized through aptamers' covalent or non-covalent immobilization on plasmonic nanoparticles. Kim et al. developed a label-free LSPR aptasensor for the detection of *Campylobacter* in contaminated chicken carcasses [173]. The specific aptamers were simply adsorbed onto gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and then mixed with the water used to rinse chicken carcasses. In the absence of the pathogen, the AuNPs were stable and showed a plasmonic band at 520 nm. However, in the presence of *C. jejuni* or *C. coli* cells, the aptamers desorbed from the AuNPs to bind to the target, causing the ion-induced aggregation of the AuNPs. The aggregated AuNPs showed a plasmonic band at 630 nm. The aptasensor was able to detect *Campylobacter* in chicken carcasses after a two-day enrichment period, with an LOD of 7.2×10^5 CFU/mL for *C. jejuni* and 5.6×10^5 CFU/mL for *C. coli*. A similar approach was used to detect *S. aureus* cells in milk and infant formulas [174]. Due to the use of nanoparticles instead of conventional prisms, LSPR biosensors possess a high surface-to-volume ratio for the sensing of surface-bacterial interactions. This enables the use of miniaturized LSPR devices with applicability for in-field measurements. Moreover, when only qualitative bacterial detection is sufficient, LSPR aptasensors provide instrument-free result visualization. The main disadvantage of these biosensors is their low sensitivity. The sensitivity of SPR and LSPR sensors can be improved by coupling them with enzymatic reactions or by labeling the aptamers with a fluorophore.

In SERS devices, the Raman signal can be enhanced by placing a bacterial cell within the localized electric field of the plasmonic nanoparticles to increase the Raman scattering cross-section and hence the detection signal [175]. SERS has high selectivity and can provide a single bacterial cell's detection due to the molecular fingerprint information. In addition, it is a fast and nondestructive method and can be used for in-field multiplex qualitative analysis. Bacterial cells are usually negatively charged and can be non-specifically immobilized on positively charged SERS substrates, as shown for *Salmonella typhimurium* [176]. However, aptamers can be used to specifically capture and immobilize a target bacterial cell to improve the specificity and selectivity of detection. For instance, an SERS-based aptasensor for the quantification of *Salmonella typhimurium* was designed by combining a Raman-active molecule, p-aminothiophenol (PATP), gold nanorods (GNRs), and cDNA, to which the aptamer could bind. In the absence of the target bacterium, the *S. typhimurium* aptamer was bound to the GNRs and specifically interacted with the cDNA, which prevented particle aggregation in a salt solution [177]. However, in the presence of both *S. typhimurium* and cDNA simultaneously, the aptamer no longer stabilized the GNRs in the salt solution, leading to particle aggregation, which gave rise to the SERS signal reflected by the attached component. Furthermore, the SERS intensity was linearly proportional to the *S. typhimurium* concentration, ranging from 56 to 56×10^7 CFU/mL, with an LOD of 9 CFU/mL. Due to the aptamer's specificity, the aptasensor showed high selectivity to other bacterial pathogens, and it was able to screen adulterated milk samples for the presence of *S. typhimurium*. Despite the many advantages of SERS aptasensors, they suffer from the requirement for sophisticated instrumentation to provide reliable detection.

Besides LSPR detection, colorimetric biosensors also provide the possibility for naked-eye bacterial detection. Bacterial spores remain a major concern in the food industry and hospitals as they are remarkably resistant to high temperatures, chemical agents, radiation, and harsh physical conditions. In their sporulated forms, bacteria exhibit resilience to unfavorable environmental conditions, making them the most resistant life forms known to date. Typically, they can withstand temperatures 40–45 °C higher than their corresponding vegetative cells. Additionally, spores can enter dormancy and survive in a wet state for thousands of years. Furthermore, spores are regarded as potential biological weapons. Indeed, *Bacillus anthracis* was initially used during the First World War. The dispersal of spores in the ambient air can result in the development of the respiratory form of anthrax. Due to these unique characteristics, in the context of biosecurity and food safety, researchers have developed aptasensors specifically designed to detect target bacteria

in their sporulated forms [5,74,178]. Recently, Rizzotto et al. developed a colorimetric assay for the detection of *Bacillus cytotoxicus* spores in food [19]. *B. cytotoxicus* belongs to a large group of bacteria commonly named the *Bacillus cereus* group [6,162]. The group is composed of different species; some of them are human pathogens (such as *B. anthracis*, *B. cereus sensu stricto*, or *B. cytotoxicus*) but others are harmless (such as *B. thuringiensis*, *B. weihenstephanensis*, and *B. mycoides*). The detection test relied on the spore-enhanced peroxidase-like catalytic activity of gold nanoparticles (Figure 9). The test was performed in a simple microtube containing AuNPs and magnetic beads (MP), both conjugated with a specific aptamer, BAS6R, as a recognition element for *B. cytotoxicus* spores. The presence of spores was detected with the naked eye due to the change in the color of the solution (blue to dark blue) upon the oxidation of tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) with H_2O_2 . This method has the advantage of the aptamer binding to an unknown epitope on the spore surface, eliminating the need to extract, purify, and amplify a specific biomarker. However, BAS6R was shown to bind to spores of different *B. cereus* species. It cannot thus distinguish between pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains of this group of bacteria.

Figure 9. Schematic illustration presenting colorimetric biosensor for detection of *B. cytotoxicus* spores based on spore-enhanced peroxidase-like catalytic activity of AuNPs. Adapted with permission from [19].

In another study, Zhou et al. developed a dual-aptamer microfluidic chip for the detection of both vegetative cells and spores of *B. cereus* [179]. To improve the selectivity and sensitivity of detection, aptamers selected through cell-SELEX were additionally, in a step-by-step manner, tailored and optimized using molecular docking. Based on this dumbbell aptamer design, the two best aptamers were obtained and integrated into a microfluidic chip biosensor. These two aptamers had repeated G-based structures, both with a strong affinity to the polar amino acids in the α -helix of the epiprotein of *B. cereus*. The biosensor was applied directly in food, such as milk and rice; provided a complete analysis within 1 h; and showed an LoD of only 9.27 CFU/mL.

As mentioned before, aptamers' structures are susceptible to matrix interference, which diminishes their ability to specifically bind to target bacteria and affects the specificity and accuracy of aptasensors. To avoid a high rate of false negatives when *Salmonella* was detected in food samples, Zhao et al. studied the dual-recognition effect of an aptamer and concanavalin A [180]. Concanavalin A bound to the lectin in the Gram-negative bacterium. The method consisted of the separation of *S. typhimurium* via aptamer-functionalized magnetic beads, and the salt-induced aggregation of concanavalin A protected the gold

nanoparticles (AuNPs). The developed visual method had improved specificity and sensitivity due to the targeting of different sites at the bacterial envelope.

4.3. Other Aptasensors for Bacterial Detection

Detecting bacteria is not always sufficient. Many bacterial pathogens, such as *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *C. botulinum*, *C. perfringens*, *C. difficile*, *B. cereus*, *C. jejuni*, *L. monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, and *Salmonella* spp., produce toxins [181–189]. Ingested bacterial toxins have various effects, ranging from disrupting cell membranes and causing cell death to interfering with the host immune response. They play a crucial role in the pathogenicity of many bacterial species, contributing to the symptoms and severity of bacterial infections [190]. For instance, *C. botulinum* toxins can cause botulism, a severe illness characterized by muscle paralysis, general weakness, and potentially fatal respiratory failure. The presence of *S. aureus* enterotoxins in food can lead to symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and severe diarrhea. As already mentioned, these toxins are thermostable and can rarely be eliminated by food treatment or preparation methods such as cooking, frying, or freezing, which can eliminate bacterial cells. Moreover, toxins can remain undetected by classical methods of pathogen detection. Usually, when strains are isolated, the presence of toxins is tested via the PCR amplification of the genes that encode them. This additional step prolongs the procedure and cannot be performed in the field. In addition, the presence of genes does not necessarily lead to toxin production. Thus, there is a need to directly detect the presence of bacterial toxins in food and biological samples. Some representative aptasensors are shown in Table 3.

To assess food safety, multiplex aptasensors have been developed for the detection of different targets in food samples. Jin et al. proposed a lateral flow strip (LFT) aptasensor for *Salmonella*, Hg^{2+} ions, and ochratoxin A (OTA) using upconversion nanoparticles (UCNP) as a signal source and a smartphone equipped with a CCD camera for detection [191]. This approach offers a fast and portable detection process. As illustrated in Figure 8, three different aptamers were used in the sensor, each grafted on the surfaces of differently colored UCNPs and hybridized with their complementary DNA (cDNA) fixed on the nitrocellulose membrane. In the presence of bacteria, ions, and small molecules, the three aptamers preferentially bound to their respective targets. Consequently, the liberated cDNA decreased the fluorescence from the UCNP. It was demonstrated that this device had no non-specific or cross-reactivity due to the separate color channels providing the detection signals. This feature was crucial to enable multiplexing. This method of detection holds great potential for the simultaneous detection of multiple targets in food samples to achieve enhanced safety (Figure 10).

A bacterial biological marker or bacterial biomarker can be defined as a specific characteristic that is measured as an indicator of a bacterium's presence, its biological processes, or its responses to external exposure or intervention, including therapeutic interventions. The detection of biomarkers enables various applications, such as the monitoring of infection and therapy efficiency, risk estimation, diagnosis, or the estimation of bacterial adaptation to environmental signals. Numerous aptamers have been developed to target a wide array of bacterial biomarkers, although targeting the entire cell is more common. Some aptamers have been developed for purposes other than detection, such as therapeutic or basic research applications. This technology has paved the way for new applications that are not only cost-effective but also capable of overcoming the limitations posed by conventional antibodies or various probes and drugs.

The methyl erythritol phosphate (MEP) metabolic pathway of isoprenoid biosynthesis is essential for many pathogenic bacteria, both Gram-positive and Gram-negative, such as *B. anthracis*, *Clostridium* spp., *L. monocytogenes*, *S. enterica*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Shigella* spp., *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Recently, a DNA aptamer, D10, was developed to target 1-deoxy-D-xylulose-5-phosphate reductoisomerase (DXR), the second enzyme of the MEP pathway [192]. This aptamer was modified with a fluorescent label and allowed the strong, specific staining of MEP+ bacterial cells (*E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*), while no staining

was observed with bacteria lacking the DXR enzyme (e.g., *E. faecalis*). It thus presents the potential to replace the specific antibody for future therapeutic and diagnostic applications.

Figure 10. Schematic illustration of lateral flow assay based on three different aptamers for simultaneous multiple targets detection. (A) sample pad design, sample pad in (B) negative and (C) positive reaction, (D) front and (E) profile view of the device. Adapted with permission from [191]. Copyright (2018) Elsevier.

More recently, an antagonist aptamer for SEB neutralization was selected through SELEX [193]. SEB is a critical virulence factor in staphylococcal toxic shock syndrome (TSS), triggering the robust release of proinflammatory cytokines by activating T lymphocytes. The aptamer demonstrated effectiveness in inhibiting SEB-induced proliferation and cytokine secretion in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells. These results highlight the potential therapeutic value of the novel aptamer antagonist in mitigating SEB-mediated TSS, and it represents a promising avenue for future therapeutic strategies.

Another expanding aptamer application was described by Stoltenburg and his co-workers [98], who explored an alternative approach to develop aptamers that bind a bacterial surface protein. In contrast to cell-SELEX, which selects specific aptamers that bind unknown targets at the bacterial cell surface, their procedure was based on selecting aptamers that recognize a purified surface protein of *S. aureus*, called protein A. This protein is a major component of the cell wall of *S. aureus*. The obtained protein-A-binding G-quadruplex aptamer was integrated into an enzyme-linked oligonucleotide assay (ELONA). They demonstrated that the aptamer and its truncated versions bound to protein A expressed by the intact cells of *S. aureus*. Some structural information about the aptamer used was also gathered because the aptamer's functionality was shown to be tightly linked to its structure. Such insights into the structural basis of aptamers' functionalities enhance our understanding of the molecular bases of their interactions and pave the way for the development of novel, more robust aptamer-based diagnostic tools.

Many bacterial virulence factors are exported by external vesicles. All Gram-negative bacteria secrete outer membrane vesicles (OMVs), proteoliposomes derived from their outer membranes, with sizes between 20 and 250 nm. OMVs play crucial roles during host-microbe interactions because they transport a broad range of molecularly diverse cargo, including adhesins, toxins, membrane-embedded and -associated proteins, small molecules, lipids, peptidoglycans, and nucleic acids. Shin et al. selected aptamers that bound the OMVs of multiple Gram-negative bacteria [194]. The aptamers, selected through

cell-SELEX, showing the strongest affinity to bind Gram-negative bacterial cells were conjugated with horseradish peroxidase (HRP) and used in an enzyme-linked aptamer assay (ELAA) to detect the OMVs. An LOD of 25 ng/mL was obtained. The recognition of the OMVs was expected because secreted vesicles contain similar proteolipids to their cells of origin. The authors suggested that the detection of bacterial OMVs was more effective than the detection of bacterial cells in clinical samples.

5. Conclusions

In the realm of pathogenic bacteria, biosensors developed for their rapid and accurate identification and monitoring offer important added value in preventing their spread, reducing treatment expenses, and ensuring food safety. Biosensors offer numerous advantages compared to traditional microbiological methods due to their enhanced sensitivity and rapidity. Currently, the identification of a microorganism typically takes between one and several days when plating or PCR-based protocols are employed. In contrast, biosensors may provide a complete microbiological analysis within several hours or even minutes [195,196]. Biosensors also hold the potential to be portable, multiplex, and accessible to a wide range of users [197,198].

Aptamers have been used extensively as an alternative to conventional antibodies in various biosensing strategies, including electrochemical, optical, and microfluidic chip-based platforms. Compared to antibodies, aptamers have a shorter production time (a few hours compared to a few days or even months), a lower cost (10- to 100-fold less expensive), higher stability in complex matrices, and the ability to bind a variety of specific targets, which enables their tailored application. However, the impact of replacing antibodies with aptamers in the lifecycle of biosensors remains to be examined. Regarding the latest research, trends in the use of aptasensors for bacterial detection include the development of portable biosensors that combine easy sample preparation with highly cost-effective biosensing strategies. Nonetheless, antibodies, which have been used for decades, are still far superior in terms of commercially available immunosensors. With this review, we aimed to demonstrate the potential of aptasensing in allowing the direct quantification of bacterial cells or toxins.

The specificity of detection and the accuracy of the overall analysis may be improved by the use of dual-aptamer probes, where the first aptamer acts as a capturing probe and the second is a detection probe. Moreover, a mixture of various aptamers, each targeting different epitopes of the same bacterium, can be employed to achieve higher accuracy in detection. To address the specificity limitations in aptasensors, the current research also considers the combination of aptamers and other sensing elements, such as vancomycin or concanavalin A, that also specifically bind bacterial cells.

Signal amplification strategies in aptasensors can be achieved by using different nanomaterials, catalysis amplification, hybridization chain reactions, and rolling circle amplification [20]. The extension and application of these strategies should be considered in further surface chemistry investigations related to improvements in the aptamer's immobilization onto the nanomaterial-modified sensor surface. The efficiency of nanostructured sensor surfaces to act as a filtering porous layer helps to eliminate the possible interference of the biological matrix and provides highly selective and sensitive detection. Moreover, aptamers adopting specific structural 3D conformations, such as G-quadruplexes, have been shown to provide high signal intensities (REF). The utilization of aptamers of specific 3D structures as recognition elements appears to be a smart and cost-effective approach to the development of sensitive biosensors [199]. At the same time, aptamers' structural changes upon target binding may induce signal transduction and/or result in target-triggered amplification, which highly simplifies device development [200]. Considering that the primary sequences of many selected aptamers suggest that they adopt a specific 3D structure, it will be helpful to determine their secondary and tertiary structures for biosensor development. Indeed, a precise understanding of how aptamers interact with their targets will facilitate the design of more efficient and selective biosensors. This is especially relevant

for aptamers adopting I-motifs (C-rich sequences) [67], which have still not been explored for bacterial detection.

6. Future Directions

Aptasensors require significant improvement to become a standard technique for microbiological applications. Indeed, there is a significant number of papers presenting proofs of concept, but there are only a few commercially available aptasensors that can be utilized at the level of the food industry or in hospitals. First, most SELEX procedures are performed using the same oligonucleotide pool, and not all selected aptamers are highly specific. Second, the selection and structural characterization of aptamers are usually performed under defined conditions, but their configuration and binding properties can be modified upon temperature, ionic strength, or pH variations, resulting in a significant reduction in their binding affinities. Consequently, although some aptasensors provide efficient bacterial detection in the buffer, they are inefficient when applied in biological or food samples. Therefore, it is highly important to characterize the individual aptamer sequences within environments that mimic real matrices. These studies should be completed with chemical modifications of the aptamers to stabilize the active conformation to ensure robust detection. Third, commercialization requires standards and standardized aptasensor specifications. Moreover, employing low-cost biodegradable materials or developing reusable aptasensors could significantly reduce the costs of bacterial detection. The future research directions should include fully automated aptasensors, integrating sample preparation, reaction chips, and signal generation, to decrease the assay time and improve the storage stability. Another important barrier in the application of aptasensors is aptamer degradation in biological matrices containing DNase or RNase enzymes. Nevertheless, the chemical modification of aptamer molecules can be performed to prevent such degradation, although this is rarely performed. Alternatively, to develop a highly stable aptasensor, a pragmatic approach could be to use a real matrix and/or a biosensor surface starting from the initial stage, i.e., the SELEX process.

We anticipate that aptamers, which can be both diagnostic and therapeutic elements, could facilitate the prevention of bacterial infections. In this double configuration, the detection of specific bacterial pathogens could trigger targeted antimicrobial drug release. The design of such systems for food safety or healthcare may be cyclical but requires a fundamental understanding of the aptamer/bacteria interactions. It is obvious that multidisciplinary approaches at the intersection of molecular biophysics, microbiology, and engineering will play pivotal roles in transitioning aptasensors from the lab to immediate, in-field detection.

Table 1. Aptamer-based optical biosensors for bacterial detection. Aptamer sequences are provided in Supplementary Data.

Bacterium	Aptamer	DNA or RNA	Target	K_d (nM)	LOD	Linear Range (CFU/mL)	Ref.
<i>S. aureus</i>	T1	RNA & DNA	IsdA protein	2.2 ± 0.5	113 pM	/	[56]
	T2			1.0 ± 0.3	17 pM		
	T3			0.7 ± 0.4	11 pM		
	A14			4 ± 2	485 pM		
<i>S. aureus</i>	SH-Apt ₂	DNA	Whole cell	210.7	/	/	[61,201]
<i>S. aureus</i>	SA20	DNA	Whole cell	70.86 ± 39.22	/	/	[65]
	SA23			61.50 ± 22.43			
	SA34			72.42 ± 35.23			
	SA31			82.86 ± 33.20			
SA43	210.7 ± 135.9						
<i>S. aureus</i>	Apt1	DNA	Whole cell	35	$7.5\text{--}8.4 \times 10^4$ CFU/mL	$10^4\text{--}10^8$	[174,202]
	Apt2			129			

Table 1. Cont.

Bacterium	Aptamer	DNA or RNA	Target	K_d (nM)	LOD	Linear Range (CFU/mL)	Ref.
<i>S. aureus</i>	H1 H2 cApt	DNA	/	/	10^1 CFU/mL	10^2 – 10^6	[203]
<i>S. aureus</i>	A15	DNA	Enterotoxin A protein	48.57	8.7×10^{-3} μ g/mL	0.01–10 μ g/mL	[204]
<i>S. aureus</i>	H1 H2	DNA	Whole cell	/	4–8 CFU/mL	45 – 4.5×10^6	[205]
<i>E. coli</i>	SH-Apt ₁	DNA	Whole cell	25.2	/	/	[55,123]
<i>E. coli</i>	E1 E2 E3	DNA	Whole cell	/	3.7×10^2 CFU/mL	/	[162]
<i>E. coli</i>	/	DNA	Whole cell	/	45 CFU/mL	10^2 – 10^8	[206]
<i>E. coli</i>	/	DNA	Whole cell	/	0.05 CFU/mL	0.1 – 10^4	[207]
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	F23	DNA	Whole cell	17.27 ± 5.00	10^4 CFU/mL	/	[208]
<i>B. cereus</i>	/	DNA	Whole cell	/	22 CFU/mL	49 – 49×10^6	[209]
<i>B. cereus</i>	/	DNA	Whole Cell	/	4 CFU/mL	20 – 2×10^8	[210]
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	AB K2	DNA	Whole cell	5.377 6.8	10 CFU/mL	10 – 10^5	[211]
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	K2	DNA	Whole cell	/	10 CFU/mL	10 – 10^5	[211]
<i>Leptospira interrogans</i>	LAP3	DNA	Outer, membrane protein	133.13	57 CFU/mL	60 – 6×10^5	[212]
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	A8	DNA	Internalin A	/	10^3 CFU/mL	10^3 – 10^5	[213]
<i>Salmonella</i>	Multi-apt	DNA	Multi	11.72	7 CFU/mL	10 – 10^7	[214]
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	/	DNA	Whole cell	/	3 CFU/mL	10 – 10^9	[215]
<i>Bacillus cytotoxicus</i>	BAS6R	DNA	Spore	/	10^2 – 10^4 CFU/mL	10^3 – 10^4	[19]
<i>Clostridium difficile</i>	No name	DNA G-quadruplex	Toxin A protein (TOA)	/	1 nM	0–200 ng/mL	[216]
<i>S. typhimurium</i>	STA	DNA	Whole cell	/	9 CFU/mL	56 – 56×10^7	[177]
<i>S. typhimurium</i>	H2	DNA	Whole cell	/	4–8 CFU/mL	36 – 3.6×10^6	[205]
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	Apt ST	DNA	Whole cell	10	30 CFU/mL	10^2 – 10^6	[217]
<i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i>	Apt VP	DNA	Whole cell	16.88	10 CFU/mL	10^2 – 10^6	[217]
<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	ONS13 ONS-23TA	DNA	Whole cell	292.8 ± 53.1	7.2×10^5 CFU/mL	/	[62,173]

Table 2. Aptamer-based electrochemical biosensors for bacterial detection. Aptamer sequences are provided in Supplementary Data.

Bacterium	Aptamer	DNA or RNA	Target	K_d (nM)	LOD	Linear Range (CFU/mL)	Ref.
<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibac1&2	DNA	Peptidoglycan	$415 + 0.047$ $1261 + 0.280$	82 pg/mL	/	[54,218]
<i>S. aureus</i>	Apt1	DNA	Whole cell	35	10–100 CFU/mL	10 – 10^5	[163,171]
<i>S. aureus</i>	P1	DNA	Whole cell	/	10	10 – 10^6	[164]
<i>S. aureus</i>	A-SEB	DNA	SEB protein	0.02	0.21 fM	5.0–500 fM	[169]
<i>E. coli</i>	ECA I ECA II	DNA	Outer membrane proteins (OMPs)	/	/	1×10^{-7} – 2×10^{-6} M	[219,220]

Table 2. Cont.

Bacterium	Aptamer	DNA or RNA	Target	K_d (nM)	LOD	Linear Range (CFU/mL)	Ref.
<i>B. cereus</i>	B15 B16	DNA	Whole cell	16.13 20.67	10 CFU/mL	/	[106]
<i>B. cereus</i>	13–18 13–24	DNA	Whole cell	22.75 36.72	9.27 CFU/mL	/	[179]
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	/	DNA	Whole cell	/	150 CFU/mL	1×10^3 – 1.0×10^8	[221]
<i>Clostridium difficile</i>	/	DNA G-quadruplex	Toxin A protein (TOA)		1 nM	0–200 ng/mL	[216]
<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>	/	DNA	MPT64 protein	8.92	4.1 fMl	/	[222]

Table 3. Other aptamer-based biosensors for bacterial detection. Aptamer sequences are provided in Supplementary Data.

Bacterium	Aptamer	DNA or RNA	Target	K_d (nM)	LOD	Linear Range (CFU/mL)	Ref.
<i>S. aureus</i>	APT ^{seb1}	DNA	Staphylococcal enterotoxin B (SEB)	/	/	/	[51]
<i>S. aureus</i>	G1 #2 #18	RNA	Teichoic acid	/	/	/	[53]
<i>S. aureus</i>	H1	DNA	/	/	41 CFU/mL	4.1×10^1 to 4.1×10^5	[223]
<i>S. aureus</i>	AT-27 AT-33 AT-36 AT-49	DNA	α -toxin protein	/	/	/	[224]
<i>E. coli</i>	GN6 GN12	DNA	Outer membrane vesicles (OMV)	29.94 20.36	/	/	[194]
<i>E. coli</i>	6-3 8-1 8-7 8-8 8-12 8-13 8-19 8-35	RNA	Heme	188 309 256 371 445 425	/	/	[225]
<i>E. coli</i>	Stx1 stx2	DNA	Shiga toxin Viz, stx1, and stx2	47 pM 29 pM	44.5 pg/mL 41.3 pg/mg	50 pg/mL 100 ng/mg	[226]
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	F23	DNA	Whole cell	17.27 ± 5.00	10^4 CFU/mL	/	[208]
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	CT916		Cholera toxin (CT)	48.5	2.1–2.4 ng/ml	0–10 ng/mL	[45]
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	/	DNA	Whole cell	/	1 CFU/mL	$1-10^8$	[155]

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/bios14050210/s1>, Table S1: Sequences of aptamer used in biosensors for bacterial detection.

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Part II

Manuscript 3

Opportunistic pathogens such as *S. aureus* possess a remarkable ability to adapt to complex and dynamic environments, enabling them to persist and proliferate in diverse niches ranging from infected tissues to food environments. Among these environments, milk and serum are particularly intriguing due to their distinct biochemical compositions and their implications in both human and animal infections.

Serum, as a component of blood, is rich in proteins, lipids, and immune factors, posing significant stress on bacteria that must evade host defenses. In contrast, milk, as a complex biological matrix and food medium, provides an abundant source of lipids and sugars, fostering bacterial growth. The ability of *S. aureus* to modulate its metabolism, cell envelope composition, and protein expression in response to these environments is therefore crucial to understanding its virulence and resistance to antimicrobial treatments.

A deeper understanding of *S. aureus* adaptation mechanisms in these environments is essential not only for predicting the evolution of its pathogenicity but also for developing more effective strategies for control, treatment, and identification. In particular, aptamer-based detection methods, such as aptasensors, for the rapid diagnosis of *S. aureus* in complex matrices like milk and serum. However, bacterial adaptation to these environments can alter key characteristics of *S. aureus*, including its cell envelope composition and structure, potentially affecting the efficiency of aptamers that were selected in a specific buffer during the SELEX process. It is therefore crucial to assess how these variations impact bacterial recognition and to develop detection approaches that account for these adaptations to ensure reliable and robust sensing.

Manuscript 3:

Serum and milk environments influence the virulence, antibiotic susceptibility, and resistance to reactive oxygen species in *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Figure 6. Adaptation of *S. aureus* to milk or serum contributes to the virulence *in vivo*.

Abstract

Staphylococcus aureus is a major pathogen in mammals, known for its ability to acquire antibiotic resistance and adapt to harsh conditions. The environment contributes to shaping the factors that induce bacterial fitness. Here we show that *S. aureus* displays distinct envelope features according to whether it is cultivated in milk, serum, or laboratory BHI medium, including differences in membrane fatty acid composition and staphyloxanthin pigment production. A comparative proteomic analysis indicated widespread protein expression differences affecting metabolic and biosynthetic pathways: remarkably, growth in milk stimulated expression of numerous virulence factors, whereas growth in serum led mainly to upregulated stress responses. The differential proteome and membrane lipid levels when comparing *S. aureus* cultures in milk, serum, and BHI were associated to marked differences in bacterial tolerance to reactive oxygen species and antibiotics, and in virulence as demonstrated in an insect infection model. Our study indicates that pathogen survival strategies involve diverse mechanisms, and that foodborne *S. aureus* growth, as shown here in milk, can be a predisposing factor that prepares bacteria for infection.

Introduction

The major bacterial pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* causes an array of diseases ranging from minor skin infections to more serious infections, including osteomyelitis, endocarditis, necrotizing pneumonia and life-threatening sepsis¹. A notable feature of this pathogen is its antibiotic resistance, particularly in methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), which can exhibit extensive resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, accounts for over 60% of *S. aureus* isolates in US hospitals². Historically, MRSA was first reported in 1961 in the United Kingdom in a clinical isolate, while in 1972 the first foodborne MRSA strain was found in milk from Belgian cows with mastitis^{3,4}. *S. aureus* is among the most common pathogens isolated from mastitis milk, and poses a significant health concern in dairy cattle⁵. The recovery time after infection can be long in cows, because *S. aureus* can persist in teat canals, teat lesions, and mammary glands. During this period, milk is spoiled and unsafe for human consumption and affected animals can act as a reservoir for staphylococcal transmission to humans⁶. Mastitis is estimated to cost the global dairy industry up to USD 35 billion per year (<https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/bovine-mastitis-market-103482>).

Upon infection, *S. aureus* senses and adapts to environmental cues by expressing a large number of virulence determinants, including secreted and envelope-associated molecules⁷. Adaptation to stress environments such as encountered in the host requires major metabolic reprogramming and cellular envelope remodeling⁸⁻¹⁰. Despite our current understanding of the biological processes underlying *S. aureus* adaptation in milk and serum^{11,12}, little is known about the fitness factors that enable *S. aureus* growth, survival and antibiotic adaptation in these natural environments.

The Gram-positive bacterial envelope is a complex semipermeable diffusion macromolecular layer that contributes to control bacterial fitness and preserve the cell integrity from surrounding conditions by sensing and triggering responses. Fatty acids (FAs), the principal elements in membrane phospholipids, play a significant role in

staphylococcal survival and adaptation to variable environments including foods and the host. They contribute to membrane fluidity, energy production, and virulence regulation, enabling the pathogen to withstand environmental stresses¹³. *S. aureus* synthesizes saturated branched-chain FAs and straight-chain FAs, by its fatty acid synthesis system pathway (FASII)¹⁴⁻¹⁶. In addition, *S. aureus*, like most known bacteria, can also scavenge environmental/host FAs, and incorporate them into its membrane phospholipids¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Notably, incorporated exogenous FAs can be saturated and unsaturated and of different chain length and side chains, such that membrane properties, e.g., thickness and fluidity, are altered, thus compromising bacterial function and survival^{20,21}. By dynamically adjusting membrane thickness and fluidity, *S. aureus* can thrive in a variety of environmental niches, enhancing its survival, virulence, and resistance to external stresses. Besides in *S. aureus*, the triterpene carotenoid pigment staphyloxanthin contributes to membrane resilience²². Having a rigid and planar structure, staphyloxanthin embedded within the membrane reinforces its structural integrity by reducing membrane fluidity and packing the lipids more tightly. The increased rigidity enhances the membrane's mechanical strength, protecting bacterium from environmental and host immune-mediated damage²³⁻²⁵.

Here, we sought to determine how two model environments for *S. aureus* multiplication, adult bovine serum and cow milk, affect *S. aureus* properties. We show that these natural environments modified membrane composition and modulated *S. aureus* resistance to oxidative stress and resistance to some antibiotics. We found surprisingly broad protein expression modifications, notably affecting primary metabolic processes, stress responses, and virulence. Growth in milk led to a remarkable upregulation of virulence factors and proteins involved in stress-response, as reflected in higher infectivity *in vivo*. These results establish a strong correlation between the virulence potential of strains and the biotopes from which *S. aureus* is sourced.

Figure 1. Exogenous fatty acid incorporation and growth of *S. aureus* JE2 in serum or milk. (a) Growth curve of *S. aureus* JE2 was assessed in BHI, serum and milk by plating dilutions on BHI agar at given time points. Data represent mean \pm SD of three independent experiments. Error bars that are smaller than the dots are not shown. (b) The JE2 strain (wild-type) cultured in BHI synthesizes fatty acids *de novo* and its FA profile is dominated by *ai*:15:0 (12-methyltridecanoic acid), its elongation products (*ai*:17:0, *ai*:19:0) and saturated straight chain fatty acids (C16:0, C18:0, C20:0). (c) FA profiles of *S. aureus* JE2 wild type and its $\Delta fabD$ mutant grown in 100% raw cow milk. $\Delta fabD$, which cannot synthesize fatty acids in *de novo* way, has similar FA profile as that of the surrounding milk used for culturing. The wild type JE2 strain incorporated exogenous branched fatty acids (like 18:1) from milk, elongated them (like 20:1) but also expressed endogenous FAs (like *ai*:15). (d) FA profiles of *S. aureus* JE2 wild type and its $\Delta fabD$ mutant grown in 100% adult bovine serum. $\Delta fabD$ has similar FA profile as that of the surrounding serum used for culturing, while the wild type JE2 strain did both incorporation of exogenous FAs from serum and production of endogenous FAs. (e) Fatty acid species are presented as the proportion within the total FA membrane composition. Shown is the average of three independent experiments. While *ai*:15 represented 55.79% of total FAs in wild-type JE2 cells grown in BHI, it counted for only 6.62% and 15.5% in serum- and milk-adapted cells, respectively. See Supplementary Fig. 3 for proportions of saturated and unsaturated FAs. (f) Membrane fluidity of wild type JE2 and its $\Delta fabD$ mutant adapted to various media was evaluated based on Laurdan generalized polarization (Laurdan GP). Laurdan GP = $(I_{440} - I_{490}) / (I_{440} + I_{490})$, where I_{440} and I_{490} are the emission intensities at 440 and 490 nm, respectively, when excited at 350 nm. Individual data points ($n = 5$ biologically independent samples) are shown together with mean \pm SD. P values were determined by an ordinary one-way ANOVA (*** $p < 0.0001$; ** $p < 0.0008$).

Results

***S. aureus* integrates exogenous FAs from milk or serum in membrane phospholipids.**

We inoculated cells of type MRSA derivative JE2 in laboratory (BHI) medium, milk, and serum, and compared their growth kinetics during a 24h period. *S. aureus* grew robustly in 100 % raw cow milk, with no significant lag phase (Fig. 1a). This was not the case in 100% adult bovine serum, where bacterial growth was preceded by a latency phase, followed by slow growth compared to BHI medium. The latency phase observed might suggest that *S. aureus* adapt to inhibitors present in bovine serum, including immunoglobulins and polyunsaturated FAs that exert antimicrobial activity against staphylococci²⁶. In contrast to the observed multiplication of *S. aureus* in bovine serum, a previous study described that *S. aureus* survived but not replicated in human serum²⁷, suggesting species-specific defense efficacy against the bacterium. *S. aureus* cells grown and adapted to the two media will be referred to as serum-adapted and milk-adapted cells.

Environmental FAs constitute an energy source and may be directly incorporated in bacterial membranes²⁸⁻³⁰. We analyzed exogenous FA incorporation upon *S. aureus* growth in serum and milk by comparing their FA profiles with that of cells grown in BHI. *S. aureus* JE2 strain in BHI synthesized predominantly anteiso branched-chain FA *ai*15:0 (also its elongation products *ai*.17:0, *ai*.19:0), and produced straight-chain FAs, mainly C18:0 and C20:0 (Fig. 1b), in keeping with previous reports³⁰⁻³². By contrast, *ai*15:0 was not the main FA in *S. aureus* when grown in either bovine serum or milk (Fig. 1c and 1d). To investigate the respective portion of FA incorporation and synthesis in adapted cells, we compared the FA profiles of the JE2 strain with those of its isogenic Δ *fabD* mutant, both adapted to serum and milk under similar conditions. FASII activity is turned off in strains lacking a functional *fabD* gene, which encodes the FASII initiation FabD protein (malonyl CoA-acyl carrier protein transacylase)³¹

(Supplementary Fig. 1). The *S. aureus* $\Delta fabD$ strain relies on exogenous FAs, and was able to replicate in serum and milk (Supplementary Fig. 2). The FA profiles of both wild-type and mutant strains, clearly reflected the FA composition of the medium they were adapted to (Figs. 1c and 1d).

The wild-type strain FA profile comprised both self-synthesized FAs, and unsaturated FA C18:1, which is necessarily derived from medium, as *S. aureus* does not synthesize unsaturated FAs. In addition, FA elongation products appeared, due to FASII activity. In contrast, milk-adapted $\Delta fabD$ incorporated milk-derived FAs but did not elongate them as FASII is non-functional (Fig. 1e). Surprisingly, although *ai.15* comprises < 3% of total FAs in cow milk³³, the $\Delta fabD$ mutant concentrated it to 10% while it incorporated no C18:0 (Fig. 1e). FA profile of serum is more complex than that of milk, and in particular comprised long-chain unsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids (C18:1, C18:2, C18:3, C20:3 and C20:4) (Fig. 1d, upper profile). These FAs were efficiently incorporated in both $\Delta fabD$ and JE2 strains (Fig. 1d and 1e, and Supplementary Fig. 3). Surprisingly, the serum-adapted wild-type JE2 was unable to elongate unsaturated fatty acids, whereas the milk-adapted cells successfully synthesized C20:1 from incorporated C18:1 (Fig. 1c and 1d). This finding aligns with the inhibitory effect of polyunsaturated FAs, which are abundant in serum, on FASII³⁴. Stopping FASII and elongation may increase membrane fluidity.

Together, the FA analysis indicates a high similarity in FA profiles in the wild-type and $\Delta fabD$ mutant adapted to serum and milk, which confirms that *S. aureus* preferentially incorporates exogenous FAs instead of synthesizing them *de novo*. It is notable that the FA profiles of the same strain cultivated in different environments share nearly no common features (compare JE2 profiles in Fig. 1 b, 1c, and 1 d). We speculate that bacterial phenotypes would be markedly impacted in these three environments.

We asked whether membrane fluidity is affected by adaptation to milk, serum, or BHI conditions. Adapted cells were labeled with the membrane fluidity-

sensitive dye Laurdan³⁵. Laurdan intercalates into the membrane bilayer and exhibits a fluorescence emission wavelength shift dependent on the amount of adjacent water molecules³⁶. Penetration of water molecules into the membrane depends on the packing density and fluidity of the lipid bilayer, which can be quantified by measuring generalized polarization (GP) of the Laurdan dye³⁵. Remarkably, serum-adapted and milk-adapted *S. aureus* displayed striking differences in membrane fluidity: while serum-adapted bacteria were highly fluid, the milk-adapted JE2 showed significantly decreased membrane fluidity. BHI-grown JE2 showed intermediate membrane fluidity (Fig. 1f left). The difference associated with milk-adapted and serum-adapted conditions was also seen in the $\Delta fabD$ mutant (Fig. 1f right). Greater rigidity of milk-adapted cell membranes may be due to an enrichment of long-chain FAs compared to BHI cultures, although the presence of other membrane structures may also contribute to membrane rigidity. In contrast, increased membrane fluidity of serum-adapted bacteria (Fig. 1f) is in line with the incorporation of polyunsaturated FAs from serum that loosens lipid packing (Fig. 1d). Collectively, these findings indicate that *S. aureus* modulates its plasma membrane composition and fluidity during adaptation to FA-rich environments such as milk and serum. In both media, *S. aureus* replaces endogenously synthesized FAs with environmental FAs, preserves membrane integrity, and maintains growth, albeit under very different physiological conditions. Moreover, it appears that milk, which lacks 'fluidifying' and potentially toxic polyunsaturated FAs, seems to be a more favorable environment for *S. aureus* growth than serum

Figure 2. Serum and milk modulate *S. aureus* envelop. (a) Representative transmission electron microscopy images of milk-adapted and serum-adapted JE2 cells. Arrows indicate envelope thickness. Scale bar, 500 nm. (b) Dot blot graph of the cell envelop thickness of JE2 cells calculated from cross-sections. Each dot represents a measurement for a single cell. (c) Bacterial cell sizes as determined from their cross-sections using ImageJ. The boxplots of panels show the median diameter distribution (thick line within boxes) and the degree of variability (amplitude of the box) for JE2 adapted to different media. (d) BHI-grown and serum- and milk-adapted JE2 cells were stained with 3 µg/mL BODIPY™ FL-vacomycin to visualize cell walls. Fluorescence values were quantified using ImageJ. Graphs represent the mean ± SD of three independent experiments. (e) Permeability test was performed using EthBr efflux assay with fluorescent reading taken for 60 minutes at 1-minute intervals, at 37 °C in PBS. Maximum intracellular accumulation of EthBr was observed with BHI-grown JE2 cells while milk- and serum-adapted JE2 cells were less permeable. Values represent means of three biologically independent samples. Error bars not shown for clarity. (f) Autolysis examined in milk- and serum-adapted JE2 cells resuspended in PBS with 0.5% Triton X-100. Saturation phase cultures in BHI were used as a reference. Data presents mean ± SD of $n = 3-4$ biologically independent samples. (g) Electrophoretic mobilities determined by zeta potential in PBS of BHI-grown and serum- and milk-adapted JE2 as a measure of cell surface charge. Data represent five independent runs with three replicates per run and are presented as mean ± SD. (h) Hydrophobicity of BHI-grown and serum- and milk-adapted JE2 cells determined based on the bacterial affinity between PBS and xylene solvent. The affinity to adhere to liquid hydrocarbons was estimated by measuring OD_{600} in the aqueous phase before and after mixing. Results show the average and range of biologically independent triplicates. P values in **b**, **c**, **d** and **h** were determined by an ordinary one-way ANOVA (**** $p < 0.00001$; *** $p < 0.0001$; ** $p < 0.0008$; * $p < 0.0160$). (i) - Summary schematic representation of the observed effects on fluidity, permeability, autolysis, and charge of *S. aureus* in serum (left) and milk (right). In serum, the more spaced lipids with unsaturated FAs indicate a more fluid and permeable membrane. The small dark blue circles represent the passage of molecules through the lipid bilayer. The brown Pac-Man illustrate autolysins.

Variations in *S. aureus* envelope thickness, permeability, surface charge, and hydrophobicity between milk and serum environments.

As FA composition modulates lipid packing density and membrane fluidity³⁷, we asked whether FAs derived from milk or serum affect physical and functional *S. aureus* envelope or cell size. Transmission electron microscopy performed on ultrathin cross-sections of *S. aureus* stationary phase cells revealed well-separated spherical cocci (Fig. 2a). Envelopes of the milk-adapted *S. aureus* JE2 were markedly thicker than those of serum-adapted or BHI-grown cells (Fig. 2a and Supplementary data Fig. 4). Quantitative analysis of envelope thickness, excluding the thread-like structures around serum-adapted cells, confirmed that envelopes of milk-adapted JE2 were about 2-fold thicker than those of serum- or BHI- adapted bacteria (39.35 nm compared to 22-29 nm respectively, Fig. 2b). Moreover, cross-sectional quantification of cell diameters showed that serum-adapted *S. aureus* cell diameters were smaller compared to the two other groups (Fig. 2c). In contrast, although milk-adapted cells had significantly thicker envelopes compared to cells from BHI cultures, there was no significant change in their total cell diameters.

Microscopy further revealed an irregularly textured surface of serum-adapted JE2, compared to the smooth surfaces in milk-adapted and BHI bacteria (Fig. 2a and Supplementary Fig. 4). The textured bacterial surfaces may come from aggregated medium components that associate with the cell surface³⁸, or bacterially inefficiently processed peptidoglycans, as observed in human serum^{11,39}. To distinguish between these possibilities, we stained cell walls with BoDipy-Vancomycin. This labeling indicated that serum-adapted *S. aureus* bound significantly higher levels of BoDipy-vancomycin than milk-adapted and BHI-grown bacteria (Fig. 2d). The increased binding of vancomycin suggests a lower efficiency of serum-adapted cells to process peptidoglycans.

The marked differences in *S. aureus* envelope properties according to growth medium led us to assess physical properties of the envelope, i.e., permeability, autolysis, surface charge and hydrophobicity. Permeability was analyzed using the ethidium bromide (EtBr) diffusion assay⁴⁰. The thick peptidoglycan layer of Gram-positive bacteria permits small molecules like EtBr to penetrate via passive diffusion, where it intercalates with DNA, enhancing fluorescence emission. Compared to bacterial cells grown in BHI, both serum- and milk-adapted cells showed lower EtBr permeability (Fig. 2e). This finding could reflect the changes in envelope morphology in response to environmental factors from serum and milk. Low permeability of EtBr highlights the increased resistance of adapted JE2 to the diffusion of small molecules in and out of bacteria.

The rates of JE2 autolysis in the serum-adapted, milk- adapted, and BHI cultures were assessed using a Triton X-100 based assay⁴⁰. After 5 h, autolysis was near-total in BHI-grown bacteria (just 15 % of the initial optical density remained), while autolysis of serum-adapted bacteria was less pronounced (55% in initial optical density remaining). Remarkably, no autolysis occurred for the milk-adapted bacteria (Fig. 2f); this correlates with the significantly thicker cell envelopes observed by electron microscopy (Fig. 2a). The intermediate and total recalcitrance to lysis might be related to the observed thread-like surface in serum-adapted cells and markedly thicker envelopes in milk-adapted cells. Lower autolytic activity could modify bacterial virulence and resistance to antibiotics^{41,42}.

Surface charge and hydrophobicity of JE2 adapted to two media were compared. The *S. aureus* electrostatic charge is conferred by surface factors such as ionized phosphoryl groups of the teichoic acid, lipoteichoic acid (LtaS), and unsubstituted carboxylate groups of the peptidoglycans that are exposed to the external environment⁴³. Peripheral electronegativity was assessed by zeta potential measurements that quantify the electrophoretic mobility of cells in an electric field⁴⁴. Milk-adapted bacteria displayed a lower negative surface charge than serum-adapted

or control cells grown in BHI (Fig. 2g). In addition, both milk- and serum-adapted JE2 cells were significantly more hydrophobic than cells grown in BHI (Fig. 2h).

Taken together, the differences in permeability, autolysis rate, surface charge and hydrophobicity (Fig. 2i), indicate that milk and serum trigger changes in the *S. aureus* envelope that might alter their fitness for infection, or for survival in their different biotopes.

Figure 3. Proteomic analysis in *S. aureus* when adapted to milk and serum. (a) Schematic representation of the sample preparation protocol for MS analysis. (b) Venn diagram showing the number of identified proteins detected in bacterial cells adapted to milk and serum or cultured in BHI to saturation in five biological replicates. (c) Volcano plot depicts the magnitude (\log_2 fold change) and statistical significance (q -value) of the change proteomic levels of the expressed proteins in JE2 between milk-adapted and BHI cultured and (c) between serum-adapted and BHI cultured. Horizontal dashed lines indicate fold change threshold ($|\log_2$ fold change $|=0.58$), vertical dashed lines indicate statistical significance threshold (q -value = 0.05). Red spots indicate significantly upregulated proteins, and blue spots indicate significantly downregulated proteins. (e-g) Heatmaps of significantly different proteins (Z-scored) involved in (e) the FASII pathway, (f) stress-response and (g) virulence, comparing milk-, serum-adapted JE2 and JE2 cells grown in BHI. All sample conditions are shown.

Proteomic analysis of *S. aureus* in milk-adapted, serum-adapted, and BHI-grown *S. aureus*

We employed a label free quantitative proteomics approach to investigate how protein expression profiles of *S. aureus* JE2 vary between milk-adapted and serum-adapted *S. aureus*. BHI-grown bacteria were used as reference. A principal component analysis (PCA) based on imputed LFQ (label-free quantification) intensities for which proteins needed to be present in at least 50% of the samples in one group showed that the biological replicates cluster together while the hierarchical clustering analysis revealed significant variations in protein profiling between conditions (Supplementary information Figs 6 and 7). The proteome identified a total of 1725 proteins among the three groups, of which 44 and 41 were unique for serum- and milk-adapted cells, respectively; 57 proteins were expressed in both adapted cells but not in cells grown in BHI (Fig. 3a, Supplementary Data 1).

Common and differentially produced proteins were identified using a p-value threshold of <0.05 and a fold change (FC) threshold of >1.5 . In all, 672 proteins were differentially expressed in milk-adapted cells vs. BHI group (332 up-regulated and 340 down-regulated) (Fig. 3b) and 642 were differentially expressed in serum-adapted cells vs. BHI group (443 upregulated and 209 downregulated proteins) (Fig. 3c). Besides, there were 630 differentially expressed proteins in serum-adapted vs. milk-adapted JE2 cells (446 were up-regulated and 164 were down-regulated) (Supplementary information Fig. 9). Interestingly, levels of numerous FASII-related proteins were the highest in serum (Fig. 3d, and Supplementary information Fig. 8), and overall lowest in milk. Expression of FASII initiation proteins were low in milk-adapted bacteria, possibly in keeping with the high availability of FAs in this medium that could reduce the need for *de novo* FASII synthesis. In milk-adapted cells most represent downregulated proteins were FabD, AccB, PdhC, PdhD, and FabH involved in FA synthesis initiation, and FabZ and FabF involved in FA elongation (Supplementary information Fig. 8). Surprisingly, LtaS expression was high in milk-adapted bacteria (1.66-fold up-regulated vs. BHI), but low

Top GO TERMS: Unique and Upregulated Milk

Top 20 KEGG Pathways: Unique and Upregulated Milk

Top GO TERMS: Unique and Upregulated Serum

Top 20 KEGG Pathways: Unique and Upregulated Serum

Figure 4. Proteomic reprogramming in milk- and serum-adapted *S. aureus*. Gene Ontology (GO) term enrichment analysis of detected differentially expressed proteins ($P < 0.05$) for molecular function (MF), biological process (BP), and localization of detected proteins in cell component (CC) between milk-adapted JE2 cells vs. cells cultured in BHI (a) and serum-adapted JE2 cells vs/ cells cultured in BHI (b). Barplot graphs for Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) functional annotation of the differently expressed proteins in milk-adapted JE2 compared to controls in BHI (c) and serum-adapted compared to BHI (d) with a P_{adj} threshold cutoff of 0.05. The longer bar means the more proteins enriched while color indicates the Level 2 subcategories within the pathway related processes or functions. Source data are provided as a Source data file.

in serum-adapted bacteria (3-fold down-regulated) compared to BHI cultures. LtaS is required for synthesis of lipoteichoic acid, which provides bacterial integrity and is implicated in virulence^{45,46}. Greater LTA production correlates with a reduction in autolysis⁴⁷, which might contribute to the observed decrease in autolysis in milk-adapted bacteria.

Unique and upregulated proteins were analyzed for their functions based on the Gene Ontology (GO) database. We detected 31 stress-response proteins differentially expressed in three groups (Fig. 3e, Supplementary data 2). These proteins participate mainly in adaptation to pH (arginase, alkaline shock protein 23, supermidine N(1)-acetyltransferase), osmotic stress (oxygen-dependent choline dehydrogenase, ABC transporter), oxidative stress/detoxifying (catalase, superoxide dismutase, Iron-regulated surface determinant proteins, peptide methionine sulfoxide reductase), pigmentation (serine-protein kinase, RNA polymerase sigma factor), and protein-refold (ATP-dependent Clp protease, chaperone proteins, chaperonins). In addition, 49 virulence-related proteins were differentially expressed in three groups (Fig. 3f, Supplementary data 2). Notably, milk-adapted cells had ≥ 2 -fold up-regulated proteins involved in virulence acting on secretion (Type VII secretion system and ESAT-6 secretion machinery) compared to both serum-adapted and BHI growth cells (Fig. 3f) suggesting that milk-adapted cells have a high virulent potential. Surprisingly, surface proteins Spa, ClfA/B, SdrD/E, Coa were strongly repressed in both serum- and milk-adapted cells compared to those grown in BHI. The reduced expression of these proteins could alter the surface charge and polarity of the adapted cells (Figs. 2g and 2f), potentially influencing their adhesion capabilities and overall pathogenicity.

Differentially expressed protein numbers and corresponding GO biological process (BP), cell component (CC) and molecular function (MF) categories are presented in Figs. 4a and 4b. Among both serum- and milk-adapted groups, proteins enriched in the BP category were involved in cellular (%), cellular metabolic (%), metabolic (V%) and primary metabolic processes (SHS%). Additionally, MF-

enriched proteins were mainly associated with catalytic and binding activities, whereas in both groups CC-enriched proteins were associated with intracellular anatomical structure (involved in maintaining bacterial cell integrity, division, and functionality), cytosol (proteins essential for metabolism, stress response, and protein synthesis) and cytoplasm (metabolic proteins and proteins synthesis machinery, DNA repair, stress response, energy generation and storage). Remarkably, the top unique and upregulated proteins in serum-adapted cells involved approximately six times more genes compared to those in milk-adapted cells (Figs. 4a and 4b). This observation suggests that serum presents a more stressful environment for *S. aureus* than milk.

To further analyze differentially expressed proteins, we performed Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) analysis. Metabolic pathways, biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, carbohydrates, antibiotics, and amino acids were the highest enriched pathways in both milk- and serum-adapted JE2 vs. BHI (Fig. 4c and 4d). Amino acids enable protein and ATP production in cells, which can be related to stress response⁴⁸. Besides, the enrichment of ABC transporters suggests that *S. aureus* adjusted transmembrane traffic of substances needed for bacteria growth in milk and serum⁴⁸. This is in line with the observed enrichment in two-component systems, which are critically involved in *S. aureus* response to changes in temperature, oxidative stress, osmotic pressure, and antibiotic exposure⁴⁹. Particularly, pathways of infection, glycerolipid metabolism, peptidoglycan biosynthesis, and quorum sensing were only enriched in milk-adapted cells, which strongly suggests that adaptation to milk increases the virulence of *S. aureus* compared to both BHI and serum. In contrast, the aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis pathway, which is linked to the production of functional proteins involved in cellular metabolism, stress responses, and adaptation to environmental conditions⁵⁰, along with the pentose phosphate pathway (PPP), that generates NADPH essential for the survival of *S. aureus* in hostile environments⁵¹, were enriched in serum-adapted but not in milk-adapted cells. Overall, *S. aureus* employs condition-specific mechanisms for survival and adaptation. It seems that milk

adaptation mainly enhances virulence, while serum adaptation prioritizes stress resilience, suggesting distinct environmental pressures.

Figure 5. Adaptation of *S. aureus* to milk environment induces resistance to oxidant killing and some antibiotics. (a) Pigmentation in cell pallets of BHI-grown, and milk- and serum-adapted JE2. Cell pallets from 1 mL cultures were collected, washed and photographed. **(b)** Expression of pigments in *S. aureus* cells adapted to milk and serum or grown in BHI. The pigments were extracted from cells and assessed by UV-Vis measuring. Triple pic is due to the presence of various carotenoids in JE2 namely staphyloxanthin, 4,4'-diaponeurosporene and 4,4'-diapolycope. **(c, d)** Singlet oxygen susceptibility of wild type **(c)** and Δcrt mutant **(d)** JE2 *S. aureus* adapted to milk and serum. After exposure to singlet oxygen, controls and samples were serially diluted, spotted on BHI agar and grown overnight to estimate survival. The experiments were repeated at least three times and data are shown as mean \pm SD. Differences were examined by ordinary one-way ANOVA for multiple comparisons; *** $p < 0.0008$, * $p < 0.016$. **(e)** Decreased susceptibility of the milk-adapted JE2 *katA* transposon (*katA::Tn*) to killing by hydrogen peroxide compared to the serum-adapted cells. Results shown are representative of at least three repeated experiments. Error bars, SD. P values were determined by an ordinary one-way ANOVA (* $p < 0.016$). Image shows the representative experiment. **(f)** MIC, minimum inhibitory concentrations as determined by turbidity for different concentrations of antibiotics after 24 h. Bacterial solutions containing adapted cells in saturation phase were diluted in corresponding medium and dispatched in 96-wall plate. Bacteria were exposed to increased concentration of antibiotics. Bacterial survival in milk was calculated after dilution spotting on BHI agar. Results are reported as mean of three independent experiments.

Resistance of serum- and milk-adapted *S. aureus* to oxidative stress and some antibiotics

The marked differences in levels of proteins involved in stress, virulence, and metabolism between milk-adapted and serum-adapted *S. aureus* led us to compare their susceptibility to oxidative stress. We assessed production of a documented oxidative stress resistance factor, the pigment staphyloxanthin, which constitutes a first line of defense against oxidative stress^{23,52}. Differences in pigmentation were detected by visual inspection (Fig. 5a), and by the presence of a triple-peak spectral profile characteristic of staphyloxanthin²³ (Fig. 5b). Pigment was clearly visible and detected in extracts of stationary phase milk-adapted and BHI-grown *S. aureus*. In contrast, pigment in serum-adapted cell extracts was below detection levels. The reduced pigmentation of serum-adapted JE2 may relate to the observed increased membrane fluidity (Fig. 1f) since staphyloxanthin confers rigidity to the bacterial membrane^{23,24,53}.

The observed variations in pigmentation (Fig. 5a), membrane fluidity (Fig. 1f), and altered stress response proteins (Fig. 3f) between milk- and serum-adapted *S. aureus* led us to compare cultures for susceptibility to oxidative stress and antimicrobials^{6,54}. Milk-adapted and serum-adapted cells, were washed and resuspended in PBS prior to ROS challenge to assure identical test conditions. Milk-adapted bacteria conferred remarkably greater resistance to singlet oxygen killing than serum-adapted cells (4-log difference; Fig. 5c). To verify whether this resistance is related to staphyloxanthin, we tested a non-pigmented JE2 *crtM* transposon mutant (*crtM::Tn*) deficient in the dehydrosqualene synthase (CrtM) which catalyzes the first step of staphyloxanthin biosynthesis^{52,53,55}. Survival to singlet oxygen treatment of the milk-adapted non-pigmented *crtM* mutant was poor compared to the milk-adapted parental strain (Fig. 5d). Nevertheless, the milk-adapted *crtM* mutant showed greater survival to singlet oxygen treatment than the serum-adapted *crtM*, indicating that factors other than staphyloxanthin production contribute to ROS tolerance. Similarly,

another *S. aureus* strain, the non-staphyloxanthin-producing RN4220, showed intermediate ROS survival in milk-adapted cultures, while serum-adapted RN4220 were eliminated (Supplementary Fig. 10). To exclude the possibility that traces of milk rested attached to bacterial cells despite washing and then buffered the effect of ROS, the serum-adapted JE2 cells were incubated in raw milk for 1h to enable milk molecules to adsorb (a time insufficient for regrowth), washed and exposed to singlet oxygen. This post-incubation in milk had no effect on the susceptibility of serum-adapted cells to singlet oxygen (Fig. 5c) indicating that the singlet oxygen resistance phenotype observed in milk was provided by *S. aureus* adaptation.

To further examine the effects of milk and serum adaptation on *S. aureus* sensitivity to ROS, we also compared survival of milk- and serum- adapted JE2 to H₂O₂. However, no killing was observed in any cells when they were exposed to 1.5% H₂O₂ in PBS. Given that *S. aureus* produces detoxifying enzyme catalase that metabolizes H₂O₂ into O₂ and H₂O⁵⁶, we tested the JE2 *katA* transposon mutant (*katA::Tn*), a catalase-deficient strain, for its susceptibility to H₂O₂. The *katA* mutant showed increased tolerance to hydrogen peroxide when adapted to milk compared to serum (Fig. 5e). Together, these results show that milk-adapted *S. aureus* have marked survival advantage against oxidative stress compared to serum-adapted cells. Greater staphyloxanthin production in milk than in serum is a major factor in survival, but other factors that are differentially expressed in milk, that remain to be identified, contributed to oxidative stress tolerance.

The striking effects of milk on ROS tolerance led us examine antimicrobial resistance in milk-adapted compared to serum-adapted *S. aureus*. Here, we treated bacteria with ciprofloxacin, vancomycin, and nisin, each of which differs in its mode of action. Ciprofloxacin inhibits DNA replication by blocking gyrase and topoisomerase, and induces oxidative stress⁵⁷. Scavengers of ROS, such as ascorbic acid, partially counteract ciprofloxacin antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (Supplementary Fig. 11). In contrast, nisin, a bacteriocin primarily used as a food preservative, docks to

peptidoglycan precursor lipid II to permeabilize the membrane and inhibit cell wall synthesis⁵⁸. Finally, vancomycin, used against MRSA infections, targets the D-Ala-D-Ala moiety of peptidoglycan precursors thereby inhibiting peptidoglycan crosslinking. The cell wall thickening in *S. aureus* has been associated with vancomycin treatment failure due to the restricted access of vancomycin to the D-Ala-D-Ala sites⁵⁹. In contrast to ciprofloxacin, nisin and vancomycin are not known to generate ROS, and ascorbic acid had no effect on their antimicrobial activity (Supplementary Fig. 11).

Strikingly, milk-adapted wild-type JE2 cells showed an overall greater tolerance to all three antimicrobials tested compared to serum-adapted and BHI-grown JE2 (Fig. 5f). Moreover, the non-pigmented *crtM* milk-adapted culture was also more tolerant than serum-adapted or BHI-grown strain, but these differences were less pronounced. These findings show that compared to serum-adapted *S. aureus*, milk-adapted bacteria are better adapted to tolerate various antimicrobials, including ciprofloxacin, which induces ROS production. The increased tolerance to nisin and vancomycin of milk-adapted JE2 cells might be related to their rigid and thick envelope. Indeed, the MIC for vancomycin of 32 mg/L for the milk-adapted JE2 cells strongly suggests a reduced accessibility of D-Ala-D-Ala moieties.

The data in this section illustrate the importance of the environment on determining stress and antimicrobial resistance of bacteria. Greater fitness of bacteria grown in milk as compared to those in serum may suggest that food-grown bacteria are 'armed' for infection. They might also suggest that udder mastitis infections in livestock, which are exposed to milk, may require widely different approaches for treatment.

Figure 6. Adaptation of *S. aureus* to milk or serum contributes to the virulence *in vivo*. *Galleria mellonella* survival curves were obtained for larvae infected with milk-adapted, serum-adapted or BHI-grown *S. aureus* JE2 bacterial cells (10^6 CFU). Experimental control groups received PBS. Surviving larva were counted after 24h, 48h and 72h (n=20 larvae/group; 3 independent experiments); insect survival in PBS treated showed no mortality. Data were analyzed using Kaplan-Meier with pooled values of biologically independent triplicates (60 samples per condition). The log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test was used to compare survival curves. Difference between the milk-adapted groups and the control BHI-grown groups ****p<0.0001, between the serum-adapted and BHI-grown, ns: not significant, and between serum-adapted and milk adapted *p<0.125.

Milk-adapted *S. aureus* has increased virulence in an insect larvae model.

We used a *Galleria mellonella* infection model to assess the effects of *S. aureus* pre-adaptation in serum *versus* milk on insect mortality (Fig. 6). The *G. mellonella* innate immune system is similar to that of vertebrates, although it lacks an adaptive immune response⁶⁰. Upon infection, *G. mellonella* produces antimicrobial peptides and ROS that accumulate in the larval haemocoel, the fluid analogous to blood/lymph^{61,62}. This makes *G. mellonella* a suitable model often used to study pathogen virulence including *S. aureus*. Larva (60 per cohort) were injected with 10⁶ CFU BHI-grown or serum- or milk-adapted *S. aureus* JE2 directly into the hemocoel, and mortality was recorded daily for 3 days. A control group was mock-infected with physiological saline under the same conditions. Virulence was defined as increased larva mortality due to the infection and presented as larval survival percentage (Fig. 6).

Strikingly, 24-hour post infection the milk-adapted JE2 conferred faster and higher virulence, displaying a significant increase in mortality compared to serum-adapted or JE2 from BHI, respectively. These differences diminished after 48h, suggesting that adaptation confers a transient advantage during infection. We conclude that adaptation to natural environments can shape *S. aureus* virulence properties *in vivo*.

Discussion

The analysis of the adaptation of *S. aureus* to nutrient rich host-related media, such as serum and milk, provides new insights into the relationship between a host environment and bacterial fitness, antibiotic susceptibility, resistance to ROS, and virulence. Our data demonstrate that *S. aureus* JE2 incorporates FA from milk and serum into plasma membrane which causes structural and functional modifications of the envelop. Additionally, using the comparative proteomic analysis, we have identified a set of proteins selectively expressed or regulated in each natural environment that include virulence factors and stress regulators.

S. aureus, has high membrane flexibility mainly determined by the saturated anteiso-branched-chain fatty acid, *ai.15*, that provides the core permeability function of the plasma membrane, regulates membrane fluidity and the anchoring of staphyloxanthin^{15,31,63}. The membrane fluidity has a pivotal role under changing environmental conditions in order to support membrane functions. We showed that serum-adapted cells exhibited lower *ai.15* levels, instead contained exogenous unsaturated FAs, were non-pigmented, and displayed increased membrane fluidity compared to cells cultured in BHI. Unsaturated and branched-chain fatty acids increase the fluidity through the regulation of phospholipid spacing and lipid phase behavior³⁷. The absence of carotenoids also increased membrane fluidity because in *S. aureus* staphyloxanthin participates in ordering the alkyl chains of cell membrane⁶⁴. Milk-adapted cells were highly pigmented, showed membrane rigidity and important increase of the envelop thickness. Interestingly, the milk-adapted cells also had less *ai.15* compared to the BHI condition, but were highly pigmented. This correlates with previous work showing that despite the final step in the staphyloxanthin synthesis involving the esterification of glucose with the carboxyl moiety of *ai.15*, the fatty acids present in membrane phospholipids do not directly correlate with carotenoid amount⁶⁵. The increased production of pigment in milk-adapted cells suggests that either the low amount of *ai.15* observed in plasma membrane enables efficient production of

staphyloxanthin or other FA can be involved in pigment production. For instance, the pigmentation in *S. aureus* was found to be correlated with the metabolism of acetate, the shortest FA^{13,65}. An in-depth investigation should confirm a link between increased pigment production and an acetate metabolism specific of the milk culture condition.

Our results highlight that milk and serum impose specific fitness challenges for *S. aureus*. Indeed, *S. aureus* in milk or serum is exposed to a diversity of stressful conditions such as osmotic stress, pH variation, nutrition availability, and antimicrobials that the bacterium has to withstand to survive and replicate⁶⁶. Besides, the envelope fitness observed is expected to alter the transport of biological substance including nutrients and metabolites in and out of cells. Prior studies indicated that fatty acids of at least eight carbon atoms possess antibacterial activity which appears more pronounced with increased chain length and degrees of unsaturation^{21,67,68}. The toxicity of one of the most abundant polyunsaturated FA in humans, arachidonic acid (C20:4), was shown to be directly modulated by the cellular ROS level since only the oxidized molecule inflicts damage on *S. aureus*⁶⁸. Among the broad-spectrum antibacterial activity of oleic acid (C18:2) or linoleic acid (C18:3) the most important are disruption of the electron transfer chain process by altering membrane integrity, binding electron carriers, or interfering with oxidative phosphorylation⁶⁷. These processes involve the ionizable headgroup of FA, and thus are highly dependent on the pH. In this regard, the toxicity of C18:2 towards *Listeria monocytogenes* was pronounced at pH 5 but not at pH 6⁶⁹. The pH of milk (6.6) and serum (7.4) could, thus, attenuate the fatty acid toxicity towards *S. aureus* and facilitate the bacterial adaptation. Besides, both serum and milk contain saturated FAs derived from sphingomyelins that were recently shown to protect *S. aureus* the toxicity of polyunsaturated fatty acids⁷⁰. In *S. aureus*, inhibitory concentrations of linoleic acid (C18:3) were shown to interfere with metabolic pathways and nutrient uptake and may cause protein leakage while oleic acid may trigger membrane depolarization and the release of low-molecular weight proteins^{19,26}. Growth phenotypes in unsaturated FA-rich serum and milk with incorporated C18:2 and C18:3 showed increased cellular hydrophobicity and decreased

surface charge, probably to shield cells against hydrophobic FAs⁷¹, or other hydrophobic metabolites.

Although the primary role of *S. aureus* carotenoids is in oxygen free-radical scavenging^{23,24}, we showed that not only staphyloxanthin participated in protecting milk-adapted *S. aureus* against ROS. Indeed, the non-pigmented *S. aureus* cells exhibited greater resistance to oxidative stress when adapted to milk compared to when adapted to serum. We found that the serum-adapted cells exhibited upregulation of numerous oxidative stress-response proteins compared to the milk-adapted cells, including catalase, peroxidase, the response repressor PerP, organic hydroperoxide resistance protein, and superoxide dismutase (Supplementary data 2). Despite this, they were more sensitive to ROS, suggesting that serum-adapted cells undergo enzymatic adaptation to compensate for a less protective envelope. To this regard, milk-adapted *S. aureus* cells had thick and rigid envelopes suggesting that envelope structure may protect bacteria against ROS, antibiotics and adverse environment since it is a robust physical and chemical barrier. We tested three antibiotics, ciprofloxacin, vancomycin and nisin, having different modes of action, and all had reduced effectiveness in milk-adapted *S. aureus* but were very efficient against serum-adapted cells. Besides having a protective role against ROS which decreased ciprofloxacin antibacterial activity, the thick envelope in milk-adapted *S. aureus* can slow or block the penetration of antibiotics⁶, as observed in the permeability test with EthBr. Especially, the large-molecule antibiotic vancomycin might have reduced penetration in milk-adapted bacterial cells. Nisin exerts its antimicrobial activity through electrostatic interactions between its positive charge and the negatively charged bacterial surface to exert its antimicrobial activity⁶. Our results revealed that the milk-adapted *S. aureus* exhibited a lower negative surface charge compared to the serum-adapted cells and those grown in BHI. This reduced surface charge weakens the electrostatic interaction with nisin, hindering its effective binding and thereby diminishing its antimicrobial activity.

Our multiply comparative proteomic analysis revealed different subsets of proteins produced in milk and serum suggesting specific regulatory mechanisms in each of these natural medium. In milk-adapted cells, most unique proteins were host-adaptation factors, including the Type VII Secretion System, EssA, aureolysin, conserved virulence factor C, TcaA, GraS (Supplementary data 3). This result is supported by the several virulence-associated genes that were essential for *S. aureus* fitness in milk also observed by Marli et al.,¹². In contrast, serum-adapted JE2 had fewer unique virulence factors, such as γ -hemolysin component C, but more unique proteins were involved in metabolism and biosynthesis, like sucrose operon repressor, alanine racemase, ATP synthase subunit A, and lipoate-protein ligase (Supplementary data 2). We observed changes in several pathways associated with metabolism, molecular binding and membrane fitness in both serum- and milk-adapted cells compared to BHI, but also between milk-adapted compared to serum-adapted cells. This result indicates that multiple pathways contribute to adaptation and functional integrity of cells in different natural media.

We further showed that *S. aureus* phenotypical adaptation to natural host environments can generate a highly virulent phenotype as observed in the *Galleria mellonella* infection model. The resistance to ROS and antibiotics *in vitro* does not always correlate with the resistance to host antimicrobials given that host antimicrobials have the broad spectrum of targets and physicochemical properties, and their concentration can be extremely elevated in some instance during infection. However, our results suggest that especially *S. aureus* fitness associated to milk can trigger further bacterial virulence *in vivo*. Indeed, controlling *S. aureus*-related bovine mastitis is difficult due to variable antibiotic effectiveness, which is affected by host- and pathogen-related factors¹². Additionally, dairy and serum environment were shown to further complicates treatment and modulate bacterial antibiotic susceptibility^{27,72}. The clinical significance of increased pathogenicity of adapted JE2 cells in *G. mellonella* model remains to be analyzed.

This study demonstrated that *S. aureus* surviving in raw milk and adult serum employs multiple adaptation strategies that influence its virulence, resistance to reactive oxygen species (ROS), and certain antibiotics. Our findings demonstrate that host/diet environments induce specific phenotypic traits, such as alterations in the fatty acid profile of membrane phospholipids and adjustments in membrane fluidity, changes in cell envelope structure and function, modifications in expressions of virulence factors and stress responses. These observed phenotypes may facilitate *S. aureus* evasion of the host's defenses and their existence should be taken into account when designing new antimicrobial agents, meaning that efficacy test should be performed in host environment like milk or serum.

Methods

Bacterial strains, media and growth conditions. The *S. aureus* strains used in this study are listed in Table 1. The brain heart infusion (BHI) is the base medium of *S. aureus* cultures unless specified. The $\Delta fabD$ mutant was grown in BHI supplemented with the appropriate fatty-acid mixture (C14:0, myristic acid; C16:0, palmitic acid; and C18:1 *cis*, oleic acid) and adult bovine serum at 10 % final concentration (CliniSense, France), referred to as SFA medium. The fatty acids purchased from Larodan Fine Chemicals (Sweden), were solubilized separately in DMSO at 100 mM, mixed in a ratio 1:1:1 and then diluted 1:200 for use in liquid or solid medium. The final concentration of each fatty acid in SFA was 0.17 mM. Commercial raw milk (Lactel, France) and adult bovine serum was obtained from cattle older than 12 months (CliniSense, France) were also used for bacteria culturing. Solid plates were prepared by adding 20% v/v of milk or serum to 1.5 % w/v non-nutrient agar (Invitrogen, France) water solution. *S. aureus* culturing in liquid media was done at aerobic conditions (4 mL in 30 mL universal glass tubes) with shaking (180 rpm) at 37°C for 17 h to reach stationary phase. To monitor growth kinetics *S. aureus* overnight cultures were diluted to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.025 and grown in different media at 37°C with shaking. The growth was monitored by measuring OD₆₀₀ every 30 min or by plating on the BHI agar. The figures that report growth curves are were performed on at least three independent samples.

Construction of double crossover *fabD* mutant *S. aureus* USA300 Wild-type fragment *plsX* and *fabG* (primers for *plsX* fragment: pMad-*plsX*_F and *plsX*-*fabG*_R; primers for *fabG* fragment: *plsX*-*fabG*_F and *fabG*-pMad_R for) were amplified by PCR from the genomic DNA of USA300-JE2 strain. The pMad vector⁷³ was digested with the *Sma*I restriction enzyme (NEB R0141). Oligonucleotide sequences are provided in Supplementary Table 1. The three fragments were assembled according to the one-step isothermal DNA assembly by the Gibson protocol (NEB – Gibson Assembly Cloning Kit). The mixture was incubated at 50°C for 30 min in a thermocycler. Two microliters of Gibson master mix were used to transform 100 μ L chemo-competent *E. coli* DH5 α

cells and plated on LB agar with 100 µg/mL ampicillin. PCR on colonies was performed with pMad oligonucleotides. Bacterial plasmid DNA extraction was performed by using QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit (Qiagen). The pMad-plsX-ΔfabD-fabG isolated plasmid from *E. coli* was introduced by electroporation into *S. aureus* RN4220-R NCTC8325 and transformant were selected at the permissive temperature (30°C) for erythromycin (ERY) resistance. Plasmid DNA extraction was conducted with a preliminary lysis treatment of *S. aureus* cell suspensions with lysostaphin (100 µg/mL) for 1 h at 37°C. Finally, pMad-plsX-ΔfabD-fabG extracted from RN4220-R strain is transformed into electrocompetent *S. aureus* JE2 cells and plated as before. To obtain the chromosomal fabD inactivation a positive transformant was performed. An overnight preculture grown at 30°C in BHI medium with 5 µg/mL erythromycin was diluted 100-fold in the same medium with selection. The cells were grown at 30° for 2h and shifted to the nonpermissive temperature at 42°C for 6h to permit the plasmid integration into the *S. aureus* chromosome by homologous recombination. Considering that *fabD* is an essential gene for *S. aureus* exogenous fatty acids were provided and mutants of interest were selected at 42°C on SFA plates with erythromycin. For the selection of the second recombination event, an overnight culture at 42°C in of single-crossover mutant grown with erythromycin (3 µg/mL) in SFA medium, diluted 1/1000-fold in SFA medium with no selection and cultivated at 30°C for 6 h to excise the plasmid. Cultures were plated at 42°C on SFA for 30 h-48 h. Clones were verified for *fabD* gene inactivation phenotypes by PCR on colony and Western Blot. The same method was used for the two *S. aureus* strains RN4220-R and USA300.

Determination of *S. aureus* fatty acid profiles. Fatty acid profiles were determined as previously described¹⁷. Briefly, for each condition, *S. aureus* aliquots were centrifuged and washed in 0.9% NaCl water solution containing 0.02% Triton X-100, succeeded by two washes in 0.9% NaCl at 4°C. This washing eliminated lipids from the medium that may attach to *S. aureus* cells. Cold cell pellets were treated on ice with 0.5 mL of 1M sodium methoxide. Fatty acid methyl esters were extracted after addition of 200 µL of heptane and methyl-10-undecenoate (Sigma-Aldrich, France) as an internal

standard. Samples were vortexed for 1 min and centrifuged to separate the phases. Fatty acid methylesters were recovered in the heptane phase (top phase)¹⁷. Analyses were performed on a Clarus® 580 Gas Chromatograph (Perkin-Elmer) equipped with a Zebron capillary column 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm (Phenomenex). Data was analyzed by TotalChrom workstation software (Perkin-Elmer).

Mass spectroscopy: sample preparation, proteolytic digestion, desalting and nanoLC-MS/MS analyses. For identification of proteins produced in *S. aureus* JE2, cells were cultivated in different media, and then cells from each medium were collected by centrifugation for 10 min at 7,000 g, resuspended in 200 µL of lysis buffer (8M urea, 25 mM HEPES, pH 8.0, 5% glycerol, 1mM DTT, 0.2% DDM (n-dodecyl-β-D-maltopyranoside), 1:200 v/v protease inhibitor (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Canada) and homogenized (using vortex mixer) for 5 min. The suspension was centrifuged for 10 min at 15,000 g and the soluble protein extract was separated from the insoluble debris. Protein concentrations were measured by the Bradford assay using a protein assay kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) following the manufacturer's protocol. The assay absorbance was measured with a spectrophotometer (Novaspec III, Biochrom) and semi-microvolume disposable polystyrene cuvettes (Bio-Rad) at 595 nm.

Protein extracts (100 µg) were digested using a modified filter-aided sample preparation (FASP) protocol designed for proteomic analysis⁷⁴. The digested samples were desalted on disposable Pierce C-18 tips (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with the addition of C-18 resins from Pierce C-18 Spin Columns (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The desalted samples were dried by vacuum centrifugation (Savant SPD111V SpeedVac Concentrator, Thermo Scientific) and reconstituted with MS grade water with 0.1% formic acid for MS analysis.

NanoLC-MS/MS analyses were performed as previously described with some modifications of liquid chromatographic gradient on an Ultimate3000 nanoRLSC (Thermo Scientific) coupled to an Orbitrap FusionTM (Thermo Scientific)⁷⁵. Two µL of protein digests were injected and separated on a column (15 cm LT x 75 µm i.d. x 365

µm o.d. fused silica capillary, Polymicro Technologies) packed in-house with Luna C18 particles (Luna C18(2), 3 µm, 100 Å, Phenomenex, Torrance, California, USA). The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of water/ACN/0.1% (v/v) FA, working at a flow rate of 0.30 µL/min (0-7 min, 2-2% ACN; 7-107 min, 2-38% ACN; 107-112 min, 38-98% ACN; 112-122 min, 98-98% ACN; 122-130 min, 98-2% ACN; 130-140 min, 2-2% ACN).

Data analysis. MaxQuant (Thermo Scientific, version v1.6.17.0)^{76,77} was used for protein identification and quantification. A maximum of two missed tryptic cleavages were allowed with precursor charge bounded between +2 and +7, a 10ppm precursor mass tolerance, and a 0.5 Da fragment mass tolerance. Moreover, search parameters were set to allow for dynamic modifications, including methionine oxidation, acetylation on the N-terminus, and fixed cysteine carbamidomethylation. The search database consisted of a non-redundant protein sequence FASTA file containing the 3,936 entries from *S. aureus* strain USA300 - Uniprot taxonomy ID 367830 (2024.10.09). Normalized label-free quantification (LFQ) values were obtained by applying the in-built MaxLFQ algorithm⁷⁶.

Bioinformatics of sample LFQ intensities was conducted using R programming language in RStudio. Potential contaminants were removed and proteins that were found in at least 4/5 biological replicates were used for further analysis. To visualize common and unique proteins, a Venn diagram was created using the VennDiagram package in R where unique proteins were defined as proteins that were present in 4/5 samples of a particular group and absent in at least 3/5 samples of all other groups. Additionally, proteins common to all three groups were defined as those present in 4/5 samples of each group. To comparatively visualize the whole proteome, a principal component analysis was conducted. Missing LFQ intensity data was first imputed. The data was then log₂ normalized and scaled. The components were then calculated using the `prcomp()` function from the `stats` package. Principal component 1(PC1) and principal component 2(PC2) were plotted using the `ggplot2` package. The data used to

make the PCA plot was then used to make the heatmap with the heatmap package in R.

Additionally, a GroupWise comparison of the log₂ normalized data was performed of common proteins by conducting a one-way Anova with the aov() function from the stats package. A Tukey's Honest Significance Difference (TukeyHSD) test was then used to adjust the p-values. In addition to the adjusted p-values, the log₂ fold change was also calculated. Both parameters, comparing serum&BHI, Milk&BHI, and Serum&Milk, were plotted to create volcano plots. Overall protein significance was defined as having an adjusted p value of <0.05 and a minimum FC of 1.5.

Autolyze assay. To monitor autolysis kinetics, *S. aureus* overnight cultures were diluted to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.025 and grown in different media at 37°C. Autolysis assays were conducted on cells in stationary phase harvested by centrifugation, washed twice and resuspended in autolysis buffer (PBS, 0.5% Triton X-100, pH 7.4). The cell suspensions were then incubated at 37°C with shaking and optical densities were recorded every hour during 5h.

***S. aureus* membrane fluidity measurement.** Bacterial membrane fluidity was determined by Laurdan generalized polarization (GP)³⁵. An overnight *S. aureus* JE2 and JE2 $\Delta fabD$ cultures in serum, milk and BHI (SFA for $\Delta fabD$) were collected, washed once with PBS and incubated in 10 μ M Laurdan (Sigma-Aldrich, France) in the dark under agitation at 30°C for 10 min. The stained cells were washed four times with Laurdan buffer (137 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl, 10 mM Na₂HPO₄, 1,8 mM KH₂PO₄, 0.2 % glucose, 1 % DMF) and transferred to a dark clear-bottom 96-well plates (Corning, France). All solutions and plastics were pre-warmed to 30°C. Laurdan fluorescence was measured between 400 nm and 540 nm under excitation at 350 nm using a Tecan Spark® at 30°C. Laurdan GP was calculated using the formula: $GP = (I_{440} - I_{500}) / (I_{440} + I_{500})$.

Cell permeability assay. *S. aureus* cells grown in serum, milk and BHI overnight were collected and washed with PBS. Thereafter, the pellet was resuspended in PBS and the

OD_{600nm} was adjusted to 0.5. A 200 µl aliquot of bacterial suspensions were placed into flat bottom, black 96-well plates, followed by addition of ethidium bromide (final concentration of 0.01 µg/mL). The thick peptidoglycan layer of Gram-positive bacteria allows small molecules like EtBr to penetrate, primarily through passive diffusion. Once inside, EtBr intercalates with the DNA resulting in increased fluorescence emission. Fluorescence was measured with an excitation and emission wavelength of 530 nm and 585 nm respectively, every 60 seconds for 60 minutes at 37 °C.

Imaging of vancomycin binding to *S. aureus*. Imaging of vancomycin binding to *S. aureus* was performed to compare the binding interaction of BODIPY™ FL-conjugated vancomycin (Invitrogen, France) to *S. aureus* JE2 cells adapted to milk and serum. JE2 cultivated in BHI were used as a control. Cells in saturation phase were deposited on poly-L-lysine (0.01%, Sigma-Aldrich, France) coated glass slides for 10 min, washed and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS. The cells were then incubated with BODIPY™ FL-vancomycin (3 µg/ml) and Hoechst (5 µg/ml) in PBS for 15 min. Subsequently, glass slides were washed 3 times with PBS. The slides were mounted with Vectashield (Vector Laboratories) and kept at 4°C until observation. Cells were visualized with an Axio-Observer Z1 inverted fluorescence microscope equipped with a Zeiss AxioCam MRm digital camera and Zeiss fluorescence filters, using a Zeiss Apochromat 100x/1.4 oil objective. Images were acquired and processed using the ZEN software package (Zeiss).

Antibiotic resistance. Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) were determined by microdilution test for *S. aureus* strains JE2 and its *crtM* mutant. Stationary phase cells adapted to milk or serum or cultured in BHI, were collected and diluted to 10⁶ CFU/mL in corresponding medium. Two-fold serial dilution of antibiotics were generated in U-bottom 96-well plates. Wells were inoculated with bacterial suspensions and incubated for 16h at 37 °C with 180 rpm shaking. Bacterial viability was assessed by plating dilutions on BHI agar. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of antibiotic that inhibited growth.

Spectral profile of the *S. aureus* pigment. Bacterial cells of the JE2 strain were recovered from the growth on milk, serum and BHI agar plates for 48 h, at 37°C, and subjected to methanol extraction. For this, bacterial cells were washed with milliQ water, pelleted and mixed with 99% methanol. The resuspended cells were held at 55°C in water bath for 5 min and cooled for 10 min. The extracts were collected by centrifugation at 6,000 rpm for 15 min. The absorbance profile of the extracted carotenoids was measured with the Cary 3500 Multicell UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent, USA).

Electron microscopy. For ultrastructural visualization of bacterial cells by the transmission electron microscopy (TEM), *S. aureus* JE2 were grown to saturation phase in BHI, or adapted in serum or milk. Cells of each culture was pelleted by centrifugation (8000 rpm, 5 min) and fixed with 2% glutaraldehyde and contrasted with 0.5% oolong tea extract in sodium cacodylate buffer as previously described⁷⁸. Samples were embedded in Epon (Delta Microscopy, Labège, France) and thin sections (70-nm) were collected onto 200-mesh copper grids and counterstained with lead citrate. Grids were observed using a Hitachi HT7700 electron microscope operated at 80 kV (Elexience, France) equipped with a charge-coupled device camera (Advanced Microscopy Techniques Corp., Japan). The thickness of cells envelop was measured on TEM micrographs of at least ten cells, taking at least six measurements on each cell using the software Image J. Statistical analysis was performed using Prism 7 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA (San Diego, Ca)) with the ANOVA test. A P value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Oxidant susceptibility assays. Tests for *S. aureus* susceptibility to oxidants were performed in PBS as described previously²³. Hydrogen peroxide was added at 1.5 % final concentration to 2×10^9 CFU. Controls were performed by replacing H₂O₂ by water. Samples were incubated at room temperature for 1 h, and then 1,000 U/ml of catalase (Sigma-Aldrich, France) was added to quench residual H₂O₂. Dilutions were plated on BHIA for enumeration of surviving cells. For the singlet oxygen assay, 10^8 S.

aureus cells were incubated at room temperature in individual wells of a 24-well culture plate in the presence of 6 µg/ml methylene blue. The plate was situated 5 cm from a 100-W light source. Bacterial viability was assessed after 3 hours by plating dilutions on BHI. Control plates were handled identically but exposed to light in the absence of methylene blue. No evidence of bacterial killing was observed in controls.

***In vivo* virulence assay.** *In vivo* virulence assay was performed in the last instar *G. mellonella* larva model (weighing ~250 mg). Larvae were reared in INRAE facilities (Jouy en Josas) on pollen and bee wax (La Ruche Roannaise Besachier, France). The rearing container was maintained at 27°C in a humidified incubator. A total of 200 last-instar larvae were used for the experiment. They were subjected to starvation for 24 hr at 27°C prior to infection. Based on our previous CFU determinations with JE2 cultured in BHI, 10⁶ CFU *S. aureus* per larva were determined as an optimal inoculum required to kill ~ 75% *G. mellonella* larvae over 72 hr. An overnight *S. aureus* preculture in BHI, serum and milk were subcultured on corresponding solid plates by spreading a 100-µl aliquot for overnight growth. Each culture was collected from the plates, washed 3 times in PBS, and then resuspended in PBS to obtain 10⁸ CFU/ml. Larvae were infected by intrahemocoelic injections with 10 µl of bacterial suspensions using a 1 mL syringe and 0.45x13 mm Argani needle (Teruma, France) placed on an injector pump KDS100 (KD Scientific, ThermoFisher, Illkirch, France). Inocula were counted after plating onto BHI agar medium. Control larvae were injected with saline alone. Larvae were incubated in small petri dishes (10 per dish) without food at 37 °C. Mortality was scored at 24, 48- and 72-hour post-injection. At least 20 larvae were infected per condition.

Statistics. The significance of experimental differences in oxidant sensitivity, envelope thickness, cell size and membrane fluidity were evaluated by ANOVA test. Results of the insect *in vivo* challenge studies were evaluated by nonparametric t-test (Mann-Whitney U). The data were analyzed using Prism v8 software (GraphPad).

Table 1. Bacterial strains.

Strain	Description	Reference or Source
JE2	FPR3757 USA300-JE2 (referred to as JE2)	⁷⁹
$\Delta fabD$	US300 with the <i>fabD</i> gene deleted	This study
RN4220	<i>S. aureus</i> cloning recipient ATCC 8325-4 derivative restriction negative	⁸⁰
JE2 <i>katA</i> mutant	USA300 derivative lacking the katalase A	BEI Resources, ⁷⁹
JE2 <i>crtM</i> mutant (<i>crtM</i> ::Tn, SAUSA300_2499)	USA3000 derivative lacking the fatty acid kinase A	BEI Resources, ⁷⁹
<i>E. coli</i> DH5 α	Used for $\Delta fabD$ construction	⁸¹

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Supplementary information

Serum and milk environments influence the virulence, antibiotic susceptibility, and resistance to reactive oxygen species in *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Supporting Information description: additional experimental details

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Table 1 - Primers used for $\Delta fabD$ mutant construction

Supplementary Fig. 1 *S. aureus* $\Delta fabD$ mutant cannot replicate without exogenous fatty acids. FabD (manoyl CoA-acyl carrier protein transacylase) intervenes in fatty acid synthesis pathway II (FASII) initiation and strains lacking the *fabD* gene are fatty acid auxotrophs^{1,2}. The *S. aureus* $\Delta fabD$ mutant is fatty acid dependent and could not multiply in BHI. In contrast, it could multiply in FA-supplemented BHI, such as FA medium ie., BHI with myristic acid (C14:0), palmitic acid (C16:0) and oleic acid (C18:1), 0.17mM each. The bacterial grow in the FA medium is slow due to the toxicity of the FA cocktail (all FA has more than 8 carbons). The grow is completely restored when 10% serum was added to the FA medium to neutralize the toxicity of FA.

Supplementary Fig. 2. *S. aureus* $\Delta fabD$ mutant can replicate in 100% adult bovine serum and 100% row cow milk. Growth of $\Delta fabD$ mutant in serum and milk is compared to its growth in SFA medium. Data presents mean \pm SD of three biological replicates.

Supplementary Fig. 3 Relative abundance of fatty acid in wild type and $\Delta fabD$ *S. aureus* JE2 strain cultivated in different media. The percentage of unsaturated and saturated fatty acids present in *S. aureus* wild type and $\Delta fabD$ JE2 were calculated from their FA profiles (Fig. 1).

Supplementary Fig. 4. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) images of cross-section of *S. aureus* JE2 grown in BHI or adapted to milk and serum media. The top row shows the bacterial cells at scalebar, 500 nm. The bottom shows cells at scale bar, 2 μm.

Supplementary Fig. 5. BODIPY™ FL- vancomycin staining of *S. aureus* cell wall to quantify fluorescence intensity in different media. The bacterial cultures were grown in BHI (control cells) or adapted to serum, and milk. Bacterial cells in stationary phase were labeled with BODIPY™ FL- vancomycin and fluorescence was detected using a fluorescence microscope. Green signals indicating the labeling of the bacterial cell wall by BODIPY™ FL dye. Differences in fluorescence intensity across the media suggest variations in the cell wall structure/composition of *S. aureus*.

Supplementary .. A principal component analysis (PCA) of serum- (group S) and milk-adapted *S. aureus* (group L) and bacterial cells growth in BHI to saturation phase (group B). Five samples were analyzed in each group. Biological replicates show clear separation between groups.

Supplementary Fig. 7. Global changes of *S. aureus* proteins when cultured in BHI or adapted to milk or serum. Clustering of protein abundance across experimental conditions. Each column presents predominance of the identified proteins and their distribution in each sample.

Supplementary Fig. 8. Relative abundance of FASII pathway proteins varies among serum- and milk-adapted and BHI-grown *S. aureus*. Relative increase (orange) and decrease (grey) were represented as circles sized to correspond to the relative expression abundance of each protein. Five samples were analyzed in each group.

Supplementary Fig. 9. Volcano plots of quantified proteins in serum- and milk adapted *S. aureus* JE2. Protein quantities between the two conditions were compared. Red dots indicate proteins that were upregulated in JE2 adapted to serum; blue dots indicate proteins that were downregulated in serum-adapted JE2; grey dots show proteins that did not change significantly between two groups. The analysis threshold was p-value < 0.05 and the fold change (FC) > 1.5 or < 0.67; anything below these thresholds was considered not significant.

Supplementary Fig. 10. Singlet oxygen stress on serum- and milk-adapted *S. aureus* RN4220. After exposure to singlet oxygen, samples were serially diluted, spotted and grown overnight to estimate survival. The experiments were repeated at least three times and the results shown are representative. Note that the single oxygen eradicated serum-adapted RN4220 expressing no staphyloxanthin, but only partially killed its milk-adapted cells.

Supplementary Fig. 11. Sensitivity of *S. aureus* against ciprofloxacin and nisin in the presence of ascorbic acid. Overnight BHI culture of RN4220 were washed in BHI and plated on BHI solid medium. Plates were spotted with 1.25 ng nisin (N), 400 ng ciprofloxacin (C), 1.25 ng nisin+10 mM ascorbic acid (NC), 400 ng ciprofloxacin + 10 mM ascorbic acid (CC), respectively.

Table 1 Primers used for $\Delta fabD$ mutant construction

Primer Name	Primer sequence (5' – 3')
pMad_F	CGAATTCTAGAAGCTTCTGC
pMad_R	CTGTCTAGTTAATGTGTAACG
PlsX_F	CTGAACACTTATTACAGTATGC
FabG_R	AACTGCATTTACAGTGATACC
pMad-plsX	cgatgcatgccatggtacccATTAGAGGTATTGATAATCCG
plsX_FabG_R	CCTGTTACTAAAGCACTCTTAGTCATTTTACTCATTGATTACCTACAG
plsX-FabG_F	CTGTAGGTGAATCAAATGAGTAAAATGACTAAGAGTGCTTTAGTAACAG G
fabG_pMadR	gcttctagaattcgagctcccGCCGCAGATTTAGTTAAACC

1 Gloux, K. *et al.* Clinical relevance of type II fatty acid synthesis bypass in *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy* **61**, e02515-02516 (2017).

2 Morvan, C. *et al.* Environmental fatty acids enable emergence of infectious *Staphylococcus aureus* resistant to FASII-targeted antimicrobials. *Nature communications* **7**, 1-11 (2016).

PART III:

Manuscript III

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The development of new detection technologies specific, rapid, and sensitive is essential to address the challenges posed by bacterial infections. With the growing emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains, such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), it is crucial to design efficient diagnostic tools that enable early and accurate detection.

In this context, aptamers, short oligonucleotides capable of specifically binding to target biomolecules, emerge as promising candidates. Their high affinity, specificity, and stability make them attractive alternatives to antibodies for the development of biosensors. However, currently available aptamers focus primarily on their interactions with biological targets, while the study of their internal structures remains largely unexplored. The secondary structures of aptamers, such as G-quadruplexes and hairpins, are well-documented, but I-motifs receive little attention, particularly in the context of pathogen detection.

The table compiling aptamer sequences selected for *S. aureus* in literature presenting a wide diversity of sequences. The majority contain a balanced mix of A, C, G, and T, with a GC% of approximately 55–60%. However, about 20% of the sequences are G-rich, while only two are C-rich (SA17 and SA61). As previously mentioned, C-rich sequences have a high propensity to form i-motif structures. Although many ligands have been identified for i-motifs, none have been definitively recognized as specific ligands for these structures. Therefore, studying C-rich sequences, which are likely to adopt an i-motif conformation, could be a promising approach for identifying a ligand specifically targeting *S. aureus*.

An I-motif is a secondary structure formed by cytosine-rich sequences, stabilized in acidic environments or through specific interactions. This configuration could provide enhanced specificity to the aptamer for its target—a hypothesis that is especially relevant for the detection of *S. aureus*. To date, no I-motif specific to a microorganism has been clearly identified or studied, paving the way for innovative investigations.

Through a literature review, we identified several aptamers targeting various molecules and compiled their characteristics in a table (see Table 2). Among them, the aptamer SA61, a cytosine-rich sequence, particularly caught our attention. Its composition suggests a strong propensity to form an I-motif, making this sequence ideal for further studies.

In this article, we present the identification and biophysical characterization of the aptamer SA61 as an I-motif. We undertook sequence optimization by modifying certain key nucleotides to improve its stability and affinity for *S. aureus*. In parallel, we evaluated the binding parameters of the aptamer, including its dissociation constant (K_d), to determine its efficiency and specificity as a detection tool. This work represents a significant advancement in understanding I-motifs and their application in pathogen diagnostics.

Ultimately, this study highlights the importance of deepening our understanding of atypical aptamer structures and exploring their potential for designing innovative diagnostic tools. The uniqueness of I-motifs, combined with their potential enhanced specificity, could transform current detection approaches, especially in complex contexts such as the rapid screening of *S. aureus* in various biological matrices.

1.1. Introduction

Cytosine-rich sequences (C-rich) have the remarkable ability to fold into a distinctive tetraplex structure known as intercalated-motif (i-motif). This structure is formed through the intercalation of hemiprotonated cytosine-cytosine (C•C⁺) base pairs (Figure 25). The first evidence C•C⁺ base pairs came from X-ray diffraction experiments on polycitidylic acid in 1963 (Langridge and Rich 1963). However, it was not until 1993 that the i-motif structure was characterized as a DNA tetraplex stabilized by C•C⁺ base pairs under acidic pH conditions (Gehring, Leroy, and Gueron 1993). Since its discovery, the biological significance of the i-motif has been a topic of considerable interest. Early studies focused more on its nanotechnological applications than its potential roles in vivo. In the last two decades, increasing evidence has shown the formation of as i-motifs in centromere, telomeres, and oncogene promoters, with more recent observations of their presence in vivo (Phan, Guéron, and Leroy 2000; Garavis et al. 2015; Dvořáková et al. 2018; Zeraati et al. 2018; K. S. Li et al. 2023a).

Figure 1. Schematic i-motif formation

Figure 1. Schematic i-motif formation

In 1993, Gehring, Leroy and Guéron described the hexamer d(TCCCC) self-associates to form a tetrameric i-motif (Gehring, Leroy, and Gueron 1993). The

following studies demonstrated numerous i-motif structures can be formed by the association of four, two or even a single nucleic acid strand. Intramolecular i-motifs are formed by the crucial spatial arrangement of C:C⁺ base pairs within a single nucleic strand, while intermolecular i-motifs involve cytosine tracts from two or four independent strands. In all cases, the cytosine tracts are arranged spatially in a tetramer composed of two parallel-stranded duplexes intercalated in an anti-parallel way (Figure 26). i-Motifs have several unique structural features. The distance between consecutive C•C⁺ base pairs is 3.1 Å, and the helical twist angle is around 12–20°, smaller than those observed in the B-form of DNA (3.4 Å and 36°). The i-motif structure contains two distinct types of grooves: two major grooves and two minor grooves. The major grooves provide accessible spaces, whereas the minor grooves do not offer this accessibility. Specifically, the minor groove formed between antiparallel strands measures only 3,1 Å, limiting potential interactions in this region. (Abou Assi et al. 2018). I-motif structures are usually stable at pH values lower than 7 but also depend of the temperature and the ionic strength. The consecutive stacking of C•C⁺ base pairs has a direct influence on the stability of an i-motif structure, but this effect reaches a maximum limit at 5 stacked pairs (Wright, Huppert, and Waller 2017). The stability of i-motifs is almost nonexistent at neutral and basic pH.

The presence and potential functions of i-motifs in cells continue to be a relevant subject. It has been suggested a potential role *in vivo* as a transcription regulator (Kendrick et al. 2014). The presence of i-motifs in cells is still debated, as their stability is highly dependent on pH and temperature. While the i-motif antibody iMab has been shown to detect i-motif formation in cells (Dzatko et al. 2018), although the iMab specificity has recently been challenged (Boissieras et al. 2024) but remains highly debated (Ruggiero et al. 2025) A more recent cell-NMR study revealed that sequences capable of forming i-motifs are mostly unfolded in living HeLa cells (Víšková et al. 2024).

Figure 2. Three different representative i-motif DNA structures resolved by NMR techniques

Figure 2. Three different representative i-motif DNA structures resolved by NMR techniques. To the left, the i-motif structure of d(CCCCAA), forms a symmetrical tetramer with two intercalated duplexes containing C:C⁺ base pairs (PDB 1YBR). In the middle – An i-motif duplex junctions structure resolved at neutral pH (PDB 7O5E) and to the right, an intramolecular i-motif formed by a C-rich sequence, stabilized by four hemiprotonated C:C⁺ base pairs (PDB 1A83). (X. Han, Leroy, and Guéron 1998; Esmaili 2005; Serrano-Chacón et al. 2021)

1.2. Methods for studying i-motif structures

1.2.1. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

Various methods can be employed to investigate the formation and stability of i-motif structures. One successful and first approach is to study the formation of these structures by using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) measurements. I-motif structures show characteristic imino proton signals around spectra 15-16 ppm, which correspond to the hemiprotonated C:C⁺.base pairs (Leroy and Guéron 1995). These signals are distinct from those of Watson-Crick G-C and A-T base pairs, which typically appear between 12-14 ppm, and non-canonical base pairs, such as T-T or G-T base pairs exhibit a signal between 10-12 ppm (Figure 1H NMR). In general, Watson-Crick and non-canonical base pairs are located in the loop regions. In general, the signal assignment of the other bases in an i-motif sequence enables resolving the observed i-motif structure. With complex sequences, the assignment of the NMR spectra can be more difficult to interpret. To resolve the topology, it necessary in consequence to introduce chemical modifications or site-specific isotopic label such as ¹⁵N isotope (Phan and Patel 2002; Jixun Dai et al. 2009).

Figure 3. NMR-based representation of DNA structures and protons assignments

Figure 3. NMR-based representation of DNA structures and protons assignments.

1.2.2. X-ray diffraction crystallography

Another method to resolve i-motif structure is to use X-ray crystallography which provides high-resolution structural information that complements solution-based techniques like NMR. This method is based on analyzing the diffraction pattern generated by X-rays incident on a sample, which allows the determination of its secondary structure. Single-crystal X-ray analysis can offer detailed insights into the atomic arrangement of i-motif structures, which are often challenging to achieve with NMR alone. The first step is to determine the optimal conditions for the growth of high-quality quality crystals. This initial step can be a limiting factor due to the difficulty of obtaining crystals with sufficient diffraction quality. Once grown, the crystals are harvested and exposed to an X-rays beam which produces a regular pattern of reflections on a photographic plate. The angles and intensities of the diffracted X-rays are measured. All the collected data are combined and processed computationally to propose a model on the atomic disposition within the crystal. From this data, an electron density map is generated, and the final model structure is resolved (Figure 28).

Recently, a team of researchers resolved the first crystal structure of an i-motif formed by a C-rich region in the *HRAS* promoter at a resolution of 1,77 Å (K. S. Li et al. 2023). Resolving the structure of i-motifs can provide valuable insights for find ligands with improved ability to interact with these structures.

Figure 4. Overview of the X-ray crystallography process.

Figure 4. Overview of the X-ray crystallography process. Created with Biorender (adapted from Guneri et al. 2024)

1.2.3. UV spectroscopy

UV spectroscopy is a valuable method for studying i-motif formation and stability. The protonation of cytosines in i-motifs produces hyperchromicity at wavelengths from 275-300 nm, whereas neutral cytosines have a maximum absorbance around 262 nm. Following absorbance evolutions in this range of wavelengths, allows researchers to study the stability of i-motifs depending of the temperature and the pH. Melting experiments, for example, can be used determine the melting temperature (T_m) of i-motif structures during the unfolding process (J.-L. Mergny 2005).

Figure 5. Principle of circular dichroism

Figure 5. Principle of circular dichroism. Created from Briorender (Adapted from E. Cheng, Yang, and Liu 2010)

Another way for detecting the formation of i-motif structures circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy (Figure 29). It is based on the interactions of a sample with two circularly polarized light beams. This method is useful when the sample exhibits a difference in absorption between right- and left-polarized light. The chirality of DNA and its natural absorbance make CD spectroscopy particularly useful for characterizing the secondary structures. This method is both simple and effective for identifying, especially i-motifs. This structure exhibits two constants characteristic CD signals: a positive peak around 285 nm and a negative peak near 265 nm. CD spectroscopy can be used to assess the stability of the i-motif by monitoring changes in temperature and pH conditions, as well as to observe their formation. (Lannes et al. 2015). Nevertheless, this method does not allow for the determination of the exact structure of the i-motif. Really recently, Joseph Boissieras and Anton Granzhan developed a new potentiometric titration method, that utilizes the pH-dependent folding of i-motif structures to study the effects of ligands on their stability (Boissieras and Granzhan 2024).

1.2.4. Fluorescence based techniques

Other molecular fluorescence-based techniques may be used to study the structure but also kinetics of i-motif. Fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) is a sensitive approach to study the stability of i-motif. FRET relies on energy transfer between a donor chromophore and an acceptor chromophore, with efficiency depending on their distance and dynamics. It is based on the quenching of a fluorophore by a quencher, triggered during the folding of DNA (Figure 30). In folded i-motifs, the chromophores are closer together, resulting a stronger FRET signals

compared to unfolded states (Jean-Louis Mergny 1999). This approach is particularly useful for investigating the stability and kinetics of i-motif formation.

Figure 6. Principle of FRET applied to an i-motif

Figure 6. Principle of FRET Applied to an i-Motif (B. Gao and Hou 2021)

The use of labeled DNA is also possible in fluorescence anisotropy experiments. It is a measure of the depolarization of emitted light when a fluorophore is excited with polarized light. This technique provides information on the changing orientation of a molecule in space. The anisotropy obtained reflects the rate of rotational diffusion of the molecule in the medium, which depends on its volume, concentration and structural changes in the fluorescent entity. This method is widely used to study protein-protein associations, protein-ligand interactions, protein-nucleic acid binding, and folding-unfolding of biological molecules. Fluorescence anisotropy is highly sensitive, and requires low sample concentrations, making it ideal for exploring i-motif interactions in various environments (H. Huang et al. 2015). Moreover, the dissociation constant of a complex formed between a labeled aptamer and a non-labeled target can be determined by monitoring fluorescent anisotropy during a titration experiment where the concentration of the non-fluorescent small molecules is gradually increased.

Figure 7. Principle of Fluorescent anisotropy

Figure 7. Principle of Fluorescence Anisotropy (Moerke 2009)

1.2.5. Other methods

A more traditional approach, Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis (PAGE) is commonly used to characterize the nature of folded i-motif structures, between duplexes, dimeric, or tetrameric conformations (Jean-Louis Mergny et al. 1995; Ahmed et al. 2018). However, this method can be challenging to interpret due to the sensibility of the i-motif to pH and temperature which may fluctuate during migration.

Another technique involves identifying the specific cytosines participating in base pairing and intercalation during i-motif formation using bromine (Br_2). Bromine selectively reacts, with double bonds of cytosines, exhibiting a 10-fold higher reactivity. This method has been successfully applied to resolve i-motif topologies (Ruggiero et al. 2019; Dhakal et al. 2010; K. Guo et al. 2007). As with other PAGE-based approaches, the results may vary due to the sensitivity of the method to pH and temperature fluctuations during the migration.

1.3. I-motif & nanotechnologies

Despite the limited studies on the biological role of i-motifs, significant progress has been made in their application in nanotechnologies. Due to their pH-dependent stability, i-motifs represent promising candidates for various biotechnological applications in therapeutics, mainly in drug carriers and deliverers. They can function as rapid and controllable pH-responsive switches, transitioning between the i-motif structure and single-stranded DNA.

For instance, fluorescent FRET pairs can be strategically integrated into i-motif based nanostructures to develop advanced pH-responsive sensors. Building on this concept, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) functionalized with oligonucleotides complementary to i-motif-forming sequences have been employed as intracellular probes. In an acidic cellular environment, the formation of the i-motif is expected to bring the FRET pair proximity, generating a detectable signal. Yue and their team demonstrated an application of this method to visually track lysosomes and monitor pH changes into living cells, utilizing an i-motif structure as pH-responsive unit with FRET (Yue et al. 2021). This strategy has also been adapted in other designs where i-motifs are attached to various scaffolds, such as hairpin-forming sequences or biotin/streptavidin systems.

The range of applications for i-motif-based technologies is expanding significantly, particularly in the field of detection. Li et al. introduced an aptamer-modified with an i-motif structure and investigated its binding affinity to cancer cells in both acidic and neutral microenvironments by modulating the aptamer's specificity. By exploiting the pH sensitivity of the i-motif, they developed a detection assay capable of targeting cell surface antigens within a tumor-like acidic microenvironment. This innovative approach demonstrates the potential of i-motif-modified aptamers as pH-responsive tools for cancer detection and diagnostics (L. Li et al. 2018). In the same field, a research team linked an i-motif DNA to iron oxide nanoclusters for use as a tool in cancer imaging (J. Lu et al. 2018). Additionally, utilizing its pH-switch characteristics, the therapeutic potential of the i-motif has been explored in several studies for

delivering drugs to treat tumorous cells both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. However, i-motifs have not yet been applied in the diagnosis or treatment of pathogens, presenting an intriguing avenue for future research.

1.4. I-motif and ligands interaction

I-motif ligands can include small molecules, metal ion complexes, or peptides, each exhibiting varying degrees of affinity and selectivity depending on their chemical (H.-J. Kang et al. 2014) which an extensive list of potential ligands exists, only a limited number of i-motif ligands have been reported in the literature. One of the main reasons for this limitation is the inherent instability of i-motifs under physiological conditions and the limitation arises from the highly confined interaction space at the core of the structure, where the intercalation of compounds is significantly restricted by the size and nature of the existing grooves. The study of i-motif ligands is of particular interest, as these molecules can significantly influence i-motif stability and serve as valuable probes for further investigations. Additionally, their highly compact structure presents a challenge for ligand accessibility and effective binding.

Ligand	Reference
PBP1	(Debnath et al. 2017)
PBP2	(Debnath et al. 2017)
[Ru(Phen)2dppz]2+	(Pages et al. 2019)
BisA	(Bonnet et al. 2022)
TMpyP4	(Fedoroff et al. 2000)
IMC-48	(H.-J. Kang et al. 2014)
Berberine	(Gargallo et al. 2021)
IMC-76	(H.-J. Kang et al. 2014)

Crystal violet	(Das et al. 2023)
RHPS4	(Abdelhamid, Gates, and Waller 2019)
Miloxantrone	(Wright et al. 2016)
QN-302	(Alexandrou et al. 2024)
BRACO-19	(Abdelhamid, Gates, and Waller 2019)
PDS	(Abdelhamid, Gates, and Waller 2019)

Table 1. List of ligands for i-motif described in the literature

Manuscript 4:

Structural Characterization and refinement of an I-motif Aptamer for specific Detection of *Staphylococcus aureus*

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2.1. Oligonucleotide synthesis

The majority of the sequences used in this study were synthesized in the laboratory using the standard solid-phase synthesis method known as "phosphoramidite chemistry." This method, widely adopted for the production of oligonucleotides, allows for precise and automated synthesis of DNA strands from protected nucleotide monomers.

The synthesis takes place on a solid support, typically a resin or silica derivative, to which the first nucleotide is attached. The elongation of the nucleotide chain proceeds from the 3' to the 5' end, contrary to natural enzymatic polymerization, which occurs in the 5' to 3' direction. Each synthesis cycle enables the controlled addition of one specified nucleotide chosen by the operator (A, G, C or T) to the growing chain and includes four main steps:

1. **Deprotection (detritylation):** The dimethoxytrityl (DMT = 4,4' dimethoxytrityl) protecting group on the 5' hydroxyl of the sugar is removed using a solution of trichloroacetic acid in dichloromethane. The released red-orange colored dimethoxytrityl cation (DMTr⁺) can be quantified spectrophotometrically to assess the efficiency of the coupling cycle.
2. **Activation and Coupling:** Following detritylation, the support-bound nucleoside is ready to react with the next base, which is added in the form of a nucleoside phosphoramidite monomer. A large excess of the appropriate nucleoside phosphoramidite is mixed with an activator, such as tetrazole or its derivatives, both dissolved in acetonitrile—a solvent well-suited for nucleophilic displacement reactions. The diisopropylamino group of the nucleoside phosphoramidite is protonated by the activator, forming a good leaving group. This allows the 5'-hydroxyl group of the support-bound nucleoside to attack the neighboring phosphorus atom of the phosphoramidite, forming a new

phosphorus-oxygen bond and generating a support-bound phosphite triester. This step is crucial for the elongation of the oligonucleotide chain.

3. **Capping:** Since each coupling step is not 100% efficient, a small proportion of 5'-hydroxyl groups may remain unreacted. If not blocked, these could react in the next cycle, producing truncated sequences and deletion mutations. To prevent this, the unreacted 5'-hydroxyl groups are acetylated using two reagents: Cap A (acetic anhydride/pyridine/THF) and Cap B (N-methylimidazole/THF). This renders them unreactive in subsequent steps, thus maintaining synthesis fidelity and simplifying purification.
4. **Oxidation:** The phosphite-triester (P(III)) formed in the coupling step is unstable to acid and must be converted to a stable (P(V)) species prior to the next TCA detritylation step. This is achieved by iodine oxidation in the presence of water and pyridine. The resultant phosphotriester is effectively a DNA backbone protected with a 2-cyanoethyl group, which prevents undesirable side reactions during subsequent cycles.

This cycle is repeated as many times as needed, depending on the desired oligonucleotide length. At the end of the synthesis, a deprotection and cleavage step releases the oligonucleotide from the solid support, followed by purification (e.g., HPLC or electrophoresis) to isolate the full-length products.

Although each synthesis cycle generally follows the same four basic steps, variations in these steps can occur depending on the synthesis scale, the incorporation of modified bases, or the addition of functional groups such as fluorophores. For example, producing large-scale DNA quantities might require optimized reagent concentrations or extended reaction times, while the introduction of specific chemical modifications or dyes may involve additional or alternative steps to ensure compatibility and efficiency.

After deprotection, the crude mixture contains full-length oligonucleotides along with truncated or side-products. To isolate the correctly synthesized sequences, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is used. This technique separates the desired product from incomplete or erroneous sequences based on differences in hydrophobicity or charge.

Following purification, additional filtration steps such as dialysis are performed to remove residual salts and small molecules, yielding a highly pure oligonucleotide stock suitable for downstream applications.

2.2. Introduction

Biosensor technology is one of the fastest-growing scientific areas that enable specific, rapid, and highly sensitive diagnostics across various applications including healthcare, environmental monitoring, and food safety. Especially detection of pathogenic bacteria using biosensor devices has gained significant attention since it offers an efficient and straightforward alternative to conventional culture-based methods.¹⁻³ Commonly, bacterial recognition relies on the coupling of biological sensing elements to the transducers (such as electrochemical or optical systems) that translate binding interactions into a measurable signal. In particular, biosensors that detect whole bacterial cells represent a powerful diagnostic tool as they do not require complicated and costly sample preparation steps prior to analysis. Such biosensors based on specific antibodies, phages, peptides, antibiotics, molecular imprinted polymers, or aptamers as recognition elements significantly shorten analysis times, which represents a tremendous asset for low-cost and rapid diagnostics.⁴⁻⁶

In this context, aptamers, short single-stranded DNA or RNA oligonucleotides capable of binding to specific targets have emerged as promising alternatives due to their low cost, high affinity, and chemical resistance^{7,8}. Unlike antibodies, aptamers can be synthesized with high reproducibility and modified for enhanced performance. Their specificity relies on structural recognition, as aptamers adopt distinct 3D structures, such as stem-loops, hairpins, and G-quadruplexes, which can recognize and bind

bacterial cells of interest⁹. Nevertheless, despite their widespread recognition in literature, aptamers struggle to prove their practical applications.^{8,9} Indeed, aptamers represent attractive alternatives to expensive antibodies for specific bacterial targeting, but most commercial kits and devices still mainly employ antibodies. One of the reasons for the low success rate in creating apta-sensors, is that specific aptamers showing high binding affinity and specificity in a lab condition, modify their 3D structure and loose functionality when applied in real biological samples.

For this reason, aptamers that fold into stable non-canonical four-stranded G-quadruplexes and i-motifs are attractive candidates as biosensing elements. These structures are stabilized by additional hydrogenic bonds, which may enhance their resistance environment variations compared to the double-stranded structure¹⁰. G-quadruplexes form in guanine-rich sequences in the presence of metal ions (e.g., Na⁺, K⁺), whereas i-motifs emerge from cytosine-rich sequences, requiring slightly acidic conditions for stabilization. Such putative sequences are prevalent in numerous GC-rich promoter oncogenes and telomeres.^{11, 12} However, until now, a plethora of apta-sensor based on G-quadruplex have been developed, while i-motif recognition elements are less explored, particularly in the context of pathogen detection. Furthermore, no ligand has been recognized as specific for the i-motif structures in the context of pathogen detection.

Given the recent increase in antibiotic-resistant strains, several aptamers have been developed and validated to bind *Staphylococcus aureus*. Table 3 (in part I), compiling previously published aptamers targeting *S. aureus*, revealing a wide diversity of sequences. The majority contain a balanced mix of A, C, G, and T, while 20% are G-rich, and only two are C-rich (SA17 and SA61). Among these, SA61 is particularly noteworthy due to its high propensity to form an i-motif structure.¹³ This configuration can be relevant for *S. aureus* biosensor development, but its structural analysis has not been performed yet.

This study aims to characterize and optimize SA61 as a potential i-motif aptamer for *S. aureus*. First, a biophysical characterization was performed to confirm that SA61 folds into an i-motif under slightly acid conditions. Second, sequence modifications were introduced not only to enhance stability and binding affinity but also to resolve the presence of multiple conformer observed in SA61, ensuring the selection of a single structure. Finally, the efficiency and specificity of the optimized sequences were evaluated by comparing their apparent dissociation constants (K_d) By focusing on the structural and functional properties of i-motif aptamers, this work explores their potential in designing innovative tools for rapid *S. aureus* detection.

2.3. Results and discussion

2.2.1 SA61 forms a stable I-motif structure

SA61 (Table 1) was shown to bind specifically to *S. aureus*¹³. Its C-rich sequence makes it a candidate for forming an I-motif structure. To test this hypothesis, we performed NMR, CD, and melting experiments as a function of pH (Figure 8, S1). The CD spectrum of SA61 at pH 5 showed a maximum at 285 nm and a minimum at 260 nm, while at pH 7, the spectrum changed markedly, with a reduced intensity at 285 nm (Figure 8A). Melting experiments revealed a decrease in melting temperature with increasing pH (Figure S1), from 43.5°C at pH 5.0 to 33°C at pH 5.5 and 22°C at pH 6.0. The NMR spectrum of SA61 at pH 7 displayed a broad peak around 13 ppm, along with sharp peaks at 15–16 ppm, 13–14 ppm, and 10–12 ppm (Figure 8B). The presence of peaks at 15–16 ppm is characteristic of C•C⁺ base pair formation¹⁴. Collectively, our data show that SA61 forms an I-motif structure.

Figure 8. CD and NMR spectra at pH 5.0 and pH 7.0

Figure 8. (A) CD and (B) NMR spectra at pH 5.0 (red curves) and pH 7.0 (black curves).

2.2.2 Binding of *S. aureus* by the SA61 I-Motif Structure

Next, we wondered whether this structure is indeed responsible for bacterial binding. To investigate this, we set up a fluorescence assay using fluorescein-labeled DNA. The assay involved mixing a known concentration of DNA with increasing quantities of bacteria followed by washing and recording the fluorescence (Figure S2)

First, we estimated the DNA concentration required to observe a change in fluorescence intensity between SA61 and two controls: a DNA sequence known to form an I-motif Imh¹⁵ and T30 (Table 1). A fixed quantity of bacteria was titrated with increasing DNA concentrations. Fluorescence intensity at 518 nm increased only for SA61, while it remained constant for Imh and T30 (Figure 9A; an example of fluorescence spectra is given in Figure S3). The difference became noticeable at 0.1 μ M and was used in subsequent experiments.

Figure 9. DNA concentration and pH dependence of fluorescence intensity at 518 nm at 100 nM

Figure 9. (A) DNA concentration and (B) pH dependence of fluorescence intensity at 518 nm at 100 nM DNA concentration. Black: SA61, Green: T30, Blue: Imh. All measurements were conducted in triplicate.

To determine whether the I-motif structure is responsible for binding *S. aureus*, we performed our assays at different pH levels. No fluorescence was detected above pH 7.0; however, below pH 6.0, the fluorescence signal for SA61 was approximately 30 times stronger than at pH 7.0, while for Imh and T30, the increase was around 6- and 10-fold, respectively (Figure 8B). These results strongly suggest that the I-motif is the structure responsible for binding *S. aureus*.

Name	Sequence (5'-3')
T30	TTT
Imh	CCC TAA CCC TAA CCC TAA CCC T
SA61	CTC CCA ACC GCT CCA CCC TGC CTC CGC CTC
S2	ACC GCT CCA CCC TGC CTC
S4	ACC GCT CCA CCC TGC CTC TGT C
S3	ACC GCT CCA CCC TGC CTC TGT C C
S5	ACC GCT CCA CCC TGC CTC TGT CTC

Table 2. Sequence used in this study

2.2.3 SA61 Forms Multiple Conformations: sequence optimisation

Our data show that SA61 forms a stable I-motif structure, but also adopts multiple conformations, as indicated by the presence of minor peaks in the imino proton region (Figure 8B). These conformations may play a role in its ability to bind *S. aureus*. To identify which cytosines are involved in the I-motif, we introduced C-to-T

mutations and conducted 1D NMR experiments (Figure S4). Our data indicate that mutating the first and last cytosines did not significantly alter the NMR spectra at 15-16 ppm (Figure S4), suggesting that these positions are not crucial for I-motif formation. This insight guided the design of shorter sequences, named S2, S3, S4, and S5. We tested their ability to form I-motifs, and indeed, NMR spectra confirmed their formation (Figure 10). Moreover, their melting temperatures (T_m) were higher than that of SA61 (Figure S6).

We conducted preliminary NMR experiments to determine the structure of the most stable sequence: S2. By using site-specific labeling with 2% ^{15}N -cytosine, we were able to identify the cytosines participating in the $\text{C}\cdot\text{C}^+$ bonds and demonstrate that our I-motif contains five $\text{C}\cdot\text{C}^+$ bonds (Figure S5). Further in-depth studies are required to fully elucidate its structure.

Figure 10. NMR spectra of S2, S3, S4 and S5

Figure 10. NMR spectra of S2, S3 S4 and S5

2.2.4 Fluorescence Anisotropy Analysis Reveals pH-Dependent Binding of Optimized Aptamers to *S. aureus*"

We then examined the binding affinity of these sequences to *S. aureus* using fluorescence anisotropy. Increasing amounts of bacteria were titrated into a fixed concentration of DNA, and fluorescence anisotropy was measured at pH 5.5 and 7.0. At pH 5.5, our data show that S2, S3, S4, and S5 bind more strongly to *S. aureus* than SA61, imH, and T30 (Figure 11), while no significant binding was observed at pH 7 (Figure SX). Collectively, our data indicate that the interaction is pH-dependent, strongly suggesting that it is I-motif dependent. To evaluate specificity, we also tested these sequences against *E. coli*, where they exhibited weaker binding.

2.4. Conclusion

Our study demonstrates that the aptamer previously selected against *S. aureus* adopts an I-motif structure, which is responsible for its binding to the bacteria. Using NMR, CD, and fluorescence spectroscopy, we systematically optimized the sequence by shortening it while preserving its structural integrity. This modification resulted in a more stable I-motif that exhibits stronger binding to *S. aureus* compared to the original sequence, while maintaining a certain level of specificity. These findings provide a basis for developing aptamer-based biosensors targeting *S. aureus* and provide insights for the future design of improved aptamers for the selective detection of *S. aureus*.

Figure 11. *S. aureus* titration with DNA aptamers at 100 nM to test the binding affinity of the aptamers

Figure 11. *S. aureus* titration with DNA aptamers at 100 nM to test the binding affinity of the aptamers.

2.5. Experimental

Bacterial strains, media, and growth conditions

The *S. aureus* strain used in this study is JE2 (FPR3757 USA300). The brain heart infusion (BHI) is the base medium of *S. aureus* cultures unless specified. *S. aureus* culturing in liquid media was done at aerobic conditions (2 mL in 15 mL Falcon Tube) with shaking (180 rpm) at 37°C. The *Escherichia coli* strain used in this study is DH5 α . The Luria-Bretani (LB) is used to cultured *E. coli* in the same conditions than *S. aureus*.

Circular Dichroism (CD) Spectroscopy

CD spectra were recorded on a Jasco-1500 CD spectropolarimeter. The scanning was carried out at the range of 220-320 nm wavelength at 20°C using 1 cm path length quartz cuvettes with a scan rate of 200 nm/min, 2 nm bandwidth, and 2 sec response time at 25°C. For each spectrum, an average of two scans was taken, the spectral contribution from the buffers was subtracted, and the data were zero-corrected at 320 nm. DNA concentration was 5 μ M in potassium phosphate buffer solution at 20 mM supplemented with 100 mM KCl at pH varying from 4,5 to 8,0.

UV melting

UV melting was measured using a UV-vis spectrophotometer. The aptamer samples were prepared in phosphate buffer solution (20 mM) with different KCl and DNA concentrations at 5 to 7 pH range. UV absorbance was monitored at 260, 290, and 320 nm to track changes in DNA stability during the heating and cooling phases. The melting curve was obtained by gradually decreasing the temperature from 80°C to 5°C (forward) and then increasing it from 5°C to 80°C (reverse) at a rate of 0.3°C/min. 10 mm path-length quartz spectrophotometer cuvettes were used for all experiments.

Absorbance data were collected at each temperature increment and melting temperature.

NMR spectroscopy

^1H -NMR and ^{15}N -NMR spectrums were recorded using Bruker 600 and 800 MHz spectrophotometers at 288 K unless otherwise stated. Samples were prepared in phosphate buffer (20 mM) and 100 mM KCl at a 5 to 7 pH range, supplemented with 10% D_2O . The NMR data were processed and analysed with TopSpin 4.1.4 software (Bruker).

Aptamer-bacteria binding test

S. aureus JE2 were cultured overnight and washed three times at 8000 rpm for 5 minutes with a working buffer (20 mM phosphate buffer with 100 mM KCl at varying pH levels. The bacterial suspension was then diluted to a final concentration of 10^6 CFU/mL. For the binding assay, the bacteria were incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes without agitation, with different concentrations of aptamer (ranging from 20 mM to $1\mu\text{M}$) in the same working buffer. Following incubation, the mixture was washed three times at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes to remove unbound aptamers. The fluorescence signal of the bound aptamer was measured using a fluorimeter.

Fluorescence anisotropy

Fluorescence anisotropy measurements were carried out on a spectrofluorometer equipped with a fluorescence polarization module. The samples used in this study consisted of the DNA sequences SA61, S2, ImH and T30, labeled with the fluorochrome FITC. Samples were prepared in phosphate buffer (20 mM) at either pH 7.0 or pH 5.5, with varying potassium chloride (KCl) and DNA concentrations and kept at 20°C during the experiment. Bacterial cultures (*S. aureus*) were titrated at concentrations ranging from 10^1 to 10^9 CFU/mL to

construct the titration curves. A blank sample containing only the phosphate buffer was used as a control. Each data point was measured five times to ensure accuracy and reproducibility. The instrument was configured with appropriate polarizing filters for FITC excitation and emission, specifically at wavelengths of 488 nm for excitation and 518 nm for emission. Anisotropy was calculated automatically by the instrument software.

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Supplementary information

Structural Characterization and Refinement of an I-Motif Aptamer for Specific Detection of *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Figure S5. S2 NMR spectra with ¹⁵N labeling

Figure S6 – S2, S3, S4 and S5 melting curves at. pH 5.5

Figure S7. *E. coli* titration with aptamers at 100 nM to test the binding effect affinity of the aptamers.

pH	pH 5	pH 5.5	pH 6
T _m (°C)	43.5	33	22

Figure S1. SA61 melting curves at. pH 5 (red line), pH 5.5 (blue line) and pH 6 (black line)

Figure S2 – *S. aureus* – aptamer-FITC binding protocol

Figure S3 – Fluorescence spectra of SA61 (black line) & T30 (green line) and Imh (blue line)

Figure S4. SA61 1D NMR spectra C-to-T mutations (A) SA61 sequence, (B) and (C) ¹H NMR spectra with C-T mutations positions.

Figure S5. S2 NMR spectra with ¹⁵N labeling

DNA	5 μ M heating	5 μ M cooling
S2	47	47
S3	29	32.7
S4	41.6	45
S5	38.7	35.6

Figure S6 – S2, S3, S4 and S5 melting curves at. pH 5.5

Figure S7. (A) *S. aureus* titration with DNA aptamers at 50 nM and pH 7 and (B) *E. coli* titration with DNA aptamers at 50 nM pH 5.5 to test the binding effect affinity of the aptamers.

Conclusions and perspectives

S. aureus is a particularly complex and adaptable pathogen, posing significant challenges in both medical and food-related contexts. This bacterium can survive and adapt to various environments, such as serum (an infection medium), milk (a common food contamination medium). In addition to its adaptability, *S. aureus* is a major contributor to the global issue of antibiotic resistance, with many strains becoming resistant to multiple drugs, including methicillin (MRSA). This resistance significantly reduces the effectiveness of current treatments, making timely and accurate diagnosis essential for better patient management. Developing new, rapid, and reliable detection methods offers a promising solution to address these challenges.

In this thesis, I studied the fitness of *S. aureus* in these different environments, revealing significant adaptations in its fatty acid composition, impacting membrane fluidity, permeability, surface charge, hydrophobicity, oxidative stress response, resistance to antibiotics and virulence. In serum, *S. aureus* shows increased membrane fluidity, absence of pigmentation, and upregulation of oxidative stress response proteins. In contrast, in milk, *S. aureus* becomes highly pigmented, with a more rigid and thickened cell envelope with better protection against oxidative stress and antibiotics. Additionally, proteomic analyses highlighted major differences in protein expression across these environments, demonstrating the influence of environmental conditions on the bacterial phenotype. Adaptation to milk appears to enhance bacterial virulence, as indicated by the *Galleria mellonella* infection model. This observation suggests that environmental conditions directly influence the pathogenic potential of *S. aureus*, which may explain challenges in treating infections in dairy environments.

These findings are also particularly relevant for understanding the absence of aptamer-based biosensors on the market for pathogen detection, specifically for this bacterium, despite a lot of methods developed in laboratory. Aptamers are typically selected for specific targets under defined environmental conditions. My work suggests that the adaptability of *S. aureus* may lead to target modifications, making them inaccessible or altering their recognition by aptamers.

In parallel, I studied and optimized an aptamer, SA61, selected against the whole bacteria *S. aureus*. This aptamer is unique in its rare ability to form an i-motif structure, a property uncommon among aptamers. To date, few ligands are known to bind i-motifs, and no specific targets in *S. aureus* have been identified as using i-motif structures. I confirmed first that the SA61 aptamer forms an i-motif by using biophysical methods such as NMR, melting and CD. I developed also a rapid fluorescent assay to evaluate SA61 binding to *S. aureus*. However, this method does not provide indication of the aptamer's affinity constant for its target and suffers from significant variability in the results. Additionally, other issues, such as potential quenching effects, are also possible. The SA61 sequence was modified to obtain a single conformer (S2), as confirmed by NMR analysis. However, resolving the structure of this aptamer is not yet complete. It appears that S2 forms probably an i-motif dimer, complicating its resolution. Crystallographic studies would be necessary to fully elucidate this structure. Moreover, melting experiments on S2 revealed lower stability at high DNA concentrations compared to low DNA concentrations, which contradicts typical findings. Generally, higher DNA concentrations promote dimers stability. This question regarding i-motif dimers remains highly open, requiring further investigation. An interesting candidate has emerged: S3. Similar NMR experiments will also be required for other aptamers, such as S3, S4 and S5 to further investigate their structure. Furthermore, our melting experiments showed no significant difference, reinforcing its potential as a promising structure. However, significant non-specific signals were observed, highlighting the need for further optimization. and the fluorescent anisotropy result did not show a significant difference on the affinity constant between our aptamers and non-specific aptamers for *S. aureus*.

Overall, these results highlight the complexity of developing an aptamer-based biosensor for *S. aureus* detection. The bacterium's ability to adapt to diverse environments presents a major challenge, making aptamers designed for specific conditions less effective. This work opens new avenues for research in this field. Identifying redundant targets across different environments and selecting aptamers

against these targets would be critical. This would require comprehensive proteomic studies of *S. aureus* in various conditions to identify potential targets, followed by SELEX procedures adapted to these findings. Furthermore, post-SELEX improvements, such as chemical modifications to enhance the stability and specificity of the selected aptamers, will be crucial for their use in detection devices. While the initial development costs may be high, once a stable and universal aptamer is identified, its widespread use would become economically viable.

Additionally, before aptamers can be effectively used for the development of detection tools or other applications, a more thorough characterization is essential. Structural properties, stability under different physiological conditions, and binding mechanisms must be fully understood to ensure their reliability and specificity. Over the past 4 to 5 years, there has been a growing interest in the structural characterization of aptamers in the scientific field. Previously, aptamers were often directly applied to the development of new biosensors, sometimes without even determining their dissociation constant (K_d). This shift highlights the importance of a deeper structural understanding to improve aptamer performance and reliability in real-world applications. In the case of SA61, the presence of an i-motif structure adds complexity, requiring advanced structural studies such as crystallography to fully resolve its conformation. Moreover, the authors who selected SA61 never mentioned this aptamer as an i-motif. This aspect should become a key consideration, as it is well established that target recognition is driven by the 3D conformation of the aptamer, highlighting the importance of its structural properties. Furthermore, factors such as pH sensitivity, thermal stability, and potential non-specific interactions should be carefully assessed to optimize aptamer performance. A comprehensive characterization would not only improve their efficiency in biosensing applications but also enhance their potential for therapeutic and diagnostic uses.

Aptamers are promising molecular recognition tools that have gained increasing interest over the past 30 years. However, a deeper understanding and more extensive studies are necessary to enable their large-scale application for pathogen detection.

Despite the limited number of known i-motif aptamers and the relatively low biological interest they have generated, these structures remain valuable in the fields of nanotechnology and biosensing. Optimizing the detection of *S. aureus* using our i-motif aptamers SA61, S2, and S3 would be a significant achievement. Identifying their exact target would be particularly interesting because it would help clarify the molecular mechanisms behind the interaction, potentially improving the specificity and sensitivity of detection. Moreover, understanding the target could reveal whether the aptamer binds to a highly conserved and essential bacterial component, which would increase its reliability across different *S. aureus* strains. This information could also contribute to the development of improved aptamer-based diagnostic tools or therapeutic strategies.

The ability of *S. aureus* to adapt to different environments may cause structural changes in its surface components, which could interfere with aptamer recognition. To overcome this challenge, it is essential to identify conserved and redundant targets across different environments, ensuring robust recognition. Conducting an in-depth proteomic study of *S. aureus* in diverse conditions could help identify the most relevant targets before optimizing SELEX accordingly.

Valorization of the thesis

Secondment and seminars (137h)

- Journées des Doctorants ABIES 2022 – 21-22 April 2022 – **16h**
- H2020 IPANEMA secondment at Biosense Institute and Ekofungi, Serbia (July–August 2022), working on the project "**Low-Cost Gold Leaf Electrode as a Platform for *Escherichia coli* Immunodetection.**"
- Surfaces and New Original Strategies for CELL Studies (SNOSCELLS) - 22-27 January, 2023 - Ecole de Physique des Houches (Les Houches, FRANCE) – **35h**
- Workshop Singapore - Paris Chemistry & Chemical Biology 2023 – Paris - 14-16 June, 2023 – **20h**
- 7th International ISEKI-FOOD conference 05-27 July, 2023. – **Poster presentation** - ISEKI-food association – AgroParisTech – **25h**
- STAPH-2024, a 2-day virtual program *- 3rd International Virtual Conference on Staphylococcal Infections - 21-22 February, 2024. – **16h**
- MIKROMED REGIO 5 • FROM BIOTECHNOLOGY TO HUMAN AND PLANETARY HEALTH – 04-06 April, 2024 – Belgrade – **25h**

Courses (102,5h)

- MOOC Ethique de la recherche et intégrité scientifique [Fr/Eng] (15 March, 2022) MOOC online. – **5h**
- Presentation skills in English - Getting your message across – 02-16 September 2022 – **24h**
- Doctoral Training in basic Statistics – 14-15 June 2022 - AgroParisTech – **16h**
- Writing and publishing research papers [English] (26 October 2022) – **4,5h**
- Journée d'accueil des nouveaux doctorants - 21 November, 2022 – **7h**

- Bien démarrer sa mission d'enseignement 2023 en ANGLAIS - 07 December, 2023) Université Paris-Saclay - **7h**
- Writing Skills in Science 1 [Eng] online course - 09 January – 6 February, 2023 - **10h**-
- Veiller à la qualité de vie au travail : identifier et prévenir les violences sexistes et sexuelles, les discriminations et les risques psychosociaux – **5h**
- MOOC - Recherche reproductible : principes méthodologiques pour une science transparente – **24h**

Teaching (32h)

- Enseignement biologie L1 – Animal Biology, Cellular Biology, Biochemistry - 02 September 2023 - 14 July 2024 - Université Paris Saclay – ORSAY.- **32h**
- Supervising experience – Marta Catto (Master Thesis) – University of Udine – Italy – 2022
- Supervising experience – Tristan Paul – AgroParisTech

Total = 271,5h

List of publications

First author publications:

- **Léguillier Vincent**, Brahim Heddi, and Jasmina Vidic. 2024. "Recent Advances in Aptamer-Based Biosensors for Bacterial Detection" *Biosensors* 14, no. 5: 210. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14050210>
- **V. Léguillier**, D. Pinamonti, C.-M. Chang, Gujan, R. Mukherjee, H. Kumar, A. Cossetini, M. Manzano, J. Anba-Mondoloni, J. Malet-Villemagne, J. Vidic 2024 "A review and meta-analysis of Staphylococcus aureus prevalence in foods" *The Microbe*, 4 pp. 1-11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microb.2024.100131>

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Contributions to publications:

- Marco Marin, Francesco Rizzotto, **Vincent Léguillier**, Christine Péchoux, Elise Borezee-Durant, Jasmina Vidic, 2022, "Naked-eye detection of Staphylococcus aureus in powdered milk and infant formula using gold nanoparticles" *Journal of Microbiological Methods*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2022.106578>.
- Ivana Podunavac, Manil Kukkar, **Vincent Léguillier**, Francesco Rizzotto, Zoran Pavlovic, Ljiljana Janjušević, Vlad Costache, Vasa Radonic, Jasmina Vidic, 2022, "Low-cost goldleaf electrode as a platform for Escherichia coli immunodetection", *Talanta*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2023.124557>
- Mathilde Manceau, Carole Farre, Florence Lagarde, Raphaël Mathey, Arnaud Buhot, Jasmina Vidic, **Vincent Léguillier**, Yanxia Hou, and Carole Chaix, 2024, "Investigation of the Affinity of Aptamers for Bacteria by Surface Plasmon Resonance Imaging Using Nanosomes", *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 16 (23), 29645-29656, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.4c02355>

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